

Binomial Coefficients Triangular Type Selfie Numbers: Basic Operations

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

By **selfie numbers**, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, **basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers**, etc. These are by use of single variable. In two variables, we worked with **binomial coefficients type selfie numbers with basic operations, factorial and square-root**. This paper brings **binomial coefficient triangular type selfie numbers**, i.e., **binomial coefficients and triangular numbers** together. This is done by use of only **basic operations**. The work is in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. The work is up to 5-digits numbers.

Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients	3
2 Binomial Coefficients Triangular Type Selfie Numbers: Digit's Order	4
2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive	5
2.2 General Representations	8
3 Binomial Coefficients Triangular Type Selfie Numbers: Reverse Order of Digits	28
3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive	28
3.2 Symmetric and Non Consecutive	32
3.3 General Representations	33
4 Summary: Selfie Numbers	59
4.1 Permutable Powers	59
4.2 Basic Operations	60
4.3 Factorial	61
4.4 Square-Root	61
4.5 Factorial and Square-Root	62
4.6 Fibonacci Sequence	63
4.7 Triangular Numbers	64
4.8 Binomial Coefficients	65
4.9 S-gonal numbers	66
4.10 Centered Polygonal Numbers	67
4.11 Quadratic-Type Selfies	68
4.12 Cubic-Type Selfies	69

¹ Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com; **Web-sites:** <http://inderjtaneja.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

1 Introduction

Let's analyse historical aspects of some numbers:

- (i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer's error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [5]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2 \quad (1)$$

Actually it is not a **printer's error**, it represents a number in its own digits. The first number with similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but is in **reverse order**.

- (ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-175 [11]):

$$\begin{aligned} 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 \\ 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Above two are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**. Still there is another number with different property, i.e.,

$$27594 := 73 \times 9 \times 42 = 7 \times 3942 \quad (3)$$

In this case, the two expressions on right side of (4) are with same digits, but the total value is with different digits. This type of study is not under work.

- (iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [11] also gave an interesting property with factorials know by **sum of factorials**:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! \\ 2 &:= 2! \\ 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations, we observe that we are dealing with numbers those have same digits on both sides, where one side is number another with same digits with certain operations. Based on above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some studies in this direction can seen in the works of Friedman [6, 7] and Rose [2, 3, 4].

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** extending the idea of equation (2) using the operations of addition and subtraction with **factorial**:

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! & 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! \\ 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$80518 := 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8!$$

$$363239 := 36 + 323 + 9!$$

$$363269 := 363 + 26 + 9!$$

$$403199 := 40319 + 9!$$

$$317489 := -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!$$

$$352797 := -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7!$$

$$357592 := -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2!$$

$$357941 := 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!$$

$$361469 := 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9!$$

$$364292 := 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2!$$

$$397584 := -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4!$$

$$398173 := 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3!$$

$$408937 := -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7!$$

$$715799 := -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!$$

$$720599 := -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!$$

1.1 Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients

See below some examples written in **both ways**, **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$6435 := C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6)$$

$$15504 := C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1)$$

$$42504 := C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24)$$

$$54264 := C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4 + 5})!)$$

$$74613 := C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!)$$

$$12650 := C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!)$$

$$12870 := C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!)$$

$$14950 := C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!)$$

$$18564 := C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!)$$

$$19448 := C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8)$$

$$26334 := C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$43758 := C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8)$$

$$53130 := C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!).$$

$$28 := C(8, 2)$$

$$792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7)$$

$$924 := C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$2024 := C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!)$$

$$4845 := C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4)$$

$$00378 := C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!)$$

$$00792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!)$$

$$00924 := C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)).$$

The symbol C used for binomial coefficients is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

For more details refer author's work [22, 31]. Also refer [5, 11] for historical books on numbers. Some initial study on **selfie numbers** are given in [6, 7], and for extensions refer [2, 3, 4]. The last Section 4 is dedicated to the summary of **selfie numbers** done by author with different functions.

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **binomial coefficients**, **s-gonal values**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

Selfie numbers:

1. **Basic Operations**: [29];
2. **Factorial**: [26, 27];
3. **Square-root**: [14, 15];
4. **Factorial and Square-root**: [14, 15, 16];
5. **Fibonacci sequence**: [23, 24];
6. **Triangular numbers**: [21, 32, 33];
7. **Fibonacci and Triangular numbers**: [24];
8. **Binomial coefficients**: [22];
9. **Binomial coefficients: Fibonacci**: [31];
10. **Binomial coefficients: Triangular**: This work;
11. **S-gonal numbers**: [17];
12. **Centered Polygonal**: [17];
13. **Concatenation-Type**: [28];
14. **Quadratic numbers**: [25];
15. **Cubic numbers**: [29];

The last Section 4 is dedicated to summary of **selfie numbers** in different situations along with necessary references.

The aim of this paper is to bring **selfie numbers** by use of **binomial coefficients** and **Triangular numbers**. This can be done in three parts. One is by use of **basic operations**, second by use of **factorial** and third by use of **square-root**. This work is concentrated only with **basic operations**. The use of **factorial** and **square-root** shall be dealt elsewhere.

Remark 1.1. *Most of the **selfie numbers** appearing in the Sections below are with lot of extra brackets "(...)"*. These can be removed easily after making simplifications.

2 Binomial Coefficients Triangular Type Selfie Numbers: Digit's Order

This subsection brings **binomial coefficients triangular type selfie numbers** just with basic operations. The results are in reverse order of digits. The work is up to 5 digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and consecutive in blocks of 10. The second representations are for general way.

Remark 2.1. *In some cases, we don't need to write in terms of "C". The numbers can be written directly. See below:*

$$C(n, 1) := n \times 1;$$

$$C(n, n) := n/n.$$

For example, $C(8, 1) = 8 \times 1$ and $C(5, 5) := 5/5$. We kept them as they appeared in calculations.

2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$**1330** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 0$$

$$**1331** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 1$$

$$**1332** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 2$$

$$**1333** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 3$$

$$**1334** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 4$$

$$**1335** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 5$$

$$**1336** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 6$$

$$**1337** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 7$$

$$**1338** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 8$$

$$**1339** := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 9$$

$$**12420** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 0$$

$$**12421** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 1$$

$$**12422** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 2$$

$$**12423** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 3$$

$$**12424** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 4$$

$$**12425** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 5$$

$$**12426** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 6$$

$$**12427** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 7$$

$$**12428** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 8$$

$$**12429** := 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 9$$

$$**13230** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 0$$

$$**13231** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 1$$

$$**13232** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 2$$

$$**13233** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 3$$

$$**13234** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 4$$

$$**13235** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 5$$

$$**13236** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 6$$

$$**13237** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 7$$

$$**13238** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 8$$

$$**13239** := T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 9$$

$$**14630** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 0$$

$$**14631** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 1$$

$$**14632** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 2$$

$$**14633** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 3$$

$$**14634** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 4$$

$$**14635** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 5$$

$$**14636** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 6$$

$$**14637** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 7$$

$$**14638** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 8$$

$$**14639** := (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 9$$

$$**14850** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 0$$

$$**14851** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 1$$

$$**14852** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 2$$

$$**14853** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 3$$

$$**14854** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 4$$

$$**14855** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 5$$

$$**14856** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 6$$

$$**14857** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 7$$

$$**14858** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 8$$

$$**14859** := T(-1 + C(T(4), 8)) \times T(5) + 9$$

$$**21420** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 0$$

$$**21421** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 1$$

$$**21422** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 2$$

$$**21423** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 3$$

$$**21424** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 4$$

$$**21425** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 5$$

$$**21426** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 6$$

$$**21427** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 7$$

$$**21428** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 8$$

$$**21429** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 9$$

$$**21930** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 0$$

$$**21931** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 1$$

$$**21932** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 2$$

$$**21933** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 3$$

$$**21934** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 4$$

$$**21935** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 5$$

$$**21936** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 6$$

$$**21937** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 7$$

$$**21938** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 8$$

$$**21939** := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 9$$

$$**24840** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 0$$

$$**24841** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 1$$

$$**24842** := T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24843 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 3 \\ 24844 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 4 \\ 24845 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 5 \\ 24846 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 6 \\ 24847 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 7 \\ 24848 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 8 \\ 24849 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \times 4 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25620 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 0 \\ 25621 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 1 \\ 25622 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 2 \\ 25623 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 3 \\ 25624 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 4 \\ 25625 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 5 \\ 25626 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 6 \\ 25627 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 7 \\ 25628 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 8 \\ 25629 &:= (2 + T(T(5))) \times C(T(6), 2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25740 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 0 \\ 25741 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 1 \\ 25742 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 2 \\ 25743 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 3 \\ 25744 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 4 \\ 25745 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 5 \\ 25746 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 6 \\ 25747 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 7 \\ 25748 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 8 \\ 25749 &:= C(T(2) \times 5, 7) \times 4 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25920 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 0 \\ 25921 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 1 \\ 25922 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 2 \\ 25923 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 3 \\ 25924 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 4 \\ 25925 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 5 \\ 25926 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 6 \\ 25927 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 7 \\ 25928 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 8 \\ 25929 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(5)) \times C(9, 2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27930 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 0 \\ 27931 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 1 \\ 27932 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 2 \\ 27933 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 3 \\ 27934 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 4 \\ 27935 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 5 \\ 27936 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 6 \\ 27937 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 7 \\ 27938 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 8 \\ 27939 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(-7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28980 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 0 \\ 28981 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 1 \\ 28982 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 2 \\ 28983 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 3 \\ 28984 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 4 \\ 28985 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 5 \\ 28986 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 6 \\ 28987 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 7 \\ 28988 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 8 \\ 28989 &:= 28 \times T(T(C(9, 8))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33250 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 0 \\ 33251 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 1 \\ 33252 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 2 \\ 33253 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 3 \\ 33254 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 4 \\ 33255 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 5 \\ 33256 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 6 \\ 33257 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 7 \\ 33258 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 8 \\ 33259 &:= C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 25 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34220 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 0 \\ 34221 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 1 \\ 34222 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 2 \\ 34223 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 3 \\ 34224 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 4 \\ 34225 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 5 \\ 34226 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 6 \\ 34227 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 7 \\ 34228 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$34229 := T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + 9$$

$$38760 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 0$$

$$38761 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 1$$

$$38762 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 2$$

$$38763 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 3$$

$$38764 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 4$$

$$38765 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 5$$

$$38766 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 6$$

$$38767 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 7$$

$$38768 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 8$$

$$38769 := C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 9$$

$$42570 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 0$$

$$42571 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 1$$

$$42572 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 2$$

$$42573 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 3$$

$$42574 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 4$$

$$42575 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 5$$

$$42576 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 6$$

$$42577 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 7$$

$$42578 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 8$$

$$42579 := C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 9$$

$$44220 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 0$$

$$44221 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1$$

$$44222 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 2$$

$$44223 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 3$$

$$44224 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 4$$

$$44225 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5$$

$$44226 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 6$$

$$44227 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 7$$

$$44228 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8$$

$$44229 := T(T(4)) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9$$

$$48620 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 0$$

$$48621 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 1$$

$$48622 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 2$$

$$48623 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 3$$

$$48624 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 4$$

$$48625 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 5$$

$$48626 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 6$$

$$48627 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 7$$

$$48628 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 8$$

$$48629 := C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 9$$

$$55320 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 0$$

$$55321 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 1$$

$$55322 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 2$$

$$55323 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 3$$

$$55324 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 4$$

$$55325 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 5$$

$$55326 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 6$$

$$55327 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 7$$

$$55328 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 8$$

$$55329 := T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 9$$

$$67830 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 0$$

$$67831 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 1$$

$$67832 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 2$$

$$67833 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 3$$

$$67834 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 4$$

$$67835 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 5$$

$$67836 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 6$$

$$67837 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 7$$

$$67838 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 8$$

$$67839 := C(T(6), -T(7) + T(8))/3 + 9$$

$$68250 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 0$$

$$68251 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 1$$

$$68252 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 2$$

$$68253 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 3$$

$$68254 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 4$$

$$68255 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 5$$

$$68256 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 6$$

$$68257 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 7$$

$$68258 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 8$$

$$68259 := T(6) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 9$$

$$86240 := C(8, 6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 0$$

$$86241 := C(8, 6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$86242 := C(8, 6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 2$$

$$86243 := C(8, 6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86244 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\ 86245 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\ 86246 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 86247 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\ 86248 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 8 \\ 86249 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 95850 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 0 \\ 95851 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 1 \\ 95852 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 2 \\ 95853 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 3 \\ 95854 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 4 \\ 95855 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 5 \\ 95856 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 6 \\ 95857 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 95858 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 8 \\ 95859 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 96390 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 0 \\ 96391 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 1 \\ 96392 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 2 \\ 96393 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 3 \\ 96394 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 4 \\ 96395 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 5 \\ 96396 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 6 \\ 96397 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 7 \\ 96398 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 8 \\ 96399 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 General Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 231 &:= T(T(C((2 \times 3), 1))) \\ 241 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 246 &:= (C(T(T(2)), 4) + T(T(6))) \\ 351 &:= T((T(T(3)) + C(5, 1))) \\ 372 &:= -((T(3) - C(T(7), 2))) \\ 427 &:= (T(C(4, 2)) + T(T(7))) \\ 462 &:= C(-((T(4) - T(6))), T(T(2))) \\ 496 &:= T((C(T(4), 9) + T(6))) \\ 525 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times 5) \\ 687 &:= (T(6) + T(T(C(8, 7)))) \\ 741 &:= T((T(7) + T(C(4, 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1081 &:= T((C(10, 8) + 1)) \\ 1128 &:= T((C(11, 2) - 8)) \\ 1176 &:= T(((C(1, 1) + 7) \times 6)) \\ 1288 &:= (1 + C((T(T(T(2))) - 8), 8)) \\ 1329 &:= (-1 + C(T(T(3)), (2 \times 9))) \\ 1364 &:= (-1 + C(-((T(3) - T(6))), 4)) \\ 1483 &:= ((-1) + T(T(T(4)))) - C(8, 3) \\ 1533 &:= ((-1) + T(T(C(5, 3)))) - (T(3)) \\ 1535 &:= (T(T(C((1 \times 5), 3))) - (5)) \\ 1561 &:= (T(T(T(-((1 - 5)))))) + T(C(6, 1)) \\ 1582 &:= ((1 - T(5)) + T(C(8, T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1596 &:= T((1 + T(C(5, (9 - 6)))))) \\ 1826 &:= ((-1) + T(C(8, T(2)))) + T(T(6)) \\ 1832 &:= ((-2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times C(8, 1) \\ 1998 &:= (T((1 + C(9, 9))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 2226 &:= (T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) + (T((T(2) \times T(6)))))) \\ 2233 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))))) \\ 2259 &:= (-2) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 5)/9) \\ 2268 &:= ((C(T(2), 2) \times T(6)) \times T(8)) \\ 2278 &:= T(((C(T(2), 2) + T(7)) + T(8))) \\ 2284 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(-((T(2) - C(8, 4)))))) \\ 2353 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 2394 &:= ((-2) + T(T(3))) \times C(9, 4) \\ 2395 &:= (-C(T(T(2)), 3) + T((T(T(9))/T(5)))) \\ 2470 &:= -((C(T(T(2)), 4) - (T(70)))) \\ 2472 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times C(4, 2)) \\ 2481 &:= ((-1) + T(C(8, 4))) - T(2) \\ 2482 &:= (-T(2)) + T(C(8, C(4, T(2)))) \\ 2484 &:= ((T(2) - (4)) + T(C(8, 4))) \\ 2491 &:= (T(C(-((1 - 9)), 4)) + T(T(2))) \\ 2539 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))/T(T(3))) - T(9)) \\ 2541 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(C(5, 4))) + 1)) \\ 2584 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))/T(T(T(8/4)))) \\ 2629 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), 6)/T(T(T(2)))) + T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2646 &:= (C((T(2) + (6)), 4) \times T(6)) & 5228 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) - 8 \\
 2842 &:= ((T(2) + (4)) \times T(C(8, 2))) & 5233 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) - 3) + T(T(T(3)))) \\
 2922 &:= -((T(2) - C((T(2) \times 9), T(2)))) & 5236 &:= (C(T(5), (2 \times 3)) + T(T(6))) \\
 2922 &:= (C((T(2) \times 9), T(2)) - T(2)) & 5246 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(4)) + T(T(6))) \\
 2923 &:= (-2) + C((9 \times T(2)), 3) & 5250 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times 50) \\
 2925 &:= C((T(2) \times 9), -(2 - 5)) & 5328 &:= ((C(5, 3) - 2) \times T(T(8))) \\
 2928 &:= (2 + T((C(9, T(2)) - 8)) & 5356 &:= (C(T(5), T(3)) + T((5 + T(6)))) \\
 2955 &:= -(((T(2) + T(9)) - C(T(5), 5))) & 5444 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) - (4)) \times 4) \\
 2975 &:= (T(-(2 - C(9, 7))) \times 5) & 5445 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) \times 4) - T(5)) \\
 2997 &:= (T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - C(9, 7))) & 5634 &:= -((T((5 + T(6))) - C(T(T(3)), 4))) \\
 3272 &:= -(((T(3) - 2) - C(T(7), T(2)))) & 5635 &:= (C(T(5), 6) + T(35)) \\
 3273 &:= (-C(3, 2) + C(T(7), 3)) & 5671 &:= (C(T(5), 6) + T(T((7 + 1)))) \\
 3282 &:= (T(3) + C(28, T(2))) & 5678 &:= ((C(T(5), 6) + (7)) + T(T(8))) \\
 3324 &:= (3 + T((C(3, 2)^4)) & 5782 &:= (T(T(-(T(5) - T(7)))) + T(C(8, T(2)))) \\
 3325 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3)/2) \times 5) & 5964 &:= -((T((T(5) - 9)) - (C(T(6), 4)))) \\
 3328 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 3) - (-T(2)) \times T(T(8))) & 5979 &:= -((T(5) + (T(C(9, 7)) \times (-9)))) \\
 3353 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) - (C(T(T(3)), 5)))/(-T(3))) & 6162 &:= (T(T((C(6, 1) + 6))) \times 2) \\
 3432 &:= (C((3 + T(4)), T(3)) \times 2) & 6216 &:= (C(T(6), (T(2) + 1)) + T(T(6))) \\
 3459 &:= ((-T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) + C(T(5), 9)) & 6357 &:= -((T((6 + T(3))) - C(T(5), 7))) \\
 3462 &:= ((C(T(3), 4) \times T(T(6))) - T(2)) & 6358 &:= ((T(T(6)))/(-3) + C(T(5), 8)) \\
 3596 &:= (T(T(3)) - (-5 - T(C(9, 6)))) & 6524 &:= ((-T(6) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 3696 &:= ((T(3) \times T(6)) + T(C(9, 6))) & 6545 &:= ((-T(T(C(6, 5)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) \\
 3772 &:= (T((3 + T(7))) + (C(T(7), T(2)))) & 6864 &:= (C((T(6) - 8), 6) \times 4) \\
 3783 &:= ((3^7) + T(C(8, 3))) & 6975 &:= (T(-(6 - C(9, 7))) \times T(5)) \\
 3844 &:= (-T(3) + (C(8, 4) \times T(T(4)))) & 7315 &:= C((T(7) - T(3)), -(1 - 5)) \\
 3963 &:= (3 \times (-9) + C(T(6), 3)) & 7546 &:= (C((7 + T(5)), 4) + T(T(6))) \\
 3973 &:= ((-3) + T(T(7))) + (T(C(9, 3))) & 7596 &:= ((-T(C(7, 5))) - T(T(9))) \times (-6) \\
 4192 &:= (T(T((C(4, 1) + 9))) + T(T(2))) & 8526 &:= (T((C(8, 5)/2)) \times T(6)) \\
 4218 &:= (C(4, 2) \times T((1 + T(8)))) & 8658 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (T(C(6, 5)) - 8)) \\
 4241 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T((T(2) + T(C(4, 1))))) & 8673 &:= ((T(C(8, 6)) + (7)) \times T(T(3))) \\
 4257 &:= (-T(C(4, 2))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) & 8991 &:= ((T(8) - T(T(9))) \times (-C(9, 1))) \\
 4284 &:= ((T(C(T(4), 2)) + T(8)) \times 4) & 9324 &:= (C(9, 3) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\
 4359 &:= (C((T(4) + T(3)), 5) - 9) & 9342 &:= (9 \times (3 + T(C(T(4), 2)))) \\
 4465 &:= T(((T(4) \times T(4)) - C(6, 5))) & 9399 &:= (C(9, 3) - (T(T(9)) \times (-9))) \\
 4522 &:= (C((4 + T(5)), T(T(2)))/T(T(2))) & 9435 &:= ((T(9) \times C(T(4), T(3))) - T(5)) \\
 4535 &:= ((T(4) \times C(T(5), 3)) - T(5)) & 9445 &:= ((T(9) \times C(T(4), 4)) - (5)) \\
 4536 &:= (C(T(4), 5) \times (3 \times 6)) & 9856 &:= (T(98) + C(T(5), 6)) \\
 4543 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + C(T(5), T(C(4, 3)))) & & & \\
 4847 &:= (-4) + T((C(8, 4) + T(7))) & 10765 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times C(7, 6)) - (T(5))) \\
 5125 &:= (C(T(5), T((1 + 2))) + T(T(5))) & 10773 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - C(7, T(3))) \\
 & & 11223 &:= (T((T(11) + C(T(T(2)), T(2)))) \times 3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11437 &:= -((T((1+1)) - C((T(4) + T(3)), 7))) \\
 11439 &:= (-1) + C((T((1 \times 4)) + T(3)), 9) \\
 11550 &:= (T(T((C(1, 1) + 5))) \times 50) \\
 11625 &:= -((T((1+1)) - C((T(6) - 2), 5))) \\
 11628 &:= C((-((1+1)) + T(6)), -((T(2) - 8))) \\
 11672 &:= ((1 + C(16, 7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \\
 11773 &:= (-1) + ((1 + T(7)) \times T(T(C(7, T(3)))))) \\
 11988 &:= (((C(1, 1) + 9) + 8) \times T(T(8))) \\
 12225 &:= ((-1) + C((T(T(2)) \times T(2)), T(2))) \times T(5) \\
 12243 &:= (T(T(T((1+2)))) \times (-2) + T(T(C(4, 3)))) \\
 12255 &:= ((1 + C((T(T(2)) \times T(2)), T(5))) \times T(5)) \\
 12256 &:= -((T(T((-1) + T(T(2)))) - C((2 + T(5)), 6))) \\
 12339 &:= ((C((-1) + T(T(T(2))))), 3) + T(T(T(3))) \times 9 \\
 12368 &:= (C((-1) + (T(2) \times T(3))), 6) - 8 \\
 12371 &:= ((C(17, T(3)) - T(T(2))) + 1) \\
 12586 &:= (-((1 - (2^5))) \times T(C(8, 6))) \\
 12644 &:= -((T((1+2)) - C((T(6) + (4)), 4))) \\
 12646 &:= ((-1) - T(2)) + C((T(6) + (4)), T(6)) \\
 12651 &:= (C((-((1-5)) + T(6)), T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \\
 12665 &:= (C(-((1-26)), T(6)) + T(5)) \\
 12683 &:= -((T((1 + T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(6)) \times (-C(8, 3)))) \\
 12705 &:= (T(T((1 + T(2)))) \times T(C(7, 05))) \\
 12752 &:= (12 + (T(7) \times C(T(5), T(2)))) \\
 12835 &:= (1 + (T(2) \times T((-C(8, T(3))) + T(T(5)))))) \\
 12885 &:= (C(((1 \times 2) \times 8), 8) + T(5)) \\
 12936 &:= (C(((1-2) + 9), 3) \times T(T(6))) \\
 12937 &:= (1 + (C((2+9), T(3)) \times T(7))) \\
 13273 &:= (1 + (T(T(3)) \times (2 + T(C(7, 3)))))) \\
 13287 &:= ((1 - C(T(T(3)), T(2))) + (T(8) \times T(T(7)))) \\
 13310 &:= ((-1) - C(T(T(3)), 3)) \times (-10) \\
 13319 &:= (-1) + (C(T(3), 3) \times T(T(-((1-9)))))) \\
 13334 &:= ((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) - (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) / (-4)) \\
 13427 &:= ((13 \times T(C(T(4), 2))) - T(7)) \\
 13499 &:= (-1) + (T((C(T(3), 4) + 9)) \times T(9)) \\
 13546 &:= (1 + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) / 4) - (T(6)))) \\
 13574 &:= (1 + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T(7)) / 4)) \\
 13624 &:= (((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) - (C(T(6), T(T(2)))) / (-4)) \\
 13648 &:= ((C(13, 6) - T(4)) \times 8) \\
 13671 &:= (T((-1) + (3 \times T(6))) \times C(7, 1)) \\
 13922 &:= (-1) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(C(9, 2)) - T(2))) \\
 13973 &:= (-13) + (T(C(9, 7)) \times T(T(3))) \\
 13976 &:= -((T((1+3)) - (T(C(9, 7)) \times T(6)))) \\
 13978 &:= ((T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T(C(9, 7))) - 8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13985 &:= (-1) + (T(T(3)) \times T(C(9, (-8) + T(5)))) \\
 13987 &:= (1 + (T(T(3)) \times T(C(C(9, 8), 7)))) \\
 14292 &:= ((1 \times 4) \times (T(2) + T(C(9, T(2)))))) \\
 14293 &:= (1 - (-4) \times (T(2) + T(C(9, 3)))) \\
 14345 &:= ((-1) \times T(T(4))) + (T(C(T(3), 4)) \times T(T(5))) \\
 14385 &:= ((-1) - (C(T(4), 3) \times (-8))) \times T(5) \\
 14391 &:= ((T((1 + T(T(4)))) + 3) \times C(9, 1)) \\
 14448 &:= ((T((1 + T(T(4)))) + (C(T(4), 4))) \times 8) \\
 14485 &:= ((14 \times T(C(T(4), 8))) - 5) \\
 14535 &:= (C((14+5), 3) \times T(5)) \\
 14558 &:= ((-1) + C(T(4), 5)) \times 58 \\
 14642 &:= 1 + (T(4) - T(6))^{C(4, T(2))} \\
 14648 &:= ((-1) - T((4 \times C(6, 4)))) \times (-8) \\
 14783 &:= (-1) + (T((4 + T(7))) \times C(8, T(3))) \\
 14875 &:= ((C(14, 8) - T(7)) \times 5) \\
 15312 &:= (T((1 + C(5, 3))) \times (1 + T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 15344 &:= (-1) + ((T(T(C(5, 3))) \times T(4)) - T(T(4))) \\
 15459 &:= (C(((1 \times 5) \times 4), 5) - T(9)) \\
 15479 &:= (-1) + (T(T(5)) \times (C(T(4), 7) + 9)) \\
 15497 &:= ((C((1+5), 4) \times T(T(9))) - T(7)) \\
 15505 &:= (1 + C((5 + T(5)), 05)) \\
 15524 &:= (-1) + (T(5) \times T((T(C(5, 2)) - T(4)))) \\
 15525 &:= (T(C(((1 \times 5) + 5), 2)) \times T(5)) \\
 15576 &:= (((-1) + C(T(5), 5)) - T(T(7))) \times 6 \\
 15631 &:= (((1 \times 5)^6) + T(C(3, 1))) \\
 15682 &:= ((1 + (5^6)) + C(8, T(2))) \\
 15745 &:= ((-1) + (5 \times T(C(7, 4)))) \times 5 \\
 15824 &:= -((T((1 + T(5))) + (T(C(8, T(2))) \times (-T(4)))) \\
 15876 &:= ((T((1 + 5)) \times T(C(8, 7))) \times T(6)) \\
 15939 &:= (C((-1) + T(5) + 9), 3) \times 9 \\
 15968 &:= ((C((-1) + T(5)), 9) - (6)) \times 8 \\
 16355 &:= ((C(T((1+6)), 3) - (5)) \times 5) \\
 16456 &:= ((1 + T(C(6, 4))) \times T((-5) + T(6))) \\
 16539 &:= (C((-1) + T(6)), (5 \times 3)) + T(T(9)) \\
 16549 &:= ((C((-1) + T(6)), 5) + T(4)) + T(T(9)) \\
 16575 &:= ((-1) - T(T(C(6, 5)))) + (7^5) \\
 16594 &:= ((C((-1) + T(6)), 5) + T(T(9))) + T(T(4)) \\
 16653 &:= ((1 + C((6+6), 5)) \times T(T(3))) \\
 16842 &:= ((T(16) + T(T(8))) \times T(C(4, 2))) \\
 17136 &:= (C((17+1), 3) \times T(6)) \\
 17432 &:= (C(17, T(4)) - T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) \\
 17437 &:= ((T(C((1+7), 4)) + T(3)) \times 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17475 &:= (C((-1) + T(7)), 4) - 75 \\ 17495 &:= (C((-1) + T(7)), 4) - T(T((9 - 5))) \\ 17496 &:= (C((-1) + T(7)), 4) - ((9 \times 6)) \\ 17529 &:= ((C(17, 5) \times T(2)) - T(T(9))) \\ 17545 &:= (C(((1 - T(T(7)))/(-T(5))), 4) - (5)) \\ 17574 &:= (C(T(-((1 - 7))), 5) - (T(74))) \\ 17653 &:= -((T((1 + T(7))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))/(-3))) \\ 17723 &:= (-1) - (-T(7) \times (T(C(7, T(2))) + 3)) \\ 17835 &:= (T((1 + T(7))) \times (C(8, 3) - T(5))) \\ 17836 &:= (T((1 \times 7)) \times (T(C(8, T(3))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 17862 &:= (((-1) + T(7)) \times T(T(8))) - (T(C(6, 2))) \\ 17935 &:= ((-17) - T(C(9, 3))) \times (-5) \\ 17976 &:= (((-1) + T(7)) \times T(C(9, 7))) - (6) \\ 18234 &:= (C(18, T(T(2))) + (-T(3)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 18264 &:= (C(18, T(T(2))) - T((6 \times 4))) \\ 18292 &:= ((1 + (T(C(8, 2)) \times T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\ 18297 &:= (-1) + ((T(C(8, 2)) \times T(9)) + T(7)) \\ 18333 &:= (C(18, T(3)) - T(T((3 + 3)))) \\ 18336 &:= ((C(18, T(3)) + 3) - T(T(6))) \\ 18343 &:= ((C(18, T(3)) + T(4)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 18344 &:= (C(18, T(3)) - (4 \times T(T(4)))) \\ 18354 &:= (C(18, T(3)) - T((5 \times 4))) \\ 18375 &:= (T((C((1 \times 8), 3) - 7)) \times T(5)) \\ 18519 &:= (C(18, (5 + 1)) - T(9)) \\ 18525 &:= ((1 + C(8, 5)) \times T(25)) \\ 18528 &:= (C(18, T((5 - 2))) - T(8)) \\ 18536 &:= -((T(-((1 - 8))) - C((T(5) + 3), 6)) \\ 18543 &:= (C(18, (T(T(5))/T(4))) - T(T(3))) \\ 18554 &:= (C(18, T((T(5)/5))) - T(4)) \\ 18557 &:= (C(18, T((T(5)/5))) - (7)) \\ 18558 &:= (C(18, 5) + (T(5) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 18562 &:= (C(18, -((T(5) - T(6)))) - 2) \\ 18563 &:= (-1) + C(((8 - 5) \times 6), T(3)) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, T(((5 - 6) + 4))) \\ 18574 &:= (C(18, (5 + 7)) + T(4)) \\ 18609 &:= (C(18, 6) + T(09)) \\ 18619 &:= (C(18, 6) + T((1 + 9))) \\ 18642 &:= (C(18, 6) + T((T(4) + 2))) \\ 18647 &:= ((C(18, 6) + T(T(4))) + T(7)) \\ 18649 &:= (1 + (C(8, 6) \times T((4 \times 9)))) \\ 18729 &:= ((1 + T((C(8, 7)^2))) \times 9) \\ 18752 &:= (-1) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(7))) - (C(T(5), 2))) \\ 18872 &:= (((1 \times 8) + T(T(8))) \times T(C(7, T(T(2)))))) \\ 18873 &:= (1 - ((-8) - T(T(8))) \times T(C(7, T(3)))) \\ 18942 &:= (((1 + T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(C(4, 2)))) \\ 18981 &:= (T((1 + T(8))) \times (-9) + T(C(8, 1))) \\ 18981 &:= (T((1 + T(8))) \times (-9) + T(C(8, 1))) \\ 19227 &:= (-1) - (C((T(9) - T(T(T(2))))), T(T(2)))/(-7)) \\ 19237 &:= (1 - ((T(C(9, 2)) + T(T(3))) \times (-T(7)))) \\ 19265 &:= -((T((1 + T(9))) + (T(2) - C(T(6), 5))) \\ 19278 &:= (T(-((1 - C(9, 2)))) - (-T(7) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 19313 &:= ((-1) - T(T(9))) + C(T(T(3)), (-1) + T(3)) \\ 19314 &:= ((-1) \times T(T(9))) + C(T(T(3)), (1 + 4)) \\ 19315 &:= ((1 - T(T(9))) + C(T(T(3)), (1 \times 5))) \\ 19321 &:= (1 - (-C(9, 3)) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1)) \\ 19335 &:= (((-1) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), 5) \\ 19353 &:= -((T((-1) + T(9))) - (C(T(T(3)), 5) - (T(3)))) \\ 19359 &:= (T((1 \times 9)) + (C(T(T(3)), 5) - T(T(9)))) \\ 19372 &:= ((1 - 9) + (C(T(T(3)), 7)/T(T(2)))) \\ 19396 &:= ((1 - 9) + (T(T(T(3))) \times C(9, 6))) \\ 19455 &:= ((C(19, 4) + T(5)) \times 5) \\ 19467 &:= (19 + C((-4) + T(6)), 7) \\ 19632 &:= (((1 + C(9, 6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(2)) \\ 19635 &:= ((1 + C(9, 6)) \times T((T(3) + T(5)))) \\ 19636 &:= (1 - ((-C(9, 6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(6))) \\ 19765 &:= -(((T((-1) + T(9))) - T(T(7))) - (C(T(6), 5))) \\ 19798 &:= (19 \times (7 + T(T(C(9, 8)))))) \\ 19853 &:= (-1) - (-9) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(C(5, 3)))) \\ 20265 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(02)) + (T(6))) \times T(5)) \\ 20325 &:= ((-T(2)) - T(T(03))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 5) \\ 20328 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + (0 - C(T(T(3))), -(T(2) - 8)))) \\ 20335 &:= ((-20) + T(3)) + C(T(T(3)), 5) \\ 20343 &:= -((T(T(2)) - C(T(T(03))), (T(4) + T(3)))) \\ 20346 &:= (-T(2)) + C(T(T(03)), (T(4) + (6))) \\ 20349 &:= C(T((2 \times 03)), -(4 - 9)) \\ 20351 &:= (2 - (C(T(T(03)), 5) \times (-1))) \\ 20352 &:= (C(T((2 \times 03)), 5) + T(2)) \\ 20353 &:= (-2) + (C(T(T(03)), 5) + (T(3))) \\ 20355 &:= (T(T(2)) - (0 - C((T(3) + T(5)), 5))) \\ 20357 &:= (-20) + (C(T(T(3)), 5) + T(7)) \\ 20425 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) - (0 - T(T(4)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 5) \\ 20447 &:= (C(T((T(2) - (0 - 4))), 4) - T(7)) \\ 20474 &:= ((T(2) + (0 - 4)) + C(T(7), 4)) \\ 20475 &:= (T((T(20) - C(T(4), 7))) \times 5) \\ 20565 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), 05) + (T(T(6)) - (T(5)))) \\ 20573 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), 05) - 7) + T(T(T(3))))$$

- 20574 := -((T(T(T(2))) - (T(T(05)) + (C(T(7), 4))))
20625 := (T((2 + T(06))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 5))
20735 := ((-20) + T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), 5)
20931 := ((20 × T(T(9))) + T(T(T(C(3, 1))))
20979 := (T(T(T(2))) × ((0 - C(9, 7)) + T(T(9))))
20995 := (C(T(T(T(2))), 09) / (9 + 5))
21394 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (-1) + T(3))) + (T(T(9)) + T(4))
21396 := (T(T(2)) × -((1 + 3)) + T(C(9, 6)))
21482 := -((T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)) + (-T(C(T(4), 8))) × T(T(T(2))))
21495 := (C(T((T(T(2)) + 1)), 4) + ((T(T(9)) - T(5))))
21729 := (-T((2 + 1)) - (-C(7, 2) × T(T(9))))
21732 := ((T(T((C(2, 1) + 7))) × T(T(3))) - T(2))
21832 := -((T(T((T(T(2)) - 1))) - (C(8, T(3))^{T(2)}))
21861 := ((T(T(2)) + T(T((1 + 8)))) × T(C(6, 1)))
21882 := (T(2) + ((C(18, 8) / 2))
21925 := ((T(T(2)) × T((1 + C(9, T(2)))) - 5)
21966 := (T(T(2)) × (T((1 + C(9, 6))) + 6))
22052 := (2 + (T(20) × C(T(5), 2)))
22155 := ((T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) + 1) × (T(T(5)) - T(5)))
22162 := (T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) + ((T((1 + 6))^{T(2)}))
22274 := (-C((2^{T(2)}), T(2))) + (T(T(7)) × T(T(4)))
22319 := (-C(2, 2) + (T(31) × T(9)))
22324 := -((T(T(2)) + (-T(C((2³), 2))) × T(T(4))))
22344 := (T(C((2^{T(2)}), 3)) × (T(4) + 4))
22372 := ((C(T(T(2)), T(2)) × T(T(3))) + ((T(7))^{T(2)}))
22379 := -((T(T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 3) × (T(7) - T(9))))
22433 := ((2 + C(24, T(3))) / T(3))
22484 := ((C(T((2 + T(2))), T(4)) × 8) - T(T(T(4))))
22525 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) - 5) × (2 + T(5)))
22562 := ((2 + C(T(T(T(2))), 5)) + T(T((T(T(6)) / T(T(T(2))))))
22563 := ((T(2) + C(T(T(T(2))), 5)) + T(T((T(T(6)) / T(T(3))))))
22565 := (T(T((T(T(T(T(2))) / T(T(T(2)))))) - (-5 - C(T(6), 5)))
22566 := (T(T(2)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + T(66))
22589 := -((T(T(T(2))) + (C((T(T(2)) + T(5))), 8) / (-9))
22595 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), (T(2) + 5)) / 9) - T(5))
22635 := (-C(T(2), 2) × (T(T(6)) - ((T(3))⁵)))
22674 := -((T(T(2)) - ((T((2 + 6)) × T(C(7, 4))))))
22680 := ((C(2, 2) + 6) × T(80))
22684 := ((C(T((2 + T(2))), 6) + T(T(8))) × 4)
22756 := (C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + (T(T(7)) × 56))
22769 := (-C(2, 2) - (-((T(7) - 6)) × T(T(9))))
22791 := (T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(2)) - T(7)) × T(T(C(9, 1))))
22841 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - (C(T(T(T(2))), 8) / (-T(4) - 1))
22854 := -(((T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) + T(8)) + (-T(5) × T(T(T(4))))))
22869 := (((C(T(2), 2) + 8) × T(T(6))) × 9)
22892 := ((T(T(2)) + (C((2 × 8), 9))) × 2)
22895 := ((2 × C((2 × 8), 9)) + T(5))
22911 := ((C(T(T(2)), T(2)) × T(T(9))) + T(T(11)))
22962 := ((T(T(2)) × T((T(2) + (C(9, 6)))) - T(T(2)))
22964 := ((T(T(2)) × T((T(2) + (C(9, 6)))) - 4)
22966 := (-2) - (T((T(2) + (C(9, 6)))) × (-6))
22979 := -((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + (-9) × T((T(7) + T(9))))))
23229 := (((C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) / T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) × 9)
23235 := -((T(T(T(2))) - (T(3) × C((-2) + T(T(3))), T(5))))
23245 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), (T(T(3)) / T(2))) - T(T(4))) / 5)
23246 := -((C(T(T(T(2))), 3) - (T(T(2)) × (4⁶)))
23252 := (2 × (C((T(T(3)) - 2), 5) - 2))
23253 := (-T(2) - (C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(5)) × (-T(3))))
23256 := (C((-2) + T((3 × 2))), T(5)) × 6
23282 := (C(T(T(T(2))), 3) + ((28)^{T(2)}))
23292 := (((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) / 2) - C(9, 2))
23296 := (C(T(T(T(2))), 3) + ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(9))) + T(T(6))))
23351 := (T((T(T(T(T(2)))) / 3)) + ((C(T(T(3)), 5) - 1))
23385 := ((C((T(2)³), 3) × 8) - T(5))
23435 := (C(T(T(2)), 3) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(3)))) × (-T(5))))
23454 := -((T(T(2)) + ((C(T(T(3)), 4) - T(T(5))) × (-4)))
23464 := (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - ((T(T(T(4))) × T(6)) - T(T(T(4))))
23493 := -((T(2) - (T(3) × T((4 + C(9, 3))))))
23496 := ((2 × 3) × T((4 + C(9, 6))))
23526 := (-((T(2))^{T(3)}) - (-C(T(5), 2) × T(T(6))))
23527 := -((T(T(T(2))) + ((-3) - T(C(5, 2))) × T(T(7))))
23538 := (-T(2) - (T(T(3)) × (-C(T(5), 3) - T(T(8))))))
23541 := ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(3))) + (T(5) × T(T(T(C(4, 1))))))
23751 := C(-((2 - 3) + T(7)), (5 - 1))
23754 := (T(2) + C(((T(3) + T(7)) - 5), 4))
23758 := (T(C(T(T(2)), 3)) + (T(T(7)) × 58))
23786 := -((C(T(T(T(2))), 3) - (T(7) × (T(T(8)) + T(T(6))))))
23892 := ((T(T((2³))) × T(8)) - (C(9, T(2))))
23928 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(3) × T(C(9, 2))) - 8))
23973 := ((T((2³)) × T(C(9, 7))) - 3)
23976 := (T((2³)) × T(C(9, C(7, 6))))
23978 := ((T(T(2)) / 3) + ((T(C(9, 7)) × T(8))))
24024 := (T(2) × C((4⁰2), T(4)))
24084 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), 4) + T(08)) × 4)

- 26226** := $(T(T(2)) \times T((C(6,2) + T((2 \times 6))))$
26243 := $((T(2) \times (T(6)^{T(2)}) - T(T(T(C(4,3))))$
26252 := $(2 + (C(T(6),2) \times (5^{T(2)})))$
26253 := $(T(2) + (C(T(6),2) \times (5^3)))$
26271 := $(T(2) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(C(7,1))))$
26279 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(C(6,2))) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(9))))$
26292 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (C(T(6), T(2)) - T((9 + T(2))))$
26297 := $((C((T(T(2)) + (T(6))), T(2)) \times 9) - T(7))$
26315 := $((2 - T(6)) + C((T(T(3)) + 1), 5))$
26328 := $((T(T((2 \times 6))) + T(C(T(3), T(2)))) \times 8)$
26335 := $(C(T(T(2)),6) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(3) - T(T(5))))$
26362 := $((T(T(T(-(2 - 6)))) - (C(T(T(3)),6)))/(-2))$
26362 := $((T(T(T(-(2 - 6)))) - (C(T(T(3)),6)))/(-2))$
26376 := $((T(2) \times C(T(6),3)) + T(T(7))) \times 6)$
26442 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(6) \times C(T(4),4) - T(2)))$
26525 := $((T((T(2) + T(6))) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \times 5)$
26535 := $(((-2) + T(T(6))) + T(T(C(5,3)))) \times T(5)$
26628 := $(2 \times (-6) + (C(6, T(2)) \times T(T(8))))$
26649 := $((T(T((2 \times 6))) - (T(C(6,4)))) \times 9)$
26824 := $((T((2 \times T(6))) \times C(8,2)) + T(T(T(4))))$
26827 := $((C(T(T(T(2))),6) - (T(T(8))))/2) + (T(7))$
26874 := $((T(2)^6 \times T(8)) + T(C(7,4)))$
26910 := $(26 \times T(T((C(9,1) + 0)))$
26911 := $((26 \times T(T(9))) + C(1,1))$
26931 := $((26 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(C(3,1))))$
26936 := $(26 \times (T(T(9)) + C(T(3),6)))$
26942 := $-((T((-2) + T(6)) - C((9 + T(4)), T(T(2))))$
26973 := $((-T(2)^6) \times (-9 - T(C(7, T(3))))$
27027 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (C(T(7), T(02))/T(7)))$
27126 := $(C((-2) + T((7 - 1))), T(T(2)) - (6))$
27131 := $(C((-2) + T((7 - 1))), T(3)) - 1)$
27132 := $(C((-2) + T((7 - 1))), (3 \times 2))$
27168 := $(C((-2) + T((7 - 1))), 6) + T(8)$
27174 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(7) + 1)) + (C(T(7),4)))$
27231 := $((2 + T(7))^{T(2)} + T(T(T(C(3,1))))$
27251 := $((-2) + T(C(7,2))) \times (T(T(5)) - 1)$
27265 := $-((C(T(-(2 - 7))), T(2)) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))))$
27272 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(C(7, T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times 2)$
27272 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(C(7, T(2)))) + (T(T(7)))) \times 2)$
27276 := $((C(T(T(T(2))),7) - ((T(T(2))^7)))/(-6))$
27288 := $(2 \times ((C(T(7),2) \times T(8)) + T(8)))$
27321 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(7)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) - 1))$
27332 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) - C(T(T(3)), T(3)))/(-2))$
27335 := $(T((2 \times C(7,3))) \times (T(3) + (5)))$
27356 := $(-C((2 \times 7),3) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))))$
27360 := $(T(T(2)) \times T((C(7,3) + 60)))$
27372 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((C(T(7), T(3))/T(7)))) \times 2)$
27372 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + ((C(T(7), T(3))/T(7)))) \times 2)$
27442 := $(2 - (T(7) \times (T(T(4)) - T(C(T(4),2))))$
27483 := $(T((-2) + T(7)) + C((T(T(4)) - T(8)), T(3)))$
27544 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(C(7,5))) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))))$
27594 := $((T((T(2) \times 7)) \times T(T(5))) - C(9,4))$
27596 := $(2 - ((T(T(7)) - C(T(5),9)) \times 6))$
27636 := $((-(2 \times 7) + C(T(6),3)) \times T(6))$
27664 := $((-2) \times T(7) - (T(T(6)) \times (-T(C(6,4))))$
27665 := $-((T((T(2) + C(7,6))) - (T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))))$
27729 := $((2 + 7) \times T(T((C(7,2) - 9))))$
27756 := $(C((2 + 7),7) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))))$
27834 := $((T(T(2))^7 - T(C(8,3)))/T(4))$
27925 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), T(-(7 - 9))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 5)$
27941 := $((27 \times T(T(9))) - C(4,1))$
27944 := $((27 \times T(T(9))) - C(4,4))$
27971 := $((T(T(2)) \times (7 \times T(C(9,7)))) - 1)$
27972 := $((2 \times 7) \times T(C(9,7))) \times T(2)$
27972 := $((2 \times 7) \times T(C(9,7))) \times T(2)$
27973 := $((27 \times T(T(9))) + T(C(7, T(3))))$
27974 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + C((T(9) - T(7)), T(4)))$
27981 := $((27 \times T(T(9))) + T(C(8,1)))$
28222 := $(-2) + ((C(8, T(2)) \times T(2))^2)$
28299 := $-((T(T(2)) + ((-T(C(8,2))) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(9))))$
28328 := $((T(T((T(2) + 8))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)))) \times 8)$
28336 := $((T(T(2)) + 8) \times C((3 + T(T(3))), T(6)))$
28417 := $(-T(2) + (C(8,4) \times T(T((1 \times 7))))$
28418 := $(-2) + (C(8,4) \times T(T(-(1 - 8))))$
28423 := $(T(2) + (C(8,4) \times T(T((T(T(T(2)))/3))))$
28424 := $-((T(T(2)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-C(T(4),2)))) - T(T(T(4))))$
28492 := $(2 + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(4))))/C(9,2)))$
28562 := $(2 - (-8) \times T(C((T(5) - 6), T(2))))$
28563 := $(T(2) - (-8) \times T(C((T(5) - 6), 3)))$
28566 := $(T(T(2)) - (-8) \times T(C((T(5) - 6), 6)))$
28593 := $((T(T(2)) \times T(C(8,5))) - (T(9))) \times 3)$
28596 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((-8) + C(T(5),9)) - T(T(6)))$
28623 := $-(((T(2) - T(8)) - C(T(6), T(2))) \times T(T(3)))$
28645 := $((-(2^8) + C(T(6),4)) \times 5)$

- 28654 := -(((T(2) + 8) - (T(6) × C(T(5), 4))))
- 28689 := -(((T(T(T(2))) + ((-C(8, 6) + T(T(8))) × (-T(9))))))
- 28694 := -(((T(T(2)) + (-C(8, 6) × (T(T(9)) - T(4))))))
- 28745 := (((C(T(T(T(2))), 8)/7) - (T((T(4) + T(5))))))
- 28836 := (T(2) × (T(8) + (T(C(8, 3)) × 6)))
- 28973 := ((28 × T(T(9))) - C(7, T(3)))
- 29172 := (T((T(T(2)) + (T(9)))) × (1 + C(7, 2)))
- 29176 := (((T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 1) × T(C(7, 6)))
- 29183 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(9)) - 1) × (-C(8, T(3)))))
- 29235 := ((T((2 × 9)²) - C(T(3), 5))
- 29245 := ((C((T(2) × 9), T(2)) × T(4)) - (5))
- 29295 := (((T(2) × T(C(9, 2))) - T(9)) × T(5))
- 29372 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), 9)/(3 + 7)) - T(T(T(2))))
- 29382 := ((C((2 × 9), 3) × T(8)) + T(T(2)))
- 29393 := (C(T(T(T(2))), 9)/T(((3 + 9)/3)))
- 29413 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), 9)/T(4)) + (-1 + T(T(3))))
- 29421 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), 9)/T(4)) + T((T(T(2)) + 1)))
- 29425 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), 9)/T(4)) + (2⁵))
- 29444 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), 9)/T(4)) + (-4 + T(T(4))))
- 29512 := ((T(T(T(T(2)))) × C(9, 5)) + T(T((1 + T(T(2)))))
- 29562 := (((2 + C(9, 5)) × T(T(6))) - T(T(2)))
- 29564 := (((2 + C(9, 5)) × T(T(6))) - (4))
- 29592 := ((2 + T((T(9) - (5)))) × C(9, 2))
- 29592 := ((2 + T((T(9) - (5)))) × C(9, 2))
- 29646 := (T(T(2)) × (-9) + T((T(C(6, 4)) - T(6))))
- 29697 := -(((T(2) + (T(9) × (6 - T(C(9, 7)))))))
- 29745 := ((T(2) - (-C(9, 7) × T(T(4)))) × T(5))
- 29750 := (T(-((2 - C(9, 7)))) × 50)
- 29891 := (2 - (-9) × T((T(8) + T(C(9, 1)))))
- 29892 := (T(2) - (-C(9, 8) × T((9²))))
- 29892 := (T(2) - (-C(9, 8) × T((9²))))
- 29931 := ((T(T(2)) × T(99)) + T(T(T(C(3, 1))))
- 29964 := -(((T(T(2)) - ((T(9) × T(C(9, (6 - 4)))))))
- 29968 := (-2) - (-T(9) × T(C(9, -((6 - 8)))))
- 29971 := (2 + ((T(9) × T(C(9, 7))) - 1))
- 29974 := -(((T(T(2)) - (((T(9) × T(C(9, 7))) + T(4))))))
- 29976 := (T(T(2)) + ((T(9) × T(C(9, C(7, 6))))))
- 29977 := -(((T(T(T(2))) - (((T(9) × T(C(9, 7))) + T(7))))))
- 29981 := ((2 + 9) - (-T(9) × T(T(C(8, 1)))))
- 29987 := ((29 × T(T(C(9, 8)))) - T(7))
- 29991 := (T(T(T(2))) - (-T(9) × T((T(9) - C(9, 1)))))
- 29997 := ((T(2) × 9) + (T(9) × T(C(9, 7))))
- 30288 := (C(T(T(3)), T(T(02))) + (T(T(8)) × (-T(8))))
- 31395 := ((C(T((T(3) - 1), 3) × T(T(9)))/T(5))
- 31542 := (T(T(3)) × ((-1) - C(T(5), T(4)))/(-2))
- 31564 := ((T(3) × (-1) + C(T(5), 6)) + T(T(T(4))))
- 31575 := ((T(3) - 1) × (C(T(5), 7) - T(T(5))))
- 31625 := (T((T(T(3)) + 1) × (T(C(6, 2)) + (5))))
- 31779 := (C(-((3 × (1 - 7))), 7) - T(9))
- 31818 := -((T(3) - C(18, -((1 - 8))))
- 31821 := (-3) + C(18, (T(T(2)) + 1))
- 31824 := C((T((3 + 1)) + 8), (T(2) + (4)))
- 31845 := (T(T(3)) + (C(18, (-4) + T(5))))
- 31941 := (-T(T(3))) × (19 - T(T(T(C(4, 1))))))
- 32175 := (C(T((3 + 2)), (1 × 7)) × 5)
- 32234 := (C(T(3), T(2)) - (T(T(T(2))) × (T(3) - T(T(T(4))))))
- 32235 := (T(T(3)) × (C(22, 3) - 5))
- 32292 := (C((3^{T(2)}), 2) × 92)
- 32312 := (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - (T((T(3) + 1))^{T(2)}))
- 32335 := ((T(T(3)) × T(T(C((2 + 3), 3)))) - (5))
- 32352 := ((T(3) × 2) + (T(T(3)) × T(T(C(5, 2))))
- 32382 := (T(T(3)) × (2 + T(C((3 + 8), 2))))
- 32403 := ((C(3, 2) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(T(03)))
- 32454 := (-T(3)) + ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(C(5, 4))))
- 32531 := (-((T(3) - (2^{T(5)}))) - T(T(T(C(3, 1))))
- 32536 := -((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)}) - C(T(3), 6))))
- 32543 := ((T(3) + (2^{T(C(5, 4))})) - T(T(T(3))))
- 32593 := ((C((T(T(3)) + 2), 5) - T(T(9))) - T(T(3)))
- 32645 := (-((3 - (2^{C(6, 4)}))) - T(T(5)))
- 32689 := (((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) × T(6))/T(8)) + T(T(9)))
- 32724 := -(((T(3)²) - (C(T(7), T(2)) × T(4)))
- 32727 := (C((T(3) × T(2)), 7) + T((T(T(2)) × 7)))
- 32734 := -((T(3) - ((-2) + C(T(7), 3)) × T(4)))
- 32745 := (((C(3, 2)⁷) - 4) × T(5))
- 32747 := -((T(T(3)) - ((2^{T(C(7, 4)/7}))))
- 32752 := -(((T(3) + 2) - (C(T(7), 5)/T(2))))
- 32753 := ((T((3 × 2) - C(T(7), 5)))/(-3))
- 32769 := (C((T(3) × T(2)), 7) + (T(6) × T(9)))
- 32774 := (T(3) + (2^{T(C(7, 7)+4)}))
- 32835 := ((-((C(3, 2)⁸) - T(3)) × (-5))
- 32886 := ((T((3²) + T(8)) × T(C(8, 6)))
- 32928 := (T((C(3, 2) + T(9))) × 28)
- 33145 := (-C(T(3), 3) + (T(T((1 + T(4)))) × T(5)))
- 33245 := ((C(T(T(3)), 3) × (T(T(T(2))) + 4)) - 5)

$$\begin{aligned}
 33278 &:= (-T(C(T(3), 3)) - (T(T((T(T(2)) + (7)))) \times (-8))) \\
 33284 &:= (C(T(3), 3) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(8) \times 4)) \\
 33292 &:= (T(T((T(T(3))/3))) \times (-2) + C(9, T(2))) \\
 33298 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 3) - (-((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(T(8)))) \\
 33325 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3) + 3) \times 25) \\
 33355 &:= ((T(T(3)) + (C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 5)) \times 5) \\
 33364 &:= (C((3 \times T(3)), (T(T(T(3)))/T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 33383 &:= (-C(T(T(3)), 3) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(8) + T(T(3))))) \\
 33428 &:= ((C(T(3), 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((2 \times T(8)))) \\
 33441 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + (T((3^4)) \times T(C(4, 1)))) \\
 33464 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - ((T(4) \times T(64)))) \\
 33472 &:= ((T(3) \times (C(T(T(3)), 4) - T(T(7)))) - 2) \\
 33474 &:= (T(3) \times (C(T(T(3)), 4) - T((7 \times 4)))) \\
 33488 &:= (T(T(((C(3, 3) + 4) + 8))) \times 8) \\
 33513 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((1 + T(C(5, 3)))) - 3) \\
 33522 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(C((3 + 5), T(2)))) + T(T(2))) \\
 33571 &:= ((T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \times T(5)) + T(T(C(7, 1)))) \\
 33592 &:= ((-C((3^3), T(5))/T(T(9))) \times (-2)) \\
 33625 &:= ((-3) - T(T(3))) + C((T(6) + 2), 5) \\
 33642 &:= (-((T((3^3)) - C(T(6), 4))) \times T(T(2))) \\
 33643 &:= ((C((3 + T(T(3))), 6)/4) - (T(3))) \\
 33649 &:= C(((T(3)/3) + T(6)), -((4 - 9))) \\
 33652 &:= (C(((T(3)/3) + T(6)), 5) + T(2)) \\
 33655 &:= (T(3) + C(((3 \times 6) + 5), 5)) \\
 33664 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3) - (6)) - (-T(6)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\
 33669 &:= (T((C(T(3), 3) + 66)) \times 9) \\
 33683 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) + (((T(3) - C(T(6), 8))/T(3)))) \\
 33696 &:= (T((C(T(3), 3) + (6))) \times 96) \\
 33825 &:= (-T(3)) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(C(8, T(2))) + T(5)))) \\
 33838 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 3) - (-T(8)) \times T((T(3) + T(8)))) \\
 33869 &:= (((-T(3)) + C(T(T(3)), 8))/6) - T(9)) \\
 33887 &:= (((T(3) \times C(T(T(3)), 8))/T(8)) - T(7)) \\
 33891 &:= (33 \times (-8) + T(T(C(9, 1)))) \\
 33912 &:= (-3) + (C(T(T(3)), (9 - 1))/T(T(2))) \\
 33915 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(3))/(-9 - 1)) \times (-5)) \\
 33916 &:= ((-T(3)) - C(T(T(3)), (9 - 1)))/(-6) \\
 33987 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(C(8, 7)))) \\
 34235 &:= ((T((3 + T(T(4)))) \times C(T(T(2)), 3)) + T(5)) \\
 34275 &:= (3 \times (C((4^2), 7) - T(5))) \\
 34314 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 4) \times T(3)) - T((1 + T(T(4)))) \\
 34320 &:= (C((3 + T(4)), T(3)) \times 20) \\
 34334 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), 4) - (T(3))) \times T(3)) - T(T(T(4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34352 &:= ((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (-3) + C(T(5), T(2))) \\
 34354 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (T(T(C(4, 3))) \times (5^4))) \\
 34364 &:= ((-T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(3) \times C(T(6), 4))) \\
 34384 &:= (((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(T(3)))) + (T(C(8, 4)))) \\
 34398 &:= (T((3 + T(4))) \times T((3 \times C(9, 8)))) \\
 34632 &:= ((-3) + T(T(4))) \times T(C((6 + 3), 2)) \\
 34635 &:= (((-3) \times T(T(4))) \times (-T(C(6, 3))) - (T(5))) \\
 34736 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(4)) + C(T(7), T(3)))/T(6)) \\
 34929 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), 4) + 9) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(9))) \\
 35272 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) \times 7) + T(T(2)))) \\
 35287 &:= ((C((3 \times 5), T(T(2))) + T(8)) \times 7) \\
 35399 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (T(T(C(5, 3))) \times T(T(9)))/T(9))) \\
 35426 &:= (C(T(3), 5) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (2 + T(6)))) \\
 35484 &:= -((T(3) - (C(T(5), 4) \times (T(8) - T(4)))) \\
 35542 &:= ((T(T(3)) + 5) \times (C(T(5), 4) + 2)) \\
 35664 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(5) + (-6) \times C(T(6), 4)))) \\
 35868 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (C((5 + 8), 6) - 8)) \\
 35916 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), -((5 - 9)) + 1) \times 6) \\
 35922 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), -((5 - 9)) + 2) \times T(T(2))) \\
 35925 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), -((5 - 9)) \times T(T(2))) + (T(5))) \\
 35946 &:= (T(3) \times (C(T((T(5) - 9)), 4) + (6))) \\
 35964 &:= (C(T(3), 5) \times (9 + C(T(6), 4))) \\
 35982 &:= (C(T(3), 5) \times ((9 \times T(T(8))) + T(2))) \\
 36225 &:= (T((3 + C((6 \times 2), 2)) \times T(5)) \\
 36248 &:= ((3 + C(6, T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(8))) \\
 36337 &:= -((T((T(T(3)) + T(6))) - (C(T(T(3)), 3) \times T(7))) \\
 36432 &:= ((T(3) \times C((6 \times 4), 3)) \times T(2)) \\
 36498 &:= (T(3) \times (C(T(6), 4) + 98)) \\
 36624 &:= (-T(3)) + (T((T(6) + C(6, 2))) \times T(T(4))) \\
 36714 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 6) - C((T(7) - 1), 4)) \\
 36744 &:= (-T(3)) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(7))) \times (-C(T(4), 4))) \\
 36947 &:= (C(T(3), 6) + (T((9 + 4)) \times T(T(7)))) \\
 37145 &:= (C((-3) + T(7), 14)/T(T(5))) \\
 37222 &:= (3 - ((-T(7)) \times C(T(T(T(2))), T(2))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\
 37227 &:= (-((T(3) + (7))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times T(7))) \\
 37232 &:= (-T(3)) + ((T(7) \times C(T(T(T(2))), 3)) - 2) \\
 37234 &:= (-T(3)) + (-T(7)) \times (T(C(T(T(2)), 3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 37235 &:= (((T(T(3)) + (7)) \times C(T(T(T(2))), 3)) - 5) \\
 37237 &:= (-3) - (-C(C(7, 2), 3)) \times T(7)) \\
 37243 &:= (3 + (T(7) \times C(T((2 + 4), 3))) \\
 37254 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) + ((T(2) + C(T(5), 4)))) \\
 37275 &:= (T(((3 \times C(7, 2)) + 7)) \times T(5)) \\
 37324 &:= ((T(T(3)) - (-7) \times C(T(T(3)), T(2))) \times 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 37356** := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (-C(T(7), 3) - T(T(5)))) / (-T(6)))$
37428 := $((T(3) \times T(7)) + (T(C(T(4), 2)) \times T(8)))$
37444 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - ((T(C(7, 4)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(4))))$
37485 := $(T(T(3)) \times (C(7, 4) \times (T(8) + T(5))))$
37566 := $-((C(T(T(3)), 7) - (T((T(5) + T(6))) \times T(T(6))))$
37583 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((-T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times T(C(8, T(3))))$
37625 := $((T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(7)))) \times (-C(T(6), 2) + (5)))$
37653 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((T(7) - (6))) + T(T(C(5, 3))))$
37677 := $(3 + (C(T(7), 6) / T((T(7)/7)))$
37695 := $(T(T(3)) + ((C(T(7), 6) / T(9 - 5))))$
37752 := $-((T(3) - T(7)) \times C((T(7) - T(5)), T(T(2))))$
37853 := $-((3^7) - (-8 \times C(T(5), T(3))))$
37926 := $((T(3) \times 7) \times T((C(9, 2) + 6)))$
37975 := $(T((T(T(3)) + T(7))) \times (C(9, 7) - 5))$
38227 := $-((T(T(3))) + ((T(8) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(2))) \times T(7)))$
38235 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times C((8 + T(2)), 3)) + (T(T(5))))$
38241 := $(T(T(3)) \times (C((8 \times 2), 4) + 1))$
38244 := $-((T(3)) \times ((T(C(8, T(2))) \times (-4)) + T(4)))$
38283 := $((3 \times T(C(8, T(2)))) \times 8 - T(T(3)))$
38283 := $((3 \times T(C(8, T(2)))) \times 8 - T(T(3)))$
38286 := $(3 \times ((T(C(8, T(2))) \times 8) - (6)))$
38304 := $((T(3) \times T(C(8, 3))) \times 04)$
38328 := $(((-3) \times T(C(8, 3))) - T(2)) \times (-8)$
38338 := $((T(T(3)) + 8) \times (C(T(T(3)), 3) - 8))$
38344 := $((T(3) \times T(C(8, 3))) + T(4)) \times 4$
38349 := $((T(3) \times T(C(8, 3))) \times 4) + T(9)$
38353 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (8 \times T(T(3)))) - (C(T(5), 3)))$
38358 := $-((T(3) \times ((T(8) + T(3)) - C(T(5), 8)))$
38416 := $((T(3) + 8)^{C(4, 1^6)})$
38445 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((C(8, 4) - T(4)))) + (T(5)))$
38494 := $-((T(3)) + ((C(8, 4) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(4))))$
38532 := $(T(38) \times (T(C(5, 3)) - T(2)))$
38544 := $(T(3) \times ((T(C(8, 5)) + T(4)) \times 4))$
38562 := $(T(3) \times (-8 + C(T(5), (6 + 2))))$
38572 := $(-38) + (C(T(5), 7) \times T(T(2)))$
38583 := $(T(T(3)) - ((8 - C(T(5), 8)) \times T(3)))$
38583 := $(T(T(3)) - ((8 - C(T(5), 8)) \times T(3)))$
38586 := $-((3 \times 8) + (C(T(5), 8) \times 6))$
38588 := $(C((3 \times 8), 5) - T(88))$
38598 := $(T(T(3)) \times (8 + T((T(5) + T(C(9, 8))))$
38638 := $((T(3) + (C(8, 6)))^3 - T(T(8)))$
38646 := $((-(3^8) + T(C(6, 4))) \times (-6))$
38658 := $((T(3) \times 8) + (6 \times C(T(5), 8)))$
38682 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(8)) + ((T(6) \times C(8, T(2))))$
38724 := $(T(T(3)) \times ((8 \times T(C(7, 2))) - (4)))$
38733 := $-((T(3) - C((-8) + T(7)), T(3))) - T(T(3))$
38736 := $(-3) + (C((-8) + T(7)), T(3)) - T(6))$
38739 := $-((T(T(3)) - (C((-8) + T(7)), -((3 - 9))))$
38757 := $(-3) + C((-8) + T(7)), T(T(-((5 - 7))))$
39312 := $((T(3) \times C(9, 3)) \times T(12))$
39432 := $((T(T(T(3))) - T(9)) \times (C(T(4), T(3)) + 2))$
39784 := $((C(T(T(3)), 9) / 7 - T(T(8))) - T(T(T(4))))$
39886 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(9)) + C(8, 8))) / 6)$
40866 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (0 - T(C(8, 6)))) \times T(6))$
41292 := $((T(T(4)) + 1) + T(T(2))) \times T(C(9, 2))$
41762 := $((T(T(T(4))) - 1) \times T(7)) - (C(T(6), T(2)))$
41776 := $((T((T(T(4)) - 1) + 7) \times T(C(7, 6)))$
41975 := $((C(T(T((4 - 1))), 9) / 7) - (T(5)))$
42218 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - C((T(2) \times T((2 + 1))), 8)))$
42235 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (-T(2)) - (-2 \times C(T(T(3)), 5)))$
42238 := $(T(T(T(4))) + ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \times (-T(3))) / (-8)))$
42288 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times C(T(2), 2) + (T(T(8)))) \times 8)$
42328 := $((T(C(4, 2)) \times T((T(T(3)) \times T(2)))) - 8)$
42329 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(3))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9)))$
42333 := $((T((T(C(4, 2)) \times 3)) \times T(T(3))) - 3)$
42368 := $(4 \times ((C(T(T(T(2))), 3) - 6) \times 8))$
42399 := $-((T(C(4, 2)) \times (T(3) - (T(9) \times T(9))))$
42427 := $((T(T(4)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 7)$
42435 := $(T(C(T(4), 2)) \times (-4) + (3 \times T(5)))$
42449 := $-((T(T(4)) - C(24, -((4 - 9))))$
42452 := $-((T(T(4)) - (C(24, 5) + T(2))))$
42458 := $-(((T(4) - C(24, 5)) + T(8)))$
42459 := $(C((C(4, 2) \times 4), 5) - T(9))$
42494 := $-((T(4) - (C(24, (9 - 4))))$
42497 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), -((4 - 9))) - (7))$
42502 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) - 02)$
42504 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), C(5, 04))$
42514 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + T(1 \times 4))$
42522 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (T(T(2)) \times T(2)))$
42523 := $((C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) - 2) + T(T(3)))$
42524 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (2 \times T(4)))$
42524 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (2 \times T(4)))$
42528 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (T(2) \times 8))$
42532 := $((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times C((5 + 3), 2))$
42534 := $(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (3 \times T(4)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42537 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (T(T(T(3)))/7)) \\
 42544 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (T(4) \times 4)) \\
 42549 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), C(5, 4)) + (T(9))) \\
 42554 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (5 \times T(4))) \\
 42559 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + T(T(-(5 - 9)))) \\
 42564 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (6 \times T(4))) \\
 42582 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + T((T(8)/T(2)))) \\
 42584 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) - (-8) \times T(4)) \\
 42594 &:= (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) - (-9) \times T(4)) \\
 42595 &:= (T((T(4) + T(2))) + C((T(5) + 9), 5)) \\
 42648 &:= (4 \times (C((T(2) + T(6)), 4) + T(8))) \\
 42675 &:= (C(T(4), 2) - ((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \times 5)) \\
 42693 &:= ((C((4 \times T(T(2))), T(6)) + 9) \times T(T(3))) \\
 42735 &:= (((T(C(4, 2)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(3))) \times 5) \\
 42745 &:= (C(T(4), 2) + (T(7) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5)))) \\
 42833 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - 2) \times C(8, T(3))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\
 42872 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - T(C(7, T(T(2)))) \\
 42885 &:= ((T(T(C(4, 2))) + T((T(8) + T(8)))) \times T(5)) \\
 42891 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - C(9, 1)) \\
 42899 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - C(9, 9)) \\
 42940 &:= (T(T(T(C(4, T(2)))))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-40)) \\
 42963 &:= (((T(T(C(4, 2))) - (T(9))) \times T(T(6))) - 3) \\
 42966 &:= (((C(T(4), 2) \times T(9)) + T(6)) \times T(6)) \\
 42975 &:= (C(T(4), 2) \times (9 + T((T(7) + T(5)))) \\
 42994 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(-(2 - 9))) - C(9, 4)) \\
 43174 &:= ((T(T(C(4, 3))) - 1) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\
 43228 &:= (((C(T(4), T(3)) - 2)^2) - T(8)) \\
 43263 &:= (((C(T(4), 3)^2) + T(6)) \times 3) \\
 43264 &:= ((C(T(4), T(3)) - 2)^{6-4}) \\
 43288 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + T(3)) \times T((T(T(2)) + C(8, 8)))) \\
 43299 &:= (-C(T((4 + 3)), T(2))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9))) \\
 43372 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + (3 \times 3)) \times T(C(7, T(T(2)))) \\
 43395 &:= (T(T(4)) \times (-3 - C((3 + 9), 5))) \\
 43488 &:= (((C(T(4), 3) \times T(4)) + 8) \times T(8)) \\
 43539 &:= (C((4 \times T(3)), (T(5)/3)) + T(T(9))) \\
 43545 &:= ((C((4 \times 3), 5) \times T(T(4))) - (T(5))) \\
 43549 &:= ((C((4 \times T(3)), 5) + T(4)) + T(T(9))) \\
 43555 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times C((-3) + T(5)), 5) - (5)) \\
 43575 &:= ((T((4^3)) - (5)) \times C(7, 5)) \\
 43594 &:= ((C((4 \times T(3)), 5) + T(T(9))) + T(T(4))) \\
 43669 &:= (T(C(4, 3)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(6) \times 9))) \\
 43673 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - C(7, T(3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43728 &:= (-C(T(4), 3) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(2) \times T(8)))) \\
 43748 &:= ((-4) - T(3)) + C((T(7) - T(4)), 8)) \\
 43749 &:= (C(((4) - T(3)) + T(7)), T(4)) - 9) \\
 43754 &:= (-4) + C(-((3 - C(7, 5))), T(4)) \\
 43758 &:= C(((T(4) + T(3)) + (7 - 5)), 8) \\
 43768 &:= (T(4) + C(((T(T(3))/7) \times 6), 8)) \\
 43795 &:= ((T(T(C(4, 3))) + T(T(7))) \times 95) \\
 43838 &:= (-T(4)) + ((-3) \times T(C(8, T(3)))) \times (-T(8))) \\
 43935 &:= ((4 + C((3 \times 9), 3)) \times T(5)) \\
 43956 &:= (T((C(4, 3) \times 9)) \times T((5 + 6))) \\
 44115 &:= ((C(T(4), 4)^{1+1}) + T(5)) \\
 44262 &:= (-(((T(4)^4) + 2) + C(T(6), T(T(2)))) \\
 44264 &:= (-((T(4)^4) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T((6 - 4)))) \\
 44266 &:= -(((T(4)^4) - 2) - C(T(6), 6)) \\
 44268 &:= ((C(T(4), 4)^2) + (T(6) \times 8)) \\
 44275 &:= ((T(T(4)) + C(T(4), T(2))) \times T((7 + T(5)))) \\
 44748 &:= (T(44) + C((T(7) - T(4)), 8)) \\
 44789 &:= (-4) + (C(-(T(4) - T(7)), 8) + T(T(9))) \\
 45045 &:= (C((T(4) + 5), T(04)) \times T(5)) \\
 45055 &:= (T(4) + (C(T(5), 05) \times T(5))) \\
 45105 &:= ((4 + C(T(5), 10)) \times T(5)) \\
 45116 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((C(5, 1) + 1)^6))) \\
 45195 &:= ((T(4) + C(T(5), (1 + 9))) \times T(5)) \\
 45225 &:= -(((T(4) - (T(C(5, 2))^2) \times T(5))) \\
 45289 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C((T(5) + T(2)), 8) - 9)) \\
 45297 &:= ((T(4) \times C(T(5), T(T(2)))) - T(97)) \\
 45298 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + C(((5 - T(2)) \times 9), 8)) \\
 45331 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(T(5))/3))) + T(T(T(C(3, 1)))) \\
 45360 &:= (C(T(4), 5) \times (3 \times 60)) \\
 45475 &:= (T(4) + ((C(T(5), T(4)) + T(7)) \times T(5))) \\
 45585 &:= ((C((T(4) + 5), 5) + T(8)) \times T(5)) \\
 45661 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-5)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(C(6, 1)))) \\
 45676 &:= (4 \times (C((-5) + T(6)), 7) - T(6)) \\
 45696 &:= ((4 \times T((-5) + T(6))) \times C(9, 6)) \\
 45736 &:= ((T(4)^5) - (C((7 \times 3), 6))) \\
 45831 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(5))) + (T(8)^{C(3, 1)})) \\
 45891 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - C(9, 1)) \\
 45899 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - C(9, 9)) \\
 45996 &:= (((4^5) \times T(9)) - (C(9, 6))) \\
 46224 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times C(T(6), 2)) + T(T(2))) \times 4) \\
 46230 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + C(6, T(T(2)))) \times 30) \\
 46244 &:= (T(T(4)) - (C(C(6, T(2)), T(4))/(-4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 46299** := $(-C((4 \times 6), 2) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9))))$
46356 := $-((T((4 \times 6)) - (C(T(3), 5)^6)))$
46375 := $(T(T(4)) + ((-C(6, 3) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(5))))$
46431 := $(T(T(-((4 - C(6, 4)))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))))$
46466 := $-((T((4 + C(6, 4))) - ((6^6))))$
46475 := $(T(T(4)) \times ((T(C(6, 4)) \times 7) + (5)))$
46486 := $(T(T(4)) + (T(6) \times T((C(T(4), 8) + T(6))))$
46487 := $((-((T(4) - C(T(6), 4))) + T(T(8))) \times 7)$
46554 := $((-((T(4) - C(T(6), T(5)))) - (5 \times T(T(T(4))))$
46567 := $(T(T(4)) - ((C(T(6), T(5)) \times (-6))/7))$
46572 := $((T(4) - (C(T(6), T(5)))/(-7)) \times T(T(2)))$
46642 := $-(((T(4) - ((6^6)) + C(4, T(2))))$
46683 := $(T(T(4)) - (-((6^6) + C(8, T(3))))$
46692 := $((T(T(-((4 - 6))))^6 + C(9, 2))$
46711 := $(T(T(4)) + ((6^{C(7,1)-1}))$
46743 := $((4 \times (C(T(6), 7)/T(4))) + T(T(T(3))))$
47235 := $((T(T(4)) \times T((C(7, T(2)) + T(3)))) - T(T(5)))$
47282 := $((-4) + T(C(7, T(2)))) + (T(8)^{T(2)})$
47336 := $(C((T(4) + (7)), 3) + (T(3)^6))$
47376 := $((T(47) \times T(3)) \times C(7, 6))$
47436 := $(T((4 + C(7, 4))) + (T(3)^6))$
47572 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + (T(7) - (T(5) \times C(T(7), T(2))))))$
47582 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((C(T(7), 5) - T(8))/2)))$
47638 := $(T(4) - ((7 - C(T(6), 3)) \times T(8)))$
47691 := $((T(-((4 - 7)))^6 + T(T(C(9, 1))))$
47695 := $(T(T(4)) + ((T(T(C(7, 6))) - 9) \times T(T(5))))$
47832 := $-((T(T(4)) - (7)) - (T(8) \times C(T(T(3)), T(2))))$
47833 := $(-47) + (T(8) \times C(T(T(3)), 3))$
47852 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(7))) + T(C(8, 5))) \times 2$
47853 := $(C(-((T(4) - T(7))), 8) + T((T(5) \times T(3))))$
47863 := $-(((T(4) + (7)) - (T(8) \times C(T(6), 3))))$
47964 := $((4 \times C(-((T(7) - T(9))), 6)) - T(T(T(4))))$
48248 := $((T(4) + T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), 4)) \times 8$
48255 := $((-4) + T(C(8, 2))) \times T(T(5)) + (T(5))$
48262 := $((T(4) + T(C(8, T(2)))) + (6^{T(T(2))}))$
48295 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times C(8, 2)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-5)))$
48375 := $((T(C(T(4), 8))/(-3)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(5))))$
48476 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(C(7, 6))))$
48529 := $-((T(T(4)) + (T(8) - C((T(5) + T(2)), 9))))$
48537 := $(T(C(T(4), 8)) + ((T(T(5)) - 3) \times T(T(7))))$
48545 := $-((T(T(4)) - (T(8) \times (C(T(5), 4) - T(5))))$
48572 := $((T((T(4) \times 8)) \times T(5)) - T(C(7, T(T(2))))$
48591 := $((T((T(4) \times 8)) \times T(5)) - C(9, 1))$
48599 := $((T((T(4) \times 8)) \times T(5)) - C(9, 9))$
48632 := $((-4) - (T(8) \times (-T(6)) - C(T(T(3)), T(2))))$
48635 := $(C((T(4) + 8), (6 + 3)) + T(5))$
48639 := $(T(T(4)) - (T(8) - (C((6 \times 3), 9))))$
48665 := $-((T(T(4)) - (T(T((8 - C(6, 6)))) \times T(T(5))))$
48935 := $(C((T(4) + 8), 9) + (T(T(3)) \times T(5)))$
48945 := $(C((T(4) + 8), 9) + T((T(4) + T(5))))$
48972 := $((-4) \times ((-8) - T(9)) \times T(C(7, 2)))$
48989 := $((C((T(4) + 8), 9) - T(T(8))) + T(T(9)))$
48998 := $(C((T(4) + 8), 9) + T((-9) + T(8)))$
49221 := $((-4) \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(T(2))))^{C(2,1)})$
49229 := $-((T(T(4)) - ((T(C(9, 2))^2)/9))$
49274 := $-((T(4) - (T(C(9, 2)) \times 74)))$
49282 := $((-((T(4) - C(9, T(2)))) \times T(T(8))) - 2)$
49335 := $(T(T(4)) \times (T((T(9) - 3) - C(T(3), 5)))$
49348 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((-9) + C(T(T(3)), 4)) \times (-8))$
49532 := $((-4 - C(9, 5)) \times T(T((T(T(3))/T(2))))$
49544 := $-((T((T(T(4)) - 9)) - ((T(C(5, 4))^4)))$
49595 := $-(((T(4) \times (T(9) - C(T(5), 9))) + (5)))$
49632 := $((T(4) + (C(9, 6))) \times T(32))$
49663 := $(T(T(4)) - ((T(96) - C(T(6), T(3))))$
49722 := $(C((T(4) + 9), 7) - T(T((2^{T(2)})))$
49724 := $(4 \times (C((T(9) - T(7)), T(T(2))) + T(T(4))))$
49725 := $(T((C(T(4), 9) + (7))) \times T(25))$
49763 := $-(((T((T(4) \times 9)) + T(T(7))) - (C(T(6), T(3))))$
49765 := $((T(4) + T(T(9))) + (T(T(C(7, 6))) \times T(T(5))))$
49825 := $(T(4) + (T((C(9, 8)^2)) \times T(5)))$
51475 := $((T(5) \times C(14, 7)) - (5))$
51636 := $-((T((51 + T(6))) - C(T(T(3)), 6)))$
51975 := $((5 \times T((1 \times 9))) \times T(C(7, 5)))$
52233 := $((-T(5)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - T((3 \times T(T(3))))$
52248 := $(C(T(T((5 - 2))), T(T(2))) - T((T(T(4)) + 8)))$
52263 := $(T(5) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - (T(63))))$
52266 := $((T(T((5 + T(2)))) \times (-T(2))) + (C(T(6), 6)))$
52284 := $(C(T(T((5 - 2))), T(T(2))) - (T(8) \times T(T(4))))$
52321 := $((-T(T(5))) + ((-2) + T(T(T(3))))^{C(2,1)})$
52325 := $((-C(T(5), T(2))) \times ((3 + 2) - T(T(5))))$
52325 := $((-C(T(5), T(2))) \times ((3 + 2) - T(T(5))))$
52332 := $((C(T(5), T(T(2))) - T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)))/2$
52345 := $((T(T(C(5, 2))) \times 34) - (T(5)))$
52375 := $((T(T(C(5, 2))) \times (T(3) + T(7))) + (T(5)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 52425 &:= (((T(5)^{T(2)}) + C(T(4), T(2))) \times T(5)) \\
 52425 &:= (((T(5)^{T(2)}) + C(T(4), T(2))) \times T(5)) \\
 52433 &:= ((-T(T(5))) - T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)))) \\
 52442 &:= (5 + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4) + T(T(C(4,2)))))) \\
 52500 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times 500) \\
 52527 &:= ((-T(T(5))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 7) \\
 52533 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(2)) \times (C(T(5), 3) - T(3))) \\
 52556 &:= ((-C(T(5), T(2))) \times (5 - T(T(5)))) + T(T(6)) \\
 52558 &:= (5 + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - T(58))) \\
 52584 &:= ((C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(T(5))) - T((8 + T(T(4)))) \\
 52604 &:= (-T(T(5))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T(T(T(04)))) \\
 52649 &:= (-T(T(5))) + ((C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(9))) \\
 52668 &:= (C((T(5) - T(2)), 6) \times (T(6) + T(8))) \\
 52694 &:= (T(5) + ((C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 52724 &:= (C(T(T((5 - 2))), T((7 - 2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 52725 &:= (5 \times T((2 + C(7, T(2)))) \times T(5)) \\
 52725 &:= (5 \times T((2 + C(7, T(2)))) \times T(5)) \\
 52745 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) + (T((T(7) + T(T(4)))) \times T(5))) \\
 52773 &:= ((T((C(5, 2) \times 7) + T(7)) \times T(T(3))) \\
 52794 &:= (((T(5) - 2) + T(T(7))) \times C(9, 4)) \\
 52833 &:= -((T(((T(5) + 2) + T(8))) - C(T(T(3)), T(3)))) \\
 52844 &:= (T(T(5)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T((8/4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 52858 &:= (T(52) - ((-8) \times C(T(5), 8))) \\
 52933 &:= ((-5) - T((T(T(2)) + T(9)))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \\
 52983 &:= (-((C(T(5), 2) - T((9 \times 8)))) \times T(T(3))) \\
 53125 &:= (-5) + C(((T(3) - 1)^2), 5) \\
 53135 &:= (5 + C((31 - T(3)), 5)) \\
 53145 &:= (T(5) + C((T(T(3)) + (1 \times 4)), 5)) \\
 53214 &:= ((-T(5)) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) - T(T((-1) + T(4)))) \\
 53229 &:= (C((T(5) + T(3)), (2 \times T(2))) - T(T(9))) \\
 53232 &:= -(((T((T(5) \times 3)) - T(2)) - C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) \\
 53235 &:= -((C(T(5), 3) \times (T(2) - T((3 \times 5)))) \\
 53235 &:= -((C(T(5), 3) \times (T(2) - T((3 \times 5)))) \\
 53239 &:= (C(5, 3) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(T(9)))) \\
 53244 &:= ((T(5) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) - T((-T(4) + T(T(4)))) \\
 53257 &:= (-T((T(5) \times 3))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (T(7))) \\
 53259 &:= (T(5) + ((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + (T(5))) - T(T(9)))) \\
 53269 &:= ((T(T(5))/3) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T(T(9)))) \\
 53298 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times T((T(2) \times C(9, 8)))) \\
 53306 &:= (-T(C(5, 3))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(06))) \\
 53325 &:= ((-T(5)) + T(C((3 \times 3), T(2)))) \times T(5) \\
 53326 &:= (-((T(5) + C(T(3), 3))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53336 &:= ((-5) - C(T(3), 3) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) \\
 53349 &:= (T(T(5)) + (C(T(T(3)), C(T(3), 4)) - T(T(9)))) \\
 53355 &:= ((-C(T(5), 3) \times (3 - T(T(5)))) + T(T(5))) \\
 53358 &:= -((T(T(5)) - ((C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T(T(5))) - T(T(8)))) \\
 53366 &:= (5 + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T((T(6) + T(6)))) \\
 53371 &:= (C(5, 3) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T((7 - 1)))) \\
 53373 &:= (5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(7, T(3))) \\
 53377 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(7, 7)) \\
 53388 &:= (((T(T(C(5, 3))) - T(T(3))) - T(8)) \times T(8)) \\
 53392 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(9, 2)) \\
 53397 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(9, 7)) \\
 53416 &:= (T(C(5, 3) + (T(T(T((4 - 1)))) \times T(T(6)))) \\
 53426 &:= ((T(C(5, 3) + T(4)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)))) \\
 53436 &:= ((5 \times C(T(3), 4) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) \\
 53466 &:= (T((C(5, 3) + 4) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6)))) \\
 53478 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (C(T(T(3)), T(-(4 - 7)))) - T(T(8)))) \\
 53519 &:= ((C(T(5), 3) \times T(T(5))) - T((1 + T(9)))) \\
 53523 &:= (-T((53 - T(5))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(3))) \\
 53528 &:= (5 + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T((2 + T(8)))) \\
 53538 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(38))) \\
 53548 &:= (5 + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(8)))) \\
 53572 &:= ((T(T(5)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) + (T(T(7)) \times (-2))) \\
 53582 &:= ((5 + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\
 53583 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T((T(8) - 3)))) \\
 53589 &:= ((C((T(5) + T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(8))) - 9) \\
 53598 &:= (C((T(5) + T(3)), (T(5) - 9)) - T(T(8))) \\
 53627 &:= -((T((T(5) + T(3))) - (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - T(T(7)))) \\
 53628 &:= ((5 \times T(3)) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - T(T(8)))) \\
 53638 &:= (((T(T(5))/3) + (C(T(6), T(3)))) - T(T(8))) \\
 53648 &:= (-5) + ((C(T(T(3)), 6) + T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \\
 53654 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) - ((5^4))) \\
 53681 &:= (T(T(5)) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) - T((T(8) + 1)))) \\
 53684 &:= (((T(T(C(5, 3))) - 6) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 53718 &:= (T(T(5)) + (C(T(T(3)), (7 - 1)) - T(T(8)))) \\
 53722 &:= -T(-5 + T(T(3))) - T(T(7)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \\
 53725 &:= (C(T(5), T(3)) + (T(T(7)) \times T((T(2) \times 5)))) \\
 53732 &:= -(((T(T(5)) + (T(3))) + T(T(7))) - C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) \\
 53733 &:= (((-5^3) - T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \\
 53735 &:= -(((T(T(5)) + 3) + T(T(7))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\
 53735 &:= -(((T(T(5)) + 3) + T(T(7))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\
 53755 &:= (((C(T(5), 3) - 7) \times T(T(5))) - 5) \\
 53763 &:= ((-5) - T((3 + T(7))) + (C(T(6), T(3))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53767 &:= (-53) - (C(T(7), 6)/(-7)) \\ 53832 &:= (-((T(5) - 3) \times T(8))) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) \\ 53865 &:= ((T((C(5, 3) + 8)) \times T(6)) \times T(5)) \\ 53945 &:= (-T(C(5, 3))) + ((T(9) \times T(4)) \times T(T(5))) \\ 53964 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(3))) + (9 \times C(T(6), 4))) \\ 54033 &:= (C(T(T((T(T(5))/40))), T(3)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 54133 &:= -(((T(T(5)) + (T(4) + 1)) - C(T(T(3)), T(3)))) \\ 54134 &:= -((T(T(5)) - C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(3)) - T(4))) \\ 54135 &:= -(((T(T(5)) + (T(4) - 1)) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) \\ 54137 &:= -((T(T(5)) - C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(3)) - (7))) \\ 54144 &:= -((T(T(5)) - C(T(T((4 - 1))), (-4) + T(4)))) \\ 54153 &:= ((T(T(5)) + C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(5)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 54154 &:= -((T(T(5)) - C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(5)) + T(4))) \\ 54165 &:= -(((T(T(5)) - T(T(4 - 1))) - C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 54196 &:= (((T(5)^4) + 1) + T(C(9, 6))) \\ 54214 &:= ((-5) \times T(4)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(-(1 - 4))) \\ 54222 &:= ((-C((T(5) + 4), T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (-2) \\ 54223 &:= (T((T(5) + 4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 54224 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(C(4, 2)), T(T(2))) - T(T(4)))) \\ 54226 &:= (((T(5) + 4)) \times (-2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), 6) \\ 54227 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) + T(7) \\ 54228 &:= (C((5 + (4^2)), T(T(2))) - T(8)) \\ 54232 &:= (((T(T(5)))/(-4)) - 2) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) \\ 54233 &:= ((5 - T((4 \times 2))) + C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \\ 54234 &:= ((T(5) + T(4)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - (T(T(4)))) \\ 54235 &:= ((-5) - (4 \times T(T(2)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 54236 &:= (-T((C(5, 4) + 2))) + C(T(T(3)), 6) \\ 54237 &:= ((5 - 4) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - (T(7)))) \\ 54239 &:= ((5 \times 4) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(9))) \\ 54244 &:= (-((5 \times 4)) + C(T(T(T(2))), (-4) + T(4))) \\ 54245 &:= -(((T(5) + 4) - C(T(T(2) + 4), T(5)))) \\ 54245 &:= -(((T(5) + 4) - C(T(T(2) + 4), T(5)))) \\ 54249 &:= (-T(5)) + C(T(C(4, 2)), T(-(4 - 9))) \\ 54251 &:= ((T(T(5)))/(-T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - 1) \\ 54252 &:= -((T(5) - C(T(C(4, 2))), T(5)) + T(2))) \\ 54253 &:= (-5) + (C(T(C(4, 2)), T(5)) - T(3)) \\ 54254 &:= (C((5 + (4^2)), T(5)) - T(4)) \\ 54255 &:= (-((5 + 4)) + C((T(T(2)) + T(5)), T(5))) \\ 54257 &:= (C((5 + (4^2)), T(5)) - 7) \\ 54258 &:= ((T(T(5))/4) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - T(8))) \\ 54259 &:= (-5) + C(T(C(4, 2)), (T(5) - 9)) \\ 54263 &:= (5 + (C(T(C(4, 2)), 6) - T(3))) \\ 54265 &:= (((5 - 4)^2) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 54266 &:= (((5 - 4) \times 2) + C(T(6), 6)) \\ 54267 &:= (-((T(5) + T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) + (T(7)))) \\ 54268 &:= ((T(T(5))/T(4)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - 8)) \\ 54269 &:= (5 + C(T(C(4, 2)), (6 + 9))) \\ 54273 &:= ((5 + 4) + C((T(2) \times 7), T(3))) \\ 54275 &:= ((T(5) - 4) + C((T(2) \times 7), T(5))) \\ 54276 &:= ((T(T(5))/T(4)) + C((T(2) \times 7), 6)) \\ 54279 &:= ((T(5)^{C(4, T(2))}) - (T(T(7)) \times (-9))) \\ 54283 &:= ((T(5) + 4) + C(T(-(2 - 8)), T(3))) \\ 54294 &:= ((T(T(5))/4) + C(T(T(T(2))), T((9 - 4)))) \\ 54314 &:= ((5 \times T(4)) + C(T(T(3)), T(-(1 - 4)))) \\ 54322 &:= ((T(5) \times 4) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - 2)) \\ 54323 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - (T(3)))) \\ 54324 &:= (C(5, 4) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + T(T(4)))) \\ 54325 &:= (T((T(5) - 4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - 5)) \\ 54326 &:= (((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - 3) + C(T(T(T(2))), 6)) \\ 54327 &:= ((T(5) + T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - 7)) \\ 54329 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + C(T(T(3)), -(T(2) - 9))) \\ 54330 &:= (T((T(5) - 4)) + C(T(T(3)), T(3 + 0))) \\ 54331 &:= (T((T(5) - 4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + 1)) \\ 54332 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(2))) \\ 54333 &:= (T((T(5) - 4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + 3)) \\ 54334 &:= ((T(5) \times 4) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(4))) \\ 54335 &:= (T((T(5) - 4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + 5)) \\ 54337 &:= (T((5 + 4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(7))) \\ 54338 &:= (T((T(5) - 4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + 8)) \\ 54339 &:= ((T(T(5))/4) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + (T(9)))) \\ 54342 &:= (T((T(T(5))/T(4))) + (C(T(T(3)), C(4, 2)))) \\ 54353 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 54358 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(8))) \\ 54359 &:= ((5 \times T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + (T(9)))) \\ 54362 &:= ((C(T(5), T(4))/3) + (T(T(6))^2)) \\ 54363 &:= ((T(T(C(5, 4))) - T(T(3))) + (C(T(6), T(3)))) \\ 54364 &:= (T((5 + 4)) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) + T(T(4)))) \\ 54365 &:= (-((T(5) + 4)) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) + T(T(5)))) \\ 54367 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) - 7)) \\ 54369 &:= ((T(5) \times T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) - (T(9)))) \\ 54374 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T(4)) + C(T(T(3)), T((7 - 4)))) \\ 54394 &:= ((T(T(5)) + T(4)) + C(T(T(3)), T((9 - 4)))) \\ 54423 &:= ((5 - (T(T(T(4)))/(-T(4)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(3))) \\ 54429 &:= (T(T(5)) + (C(T((-4) + T(4)), T(T(2))) + (T(9)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 54433 := $(T(5) - ((T(T(T(4)))/(-T(4))) - (C(T(T(3)), T(3))))$
 54440 := $((C(T(5), 4) - 4) \times 40)$
 54523 := $(((-C(T(5), 4) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))/(-3))$
 54535 := $-(((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + (-C(T(5), 3) \times T(T(5))))$
 54552 := $(T(T(5)) + (C(T(4), 5) \times (-T(5) + T(T(T(2))))))$
 54585 := $((C(T(5), 4) \times (5 \times 8)) - T(5))$
 54595 := $((C(T(5), 4) \times (-5 + T(9))) - 5)$
 54625 := $((T(T(5)) + T(4) + T(T(6))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)))$
 54648 := $((C(T(5), 4) + T((T(6) - 4))) \times T(8))$
 54663 := $((T(5) + 4) \times T(6) + C(T(6), T(3)))$
 54722 := $((T((T(T(5))/4) - 7) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))))$
 54733 := $((C(T(5), 4) + 7) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3))))$
 54736 := $((T((T(5) - 4)) + T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), 6))$
 54865 := $-(((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) - (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 54879 := $(C(T(5), T(4)) - (-T(8) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(9))))$
 54891 := $((-T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8) - C(9, 1))$
 54894 := $((-C(T(5), 4) - T(T(8))) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))))$
 54899 := $((-T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8) - C(9, 9))$
 54935 := $(5 + T((4 \times 9))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$
 54956 := $((T(5) - 4) \times (-9) + C(T(5), 6))$
 54966 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(4))) \times 9) + (C(T(6), 6)))$
 55237 := $(-C(T(5), 5) + (T(2^{T(3)})) \times T(7))$
 55265 := $((C(T(5), 5)/T(2)) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 55266 := $((T(T(5)) \times C(T(5), T(2))) + T((6 \times 6)))$
 55269 := $((-T(5) + T(5)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) + T(T(9))))$
 55299 := $(C(T(T(T(5)/5)), -(T(2) - 9)) + T(T(9)))$
 55384 := $(-C((T(T(5))/T(5)), 3) - (-T(8) \times T(T(T(4))))$
 55392 := $(C(T(T(T(5)/5)), T(3)) + T((T(9) + 2)))$
 55435 := $((T(T(5)) \times C((T(5) - 4), T(3))) - 5)$
 55455 := $((T(T(5)) \times C((T(5) - 4), 5)) + T(5))$
 55455 := $((T(T(5)) \times C((T(5) - 4), 5)) + (T(5)))$
 55461 := $((T((T(T(5))/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(C(6, 1)))$
 55642 := $(C(T(T(T(5)/5)), 6) + T((T(T(4)) - T(2))))$
 55785 := $(-5) \times (T(5) + (-7) \times T(C(8, 5)))$
 55847 := $(C(5, 5) - ((-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(7))))$
 55923 := $((T(T(T(T(5))/T(5))) \times C(9, T(2))) - (T(T(3))))$
 55934 := $((T(T(T(T(5))/T(5))) \times C(9, 3)) - T(4))$
 55937 := $((T(T(T(T(5))/T(5))) \times C(9, 3)) - 7)$
 55938 := $((T(T(T(5)/5)) + (-C(9, 3) \times T(T(8))))$
 55950 := $(T(5) \times (C(T(5), 9) - T(50)))$
 55965 := $(T(T(T(T(5))/T(5))) + ((T(T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(5)))))$
 55968 := $((T(T(5))/5) - (-C(9, 6) \times T(T(8))))$
 56222 := $((5 + T(62)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))))$
 56262 := $((T((T(5) + T(6))) \times T(2)) + C(T(6), T(T(2))))$
 56329 := $((-5) + C(T(6), T(3))) + (2 \times T(T(9)))$
 56349 := $((5 + C(T(6), T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 9)))$
 56355 := $(T(T((5 + 6))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(5))))$
 56382 := $((T(T(5)) + (C(T(6), T(3)))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(2))))$
 56435 := $-((C(T(5), 6) - ((4^{T(3)}) \times T(5)))$
 56465 := $(T(T((5 + 6))) - ((T(4) - C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56465 := $(T(T((5 + 6))) - ((T(4) - C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56823 := $((T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times (T(C(8, 2)) - 3))$
 56832 := $((T(T(5)) - T(T(6))) \times (-8^{C(3, 2)}))$
 56952 := $((-5) + T(T(6))) \times (C(9, 5) \times 2)$
 57325 := $(-5) - (-T(C(7, 3)) \times T((-2) + T(5)))$
 57329 := $((5 \times T(T(7))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + T(T(9))))$
 57344 := $(C(T(T(T(-((5 - 7))))), T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4))))$
 57366 := $((T(T((5 + 7))) + T(T(3))) + (C(T(6), 6)))$
 57431 := $(-T((T(5) + 7))) \times (4 - T(T(C(3, 1))))$
 57495 := $((T((T(5) + (C(7, 4)))) \times T(9)) + T(T(5)))$
 57528 := $((T(57) - T(C(5, 2))) \times T(8))$
 57622 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(7)) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - 2))$
 57624 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(7)) + C(T(6), (2 + 4)))$
 57634 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(7)) + ((C(T(6), T(3)) + T(4))))$
 57669 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(7)) + (C(T(6), 6) + T(9)))$
 57699 := $((C(T(5), 7) + T(6)) - T(9)) \times 9$
 57735 := $((T(57) \times C(7, 3)) - T(T(5)))$
 57798 := $(T((5 + 7)) \times T((-7) + T(C(9, 8))))$
 57828 := $(T(T(5)) - ((-7) - T(C(8, T(2)))) \times T(8))$
 57912 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - (1 + 2))$
 57913 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + ((1 - 3)))$
 57914 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - (1^4))$
 57915 := $(C(T(5), 7) \times C(9, (1^5)))$
 57916 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (1^6))$
 57921 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + T((2 + 1)))$
 57922 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))$
 57923 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (2^3))$
 57925 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (2 \times 5))$
 57926 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6)))$
 57928 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + T(T(T(2)))) - 8$
 57933 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (3 \times T(3)))$
 57936 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + T(T(-(3 - 6))))$
 57937 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - T(3)) + T(7)$
 57939 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - T(T(3))) + (T(9))$
 57943 := $((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + T((4 + 3)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 57946 &:= (((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + T(4)) + T(6)) & 59772 &:= (((T(5) \times T(C(9, 7))) - T(7)) \times T(T(2))) \\
 57947 &:= (((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (4)) + T(7)) & 59864 &:= (5 - (-9) \times (T(T(8)) + (C(T(6), 4)))) \\
 57958 &:= ((T(5) + T(7)) + (9 \times C(T(5), 8))) & 59892 &:= ((5 + C(9, 8)) \times T(92)) \\
 57963 &:= (((5 + T(T(7))) \times 9) + (C(T(6), T(3)))) & 59952 &:= ((C(T(5), 9) - 9) \times (T(5) - T(2))) \\
 57964 &:= (((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - (6)) + T(T(4))) & 59985 &:= ((T(T(5)) + 9) \times T((C(9, 8)) - T(5))) \\
 57969 &:= ((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + ((6 \times 9))) & 60732 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(07)) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) \\
 57982 &:= ((T(5) + (7)) + (T(T(9)) \times C(8, T(2)))) & 61422 &:= ((C(T((6 + 1)), 4) \times T(2)) - T(2)) \\
 57983 &:= ((-5) + T(7)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 3))) & 61425 &:= (C(T((6 + 1)), 4) \times (-2 - 5)) \\
 57989 &:= ((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - (T(T(8)) / (-9))) & 61544 &:= ((T(6) \times (1 + C(T(5), T(4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 57993 &:= ((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + T((9 + 3))) & 62271 &:= (T((C(6, 2) + 2)) \times (T(T(7)) + 1)) \\
 58146 &:= ((C(T(5), 8) \times (-1) + T(4)) + T(T(6))) & 62397 &:= ((T((T(T(6)) / T(2))) \times T(T(3))) - T(C(9, 7))) \\
 58174 &:= (T(58) \times (-1 - C(7, 4))) & 62489 &:= ((C(T(6), T(T(2))) - T(T(4))) - (-8) \times T(T(9))) \\
 58236 &:= -(T((T(5) + 8)) \times (C(T(T(2)), 3) - T(T(6)))) & 62622 &:= ((T(T(6))^2) + ((T(6)^{C(T(2), 2)})) \\
 58239 &:= ((C(T(5), 8) + T((2^3))) \times 9) & 62657 &:= ((T((T(T(6)) / T(2))) \times T(C(6, 5))) - (T(T(7)))) \\
 58246 &:= (-(T(5) \times T(8)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(4)) / 6)) & 62762 &:= -(T((T(6) / T(2))) + (-C(T(7), 6) / T(T(2)))) \\
 58248 &:= ((C((5 + 8), 2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) & 62763 &:= ((-T(6) - T(T(2))) + ((C(T(7), 6) / T(3)))) \\
 58265 &:= (5 + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(2))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) & 62766 &:= -((T(6) + T(2)) + (C(T(7), 6) / (-6))) \\
 58266 &:= (-C(T(5), 8) - (T(T((2 \times 6))) \times (-T(6)))) & 62868 &:= (C(T(6), T(T(2))) + ((8 + T(T(6))) \times T(8))) \\
 58366 &:= (C(T(5), (T(8) / T(3))) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6)))) & 63232 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(T(3))) + (C(T(T(2)), 3)))^2) \\
 58386 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(C(8, T(3)))) \times T(T(8))) / 6) & 63345 &:= ((T(6) + C(T(3), 3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 5)) \\
 58419 &:= (((-C(T(5), 8)) - T(T(4))) - 1) \times (-9)) & 63425 &:= ((-C(6, 3) - (-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times 5) \\
 58435 &:= ((-T(5)) + T((T(8) + T(T(4)))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) & 63549 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(T(3)) + (C(T(5), T(4)))) + (T(9))) \\
 58465 &:= ((T(5) + T((T(8) + T(T(4)))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) & 63588 &:= (C(T(6), T(3)) - ((-T(5)) \times T(T(8))) + T(T(8))) \\
 58629 &:= ((5 \times T(T(8))) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) + T(T(9)))) & 63735 &:= ((T((T(T(6)) / 3)) \times T(7)) - (C(T(T(3)), 5))) \\
 58695 &:= -(T((5 + 8)) + (C(T(6), 9) / (-5))) & 63784 &:= ((C(T(6), 3) + (T(T(7)) \times T(8))) \times 4) \\
 58926 &:= ((T(T(5)) - T((-8) + C(9, T(2)))) \times (-T(6))) & 63822 &:= (((C(T(6), 3) \times 8) - T(2)) \times T(T(2))) \\
 58987 &:= (((C(T(5), 8) \times 9) + T(T(8))) + T(T(7))) & 63825 &:= (((C(T(6), 3) \times 8) \times T(T(2))) - (T(5))) \\
 59169 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((C(9, 1)^6) / 9)) & 63835 &:= (((C(T(6), 3) \times 8) \times T(3)) - 5) \\
 59263 &:= ((C(T(5), 9) - T(T(2))) + (C(T(6), T(3)))) & 63840 &:= (C(T(6), 3) \times (8 + 40)) \\
 59266 &:= ((C(T(5), 9) - T(2)) + C(T(6), 6)) & 63946 &:= ((C(T(6), 3) \times T(9)) + (4^6)) \\
 59269 &:= (C(T(5), 9) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(-(6 - 9)))) & 63948 &:= (C(T(6), T(3)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-T(4))) + T(T(8)))) \\
 59284 &:= (((5 + C(9, T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + T(4)) & 63966 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (-3) + T(9)) + (C(T(6), 6))) \\
 59289 &:= (T(5) + (T(C(9, 2)) \times 89)) & 63987 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((T(3) \times T(C(9, 8))) + (7))) \\
 59349 &:= (T((T(5) + 9)) + (3^{C(T(4), 9)})) & 64239 &:= (T(6) \times (C((4 \times T(T(2))), 3) + T(T(9)))) \\
 59385 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times C((9 + 3), 8)) - (T(5))) & 64428 &:= ((6 - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-C(4, 2) - T(8))) \\
 59625 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times (C(T(6), T(2)) - 5)) & 64482 &:= ((-((T(6)^4)) + T(C(T(4), 8))) / (-T(2))) \\
 59654 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(5)) - T(4))) & 64522 &:= (6 + ((C(T(4), 5) + 2)^2)) \\
 59657 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(5)) - 7)) & 64571 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(4) \times (C(T(5), 7) - 1))) \\
 59662 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) + (C(T(6), 6) - 2)) & 64581 &:= (T(T(6)) - (T(4) \times (C(T(5), 8) \times (-1)))) \\
 59664 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) + C(T(6), C(6, 4))) & 64815 &:= (((C(T(6), 4) \times T(8)) + 1) \times T(5)) \\
 59667 &:= (-T(5)) - ((C(9, 6) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(7))) & 65142 &:= ((T(T(6)) + 51) \times T(T(C(4, 2)))) \\
 59724 &:= (((C(T(5), 9) - T(7)) \times T(2)) \times 4) & 65229 &:= (-T(6)) - ((T(T(5)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(2))) \times (-T(9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 65338 := ((T(6) + C(T(5), T(3))) × (T(T(3)) - 8))
 65372 := ((C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(3))) - T(T(7))) - 2)
 65373 := (T(T(6)) × ((C(5,3) × T(7)) + 3))
 65374 := (C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(3))) - T((7 × 4)))
 65450 := ((-T(T(C(6,5)))) + T(T(T(4)))) × 50
 65491 := (((T(6) - (5))⁴) - T(C(9,1)))
 65536 := ((T(6) - (5))^{C(5,3)-6})
 65555 := (C((T(6) + (5)), 5) - (T(5) × T(5)))
 65772 := ((T(T(6)) - (57)) × C(T(7), 2))
 65775 := (C((T(6) + (5)), (-7) + T(7)) - (5))
 65793 := (T(C(6,5)) × (T(7) + (T(T(9)) × 3)))
 65795 := (C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(T(-((7-9)))))) + T(5))
 65845 := (65 + C((T(8) - T(4)), 5))
 65846 := (T((6 + 5)) + C((T(8) - T(4)), T(6)))
 65856 := (T((C(6,5) × 8) × 56))
 65924 := (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) × T(C(9,2))) - T(4))
 65927 := (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) × T(C(9,2))) - (7))
 65928 := (-6) + ((T(5) + C(9, T(2))) × T(T(8)))
 65934 := ((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) × T(C(9, (3 + 4)))
 65979 := (((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) × T(C(9, 7))) + (T(9)))
 66239 := (-C(6, 6)) + ((2^{T(3)}) × T(T(9)))
 66241 := ((T(6) × T(T(6 × 2))) + T(T(T(C(4, 1))))))
 66276 := (-6) × ((-T(C(6,2))) - T(T(7))) × T(6))
 66297 := ((T(6) + (C(T(6), 2) × T(9))) × 7)
 66360 := (T(6) × (C(T(6), 3) + T(60)))
 66399 := -(T(6) - (C(6,3) × T(9 × 9)))
 66584 := (C(T(6), C(6,5)) - (-8) × T(T(T(4))))
 67368 := (T(6) × (C(T(7), 3) - 68))
 67551 := (T(T(6)) + (T((T(7) + (5))) × T(T(C(5, 1)))))
 67575 := (C(T(6), 7) - ((T(T(5)) × T(T(7))) - (T(5))))
 67683 := ((T(6) × (-7)) + (C(T(6), 8)/3))
 67753 := (((6 × T(T(7))) × T(7)) - (C(T(5), 3)))
 67823 := ((C(T(6), -(T(7) - T(8))) - T(T(T(2))))/3)
 67825 := ((C(T(6), -(T(7) - T(8)))/T(2)) - (5))
 67827 := ((T(T(6)) - C((-7) + T(8)), T(T(2)))/(-7))
 67854 := ((-C(T(6), 7) - T(T(8))) - (-T(T(5))) × T(T(T(4))))
 68061 := ((T(6) × T(80)) + T(C(6, 1)))
 68235 := ((T(6) × T(T(8))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(5)))
 68237 := (((C(T(6), 8) + T(2))/3) + T(T(7)))
 68250 := ((T(T(6)) - T(C(8, T(2)))) × (-50))
 68283 := (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), 8))/3))
 68295 := ((C(T(6), 8)/T(2)) + T((T(9) - T(5))))
 68594 := (-6) + (C(8,5) × T((T(9) + (4))))
 68628 := (T(6) × (C(C(8,6), T(2)) - 8))
 68640 := (C((T(6) - 8), 6) × 40)
 68648 := (((T(6) × T(C(8,6))) + T(T(4))) × 8)
 68733 := ((T(T(6)) + (T(8) × T(C(7,3)))) × 3)
 68796 := ((T(6) × T(8)) × (7 + C(9,6)))
 68894 := (-T(T((6 + C(8,8)))) - (-T(9)) × T(T(T(4))))
 69272 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - T(C(7, T(T(2))))
 69291 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - C(9, 1))
 69299 := ((T(T(6)) × T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - C(9,9))
 69525 := ((-T(6)) + T((-9) + C(T(5), 2))) × T(5)
 69657 := (-T(6)) × (-T(C(9,6)) + T((T(5) + (7))))
 69678 := (T(6) × (T(C(9,6)) + (-7) × T(8)))
 69759 := ((6 × C((-9) + T(7)), 5) - 9)
 69936 := ((T((6 + 9)) × T(T(9))) - C(T(T(3)), 6))
 69972 := ((T(6) × T((9 × 9))) + T(C(7, 2)))
 71253 := (C((T(7) + 1), 25) × 3)
 71393 := (-7) - ((-1) + T(T(3))) × (-T(C(9,3)))
 71442 := (-T((T(7) - 1))) × (-C(T(4), 4) + T(T(T(2))))
 72072 := ((T(7) - T(T(2))) × C(T(07), T(2)))
 72288 := ((T((C(7, 2) × T(2)) - 8) × T(8))
 72292 := ((T(7) × (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - T(9)))/T(T(T(2))))
 72325 := (T((7 + T(2))) × (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) - (T(5))))
 72352 := (T(7) × (C(C(T(T(2))), 3, 5)/T(T(2))))
 72363 := (((T(7) × C(T(T(T(2))), T(3))) + T(T(6)))/T(T(3)))
 72625 := ((T(T(7)) × (-2) + T(T(6))) - C(T(T(T(2))), 5))
 72632 := (T(7) × (C(26, 3) - T(T(2))))
 72634 := -(T(T(7)) - ((-2) + C(T(6), 3)) × T(T(4)))
 72738 := ((C(T(7), T(2)) × (T(7) - T(3))) + T(T(8)))
 72765 := (T(((7 × 2) × C(7, 6))) × T(5))
 72785 := ((C(7, T(2)) × T((T(7) + T(8)))) - (T(5)))
 72864 := ((C(T(7), 2) + T(8)) × (T(T(6)) - T(T(4))))
 72928 := (T(C(7, T(T(2)))) + (((T(9)²) × T(8)))
 72996 := ((T(T(7)) × T((2 × 9))) + (T(C(9,6))))
 73122 := (-T(7)) + (T(T((3 + 1))) × C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)))
 73206 := ((C(T(7), 3) + T(20)) × T(6))
 73269 := (((T(T(7)) × C(T(3), T(2))) + (T(6))) × 9)
 73276 := ((T(T(7)) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2)))))) × T(C(7, 6)))
 73535 := -(T(T((7 + 3))) - ((C(T(5), T(3)) × T(5))))
 73584 := (T(7) × T(-((3 - 5) - C(8,4))))
 73626 := (((C(T(7), 3) + T(T(6))) × T(T(T(2)))) - (T(6)))
 73647 := ((C(T(7), 3) + T(T(6))) × T(T(-((4 - 7))))
 73836 := (T(C(7, 3)) + (T(83) × T(6)))

$$\begin{aligned} 74248 &:= ((C((T(7) - T(4)), T(T(2))) \times 4) - 8) \\ 74256 &:= (T((7 - 4)) \times C((2 + T(5)), 6)) \\ 74262 &:= ((C((7 + T(4)), T(T(2))) \times 6) + T(T(2))) \\ 74263 &:= (7 + (4 \times C((T(2) \times 6), T(3)))) \\ 74313 &:= -((T((T(7) - 4)) - C((T(T(3)) + 1), T(3)))) \\ 74333 &:= (T(7) + (T(T(4)) \times (C(T(T(3)), 3) + T(T(3)))) \\ 74382 &:= (7 \times C((4 \times T(3)), (8/2))) \\ 74519 &:= ((T(C(7, 4)) \times T(T(5))) - T((1 + T(9)))) \\ 74595 &:= -((((T(7) + 4) - C(T(5), 9)) \times T(5))) \\ 74613 &:= C(((7 \times 4) - 6), T((1 \times 3))) \\ 74616 &:= ((7 - 4) + C((T(6) + 1), 6)) \\ 74662 &:= (T(T(7)) + (C((-4) + T(6)), 6) \times T(T(2))) \\ 74676 &:= ((-T(C(7, 4)) + T(T((6 + 7)))) \times T(6)) \\ 74732 &:= ((C(T(7), 4) - 7) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) \\ 74755 &:= (((T(C(7, 4)) - 7) \times T(T(5))) - 5) \\ 74766 &:= (T((7 + T(4))) + C((T(7) - 6), 6)) \\ 74844 &:= ((-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (C(8, 4) - 4) \\ 74851 &:= -(((T(T(7)) - T(C(T(4), 8))) \times (T(T(5)) - 1))) \\ 74932 &:= (-((T(7) + T(4))) + (T(C(9, 3)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 74965 &:= ((T(T((7 - 4))) \times T(C(9, 6))) - 5) \\ 75225 &:= ((7 + (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(2))) \times T(5)) \\ 75264 &:= (T((-7) + T(C(5, 2)))) \times 64 \\ 75282 &:= ((C((7 + T(5)), T(T(2))) + T(T(8))) + T(2)) \\ 75345 &:= ((T(7) + (C(T(5), T(3)) - T(4))) \times T(5)) \\ 75393 &:= (C((7 + T(5)), T(3)) + T((T(9) - T(3)))) \\ 75397 &:= (((-7) \times T(T(C(5, 3)))) + 9) \times (-7) \\ 75487 &:= (7 + (T(T(5)) \times (T(C(T(4), 8)) - T(T(7)))) \\ 75495 &:= ((T(7) + C(T(C(5, 4)), 9)) \times T(5)) \\ 75574 &:= -((T(T(7)) - C((5 + T(5)), 7))) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 75591 &:= ((T((7 \times 5)) \times T(T(5))) - C(9, 1)) \\ 75599 &:= ((T((7 \times 5)) \times T(T(5))) - C(9, 9)) \\ 75748 &:= (T(7) + (T(T(5)) \times (-C(7, 4) + T(T(8)))) \\ 75960 &:= ((-T(C(7, 5)) - T(T(9))) \times (-60)) \\ 75978 &:= (C(7, 5) \times ((9 \times T(T(7))) - T(8))) \\ 76245 &:= ((7 + 6) \times (C(T(T(T(2))), 4) - (T(T(5)))) \\ 76324 &:= (C((T(7) - 6), T(3)) + T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) \\ 76425 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C(T(4), T(2))) - (T(5))) \\ 76435 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C(T(4), 3)) - 5) \\ 76488 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(C(T(4), 8))) \times 8) \\ 76545 &:= (((T(7) \times T(T(6))) - C(T(5), 4)) \times T(5)) \\ 76573 &:= ((C(T(7), 6)/5) + T((T(7) + T(T(3)))) \\ 76582 &:= (T(T(C(7, 6))) + (T((T(5) + 8))^2)) \\ 76589 &:= -((T(T(C(7, 6))) - (T(58) \times T(9)))) \\ 76594 &:= (-T(T(C(7, 6))) - ((-5) - T(9)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 76617 &:= -((T((7 \times 6)) - C((T(6) - 1), 7))) \\ 76698 &:= ((T(T(C(7, 6))) \times (T(6) \times 9)) - T(8)) \\ 76832 &:= (T(7) \times ((6 + 8)^{C(3, 2)})) \\ 76888 &:= (T(C(7, 6)) \times (T(T(8)) + T((8 \times 8)))) \\ 76965 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) \times 9)) + T(T(C(6, 5)))) \\ 77224 &:= (-T(7) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-C(T(2), 2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 77321 &:= (((T(T(7)) + (C(T(7), 3))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 1) \\ 77322 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (C(T(7), 3))) \times T((2 \times T(2)))) \\ 77392 &:= (7 + (C(7, 3) \times T(T((9 + 2)))) \\ 77525 &:= (-((T(T(7)) - C(T(7), 5))) - C(T(T(T(2))), 5)) \\ 77527 &:= (7 + C(((T(7) - 5) - T(2)), 7)) \\ 77616 &:= (T(77) + C((T(6) + 1), 6)) \\ 78274 &:= (-7) \times ((T(C(8, T(2))) \times (-7)) - T(4)) \\ 78421 &:= ((-7) + T(T(8))) \times (C(T(4), T(2)) - 1) \\ 78479 &:= -((T(T(7)) - ((T(T(8)) \times C(T(4), 7)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 79534 &:= ((C(T(7), T((9 - 5)))/3)/T(T(4))) \\ 79692 &:= ((-((7 - C(9, 6))) \times T(T(9))) - T(2)) \\ 79695 &:= (-((7 - C(9, 6))) \times T((9 \times 5))) \\ 79723 &:= (T(7) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(C(7, 2))/3))) \\ 79847 &:= (-((T(7) + T(9))) + (T(T(8)) \times C(T(4), 7))) \\ 81395 &:= (T(T(8)) - (1 - C((3 \times 9), 5))) \\ 81396 &:= (T(C(C(8, 1), 3)) \times (T(9) + (6))) \\ 81928 &:= (T((8 - 1)) \times T((C(9, T(2)) - 8))) \\ 82368 &:= (C((-8) + T(T(T(2))), T(3)) \times (6 \times 8)) \\ 82425 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(4), T(2))) - T(5)) \\ 82435 &:= (((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(4), 3)) - 5) \\ 82544 &:= (C(8, 2) \times (C(T(5), T(4)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 82754 &:= (((-T(T(8))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(7), 5))) - T(T(T(4))) \\ 82992 &:= (T(C(8, T(2))) \times (T(9) + (9 - 2))) \\ 83104 &:= (-T(C(8, 3)) + (T(T(10)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 83214 &:= ((C(8, 3) - 2) \times (1 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 83382 &:= (((-T(8)^3) - C(T(T(3)), 8))/(-T(2))) \\ 83538 &:= ((T(8) \times C((3 + T(5)), T(3)))/8) \\ 83538 &:= ((T(8) \times C((3 + T(5)), T(3)))/8) \\ 83622 &:= (((-8) - (-3) \times C(T(6), T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 83625 &:= ((T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(C(6, 2)) + 5)) \\ 83768 &:= (8 \times (T(3) + (C(T(7), 6)/T(8)))) \\ 83895 &:= -((T((T(8)/T(3))) + (T(T(8)) \times (-C(9, 5)))) \\ 83916 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (T(3) + T((C(9, 1) + 6)))) \\ 83937 &:= ((T(C(8, 3)) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 7) \\ 83958 &:= ((T(8) + T(3)) - (-C(9, 5) \times T(T(8)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 83972** := $(-8) - ((C(T(T(3)), 9)/(-7)) \times 2)$
83975 := $((8 \times C(T(T(3)), 9))/T(7) - 5)$
84246 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(C(4, 2))) + T(T(4))) \times 6$
84294 := $((T(T(8)) + T((4 - 2))) \times C(9, 4))$
84425 := $(T(T((8 - 4))) \times (T(T(T(C(4, T(2)))))) - 5)$
84429 := $(-T(T(8))) - (T((T(T(4)) + C(4, 2))) \times (-T(9)))$
84476 := $((-8) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(C(7, 6))$
84529 := $-((T(T(8)) - (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(C(5, 2))) + 9))))$
84546 := $((T(8) + C((-4) + T(5)), 4) \times T(T(6)))$
84646 := $(T(T(8)) - ((T(T(4)) \times (-C(T(6), T(4))))/T(T(6))))$
84728 := $((T(C(8, 4)) + 7) \times (-2) + T(8))$
84732 := $(-T((8 \times 4))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(C(T(3), T(2))))$
84754 := $(T(T(8)) + (4 + (T(7) \times C(T(5), T(4))))$
84848 := $((T(T(8)) + (4 \times T(C(8, 4)))) \times 8$
84848 := $((T(T(8)) + (4 \times T(C(8, 4)))) \times 8$
85064 := $(C(8, 5) \times ((0 - T(6)) + T(T(T(4))))$
85065 := $((T(T(8)) + C(T(5), 06)) \times T(5))$
85134 := $-((T(T(8)) - (T(T(5)) \times C(13, 4)))$
85149 := $((T(C(8, 5)) \times (-1) + T(T(4))) - T(T(9)))$
85237 := $((-8) - T(5)) + (T(C(T(T(2)), 3)) \times T(T(7)))$
85272 := $(C((-8) + (T(5) \times 2)), 7)/2$
85296 := $(T(T(8)) - (-C(T(5), T(2))) \times (-T(9) + T(T(6))))$
85344 := $(C(8, 5) \times ((-T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(4))$
85461 := $((T(8) + C(T(5), 4)) \times 61)$
85764 := $(-T(8)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-C((7 + 6), 4)))$
85834 := $-((T(T((-8) + T(5))) - (C(8, 3) \times T(T(T(4))))))$
85968 := $(8 \times ((T(T(5)) \times C(9, 6)) + T(T(8))))$
85974 := $(-T(C(8, 5))) - (T(9) \times (-T(T(7)) - T(T(T(4))))))$
85984 := $((T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9)) + (C(8, 4)))$
86184 := $(T(8) \times (-T(6)) + T(-((1 - C(8, 4))))$
86212 := $(C(8, 6) \times (-2) + T(T(12)))$
86259 := $((C(8, 6) \times T(T(-(T(2) - T(5)))))) - 9$
86262 := $((C(8, 6) \times T(T((2 \times 6)))) - T(T(2)))$
86264 := $((C(8, 6) \times T(T((2 \times 6)))) - 4)$
86268 := $(C(8, 6) \times T(((2 \times T(6)) + T(8))))$
86268 := $(C(8, 6) \times T(((2 \times T(6)) + T(8))))$
86292 := $(-T(8)) \times (T(T(6)) - T((2 \times C(9, 2))))$
86324 := $(C(8, 6) \times (3 + (2 \times T(T(T(4))))))$
86422 := $(T(C(8, 6)) + ((4^{T(T(2))}) \times T(T(T(2))))$
86484 := $(-T(8)) - (-T(C(6, 4))) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4)))$
86548 := $(C(8, 6) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(8))))$
86658 := $((-8) + T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) + C(T(5), 8))$
86855 := $((8 + T(6)) \times (-8) + C(T(5), 5))$
86961 := $((T(8) \times T(69)) + T(C(6, 1)))$
86969 := $((8 + T(6)) + (C(9, 6) \times T(T(9))))$
87282 := $(-T(8)) - (-C(T(7), 2)) \times T(T((8 - 2)))$
87326 := $(8 - (-C(T(7), (T(3)/T(2)))) \times T(T(6)))$
87372 := $((C(8, 7)^{T(3)} - T(7))/T(2))$
87426 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) - C(T(4), 2)) \times 6$
87480 := $(-(8 - C(7, 4))) \times T(80)$
87641 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(T(C(4, 1)))$
87675 := $((T(8) \times T(T(7))) \times 6) - C(7, 5)$
87696 := $(T(C(8, 7)) \times (T(69) + T(6)))$
87732 := $((T(C(8, 7)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(3))) \times T(T(2))$
88248 := $(-8) - (-C(8, T(2))) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(8))$
88254 := $-((T(T(8)) - (T((T(8) + 2)) \times T(T(C(5, 4))))))$
88362 := $(T(T(8)) - (T(C(8, T(3))) \times (-6^{T(2)})))$
88425 := $((T(8) \times T(C(8, 4))) - T((T(2) \times T(5))))$
88452 := $(T(8) \times (T(C(8, 4)) - T((5 + 2))))$
88473 := $((T(8) \times (T(C(8, 4)) - T(7))) + T(T(3)))$
88482 := $((T(T(8)) + T(8)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(C(8, T(2))))$
88572 := $(T(T(8)) - (T(T((8 + 5))) \times (-C(7, 2))))$
88884 := $(T(8) \times (-((8 + 8) + T(C(8, 4))))$
89244 := $(T(T(8)) \times ((T(9) \times T(2)) - C(4, 4)))$
89298 := $-((T(T(8)) + (-C(9, T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(8))))$
89298 := $-((T(T(8)) + (-C(9, T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(8))))$
89667 := $(T((T(8) + T(9))) \times (-C(6, 6) + T(7)))$
89744 := $((T(8) \times T(C(9, 7))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 4$
89928 := $((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times C(9, T(2))) - T(8)$
89962 := $((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times C(9, 6)) - 2$
89964 := $((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times C(9, T((6 - 4))))$
91122 := $((T(9)^{C(1,1)+2}) - T(2))$
91126 := $((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + C(T(T(2)), 6))$
91131 := $((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + T(C(3, 1)))$
91737 := $(9 + (C(T((1 \times 7)), 3)) \times T(7))$
91772 := $((T(9) - 1) + (T(7) \times C(T(7), T(2))))$
91773 := $(T(9) + (T((1 \times 7)) \times C(T(7), 3)))$
92324 := $((-9) \times T(T(2))) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(4))$
92333 := $(-T(9)) + C((-2) + T(T(3))), (3 \times 3))$
92335 := $((T(9)^{T(2)}) + (C(T(T(3)), 3) - T(T(5))))$
92369 := $(-9) + C(((T(T(2)))/(-3)) + (T(6))), 9)$
92391 := $((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(C(9, 1)))$
92393 := $(9 + (C((-2) + T(T(3))), 9) + (T(3)))$
92397 := $(-9) + (C((-2) + T(T(3))), 9) + T(7))$
92459 := $((9^2) + C((4 + T(5)), 9))$

$$\begin{aligned} 92544 &:= ((C(9,2) - (-T(5) \times T(T(T(4)))) \times 4) \\ 92549 &:= (T((9 \times 2)) + C((T(5) + (4)), 9)) \\ 92586 &:= (-T(9) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (5 - T(C(8,6)))) \\ 92721 &:= ((T(9)^{T(2)} + T((T(7) \times C(2,1)))) \\ 92741 &:= (-T(T(9)) - ((T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) + T(C(4,1))) \\ 92742 &:= ((T(9)^{T(2)} - (-7) \times T(T(C(4,2)))) \\ 92757 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) + (-T(C(7,5))) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 92772 &:= ((-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(C(7,2)))) \\ 92988 &:= (T((9 - 2)) \times T((T(C(9,8)) + T(8))) \\ 93321 &:= (9 - ((T(3)^{T(3)} \times (-C(2,1))) \\ 93375 &:= ((T(T(9)) + T(C(T(3),3))) \times 75) \\ 93492 &:= ((T(T(9)) + (T((3 \times 4))) \times C(9, T(2))) \\ 93572 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - T(C(7, T(T(2)))) \\ 93591 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - C(9,1)) \\ 93599 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times T(T(5))) - C(9,9)) \\ 93702 &:= (-C(9,3) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(02)))) \\ 93786 &:= (T(((9/3) \times 7)) \times T(C(8,6))) \\ 93831 &:= (T(9) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(C(8,(3-1)))))) \\ 93933 &:= ((T((T(9) - 3)) + (T(C(9,3)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 93996 &:= ((-C(9,3) - T(T(9))) \times (-C(9,6))) \\ 94766 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(C(7,6))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 94878 &:= (-C(9,4) \times (-87 - T(T(8)))) \\ 95262 &:= (((C(9,5)^2) \times 6) + T(T(2))) \\ 95276 &:= ((T(T(9)) + (C(T(5), T(2)))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 95325 &:= (T((T(9) - T(5))) \times (T(C(T(3), T(2))) - (5))) \\ 95328 &:= (((C(9,5) \times T(T(3))) + 2) \times T(8)) \\ 95472 &:= (C(((9+5)+4), 7) \times T(2)) \\ 95544 &:= (9 \times (C((T(T(5))/5), 4) - T(4))) \\ 95755 &:= ((T(95) \times C(7,5)) - (5)) \\ 95895 &:= (T(9) + ((C(T(5), 8) - T(9)) \times T(5))) \\ 95940 &:= ((C(9,5) - 9) \times T(40)) \\ 96348 &:= (C(9,6) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) - 8)) \\ 96375 &:= ((T(9) - C(T(6), 3)) \times (-75)) \\ 96475 &:= (((T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) \times C(T(4), 7)) - (5)) \\ 96498 &:= ((T(C(9,6) + (4)) \times (-9) + T(8))) \\ 96522 &:= ((T(9) \times T(65)) - C(T(2), 2)) \\ 96526 &:= ((T(9) \times T(65)) + C(T(T(2)), 6)) \\ 96531 &:= ((T(9) \times T(65)) + T(C(3, 1))) \\ 96577 &:= (C((T(9) - T(6)), (5 + 7))/T(7)) \\ 96768 &:= ((96 \times T(C(7,6))) \times T(8)) \\ 96798 &:= (T((T(9) + (6))) \times (T(7) + T(C(9,8)))) \\ 96936 &:= (((T(C(9,6)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) \\ 96943 &:= -((T(T(9)) + ((C(T(6), 9) + (4))/(-3))) \\ 96975 &:= (((T(9) \times (-6)) - T(T(9))) + (C(T(7), 5))) \\ 97125 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C(T(7), (-1) + T(T(2)))) - T(T(5)))) \\ 97163 &:= ((T(9) + T(7)) \times (1 + C(T(6), 3))) \\ 97217 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C(T(7), (T(T(2)) - 1)) - T(7))) \\ 97266 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C(T(7), (2 + T(6))) + T(6))) \\ 97422 &:= ((-9) - (T(T(7)) \times (-C(T(4), T(2)))) \times 2) \\ 97425 &:= (T(T(9)) - (-T(C(7,4)) \times T((2 + T(5)))) \\ 97587 &:= ((-T(9)) - (-C(7,5) \times T(T(8)))) \times 7) \\ 97635 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C(T(7), T(6)))/(-3) + T(5))) \\ 97662 &:= ((-9) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) + C(6,2)) \\ 97775 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(T(T(T(7)/7)))) + (C(T(7), 5))) \\ 97776 &:= (T((97 - C(7,7))) \times T(6)) \\ 97846 &:= (T((C(9,7) - 8)) \times (T(4) + T(T(6)))) \\ 97865 &:= ((-9) - T(T(7))) + (C(C(8,6), 5)) \\ 98235 &:= -((T(9) - (C(C(8,(2 \times 3)), 5))) \\ 98325 &:= (T(9) + (C((C(8,3)/2), 5))) \\ 98355 &:= (-((T(9) - C(C(8, T(3)), 5))) + T(T(5))) \\ 98375 &:= ((98 - 3) + C(T(7), 5)) \\ 98663 &:= ((C((-9) + T(8)), T(6)) - T(6))/3) \\ 98682 &:= ((C((-9) + T(8)), T(6)) + T(8))/T(2)) \\ 98752 &:= ((T((T(9) - 8)) + (C(T(7), 5))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 99315 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(((9 \times 3) + 1), 5))) \\ 99486 &:= (-9) + (T(9) \times T((C(T(4), 8) + T(6)))) \\ 99492 &:= ((T(T((C(9,9) + T(4)))) \times T(9)) - T(2)) \\ 99552 &:= (C((9 + 9), T(5)) \times (T(T(5)) + 2)) \\ 99765 &:= (T((9 + T(9))) + (C(T(C(7,6)), 5))) \\ 99792 &:= ((99 \times T(7)) \times C(9, 2)) \\ 9981 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times 9) + T(T(C(8,1)))) \\ 99912 &:= -((T(T(9)) - C((T(T(9))/T(9)), T((1+2)))) \\ 99933 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C((T(T(9))/T(9)), T(3)) + T(T(3)))) \\ 99937 &:= ((T(T(9)))/(-T(9))) + ((T(C(9,3)) \times T(7))) \\ 99945 &:= -((T((C(9,9) + 9)) - (T(4)^5))) \end{aligned}$$

3 Binomial Coefficients Triangular Type Selfie Numbers: Reverse Order of Digits

This subsection brings **binomial coefficients triangular type selfie numbers** just with basic operations. The results are in reverse order of digits. The work is up to 5 digits. This section is divided in three parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for symmetrical and non consecutive. The third representations are for general way.

3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned} 1330 &:= 0 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1331 &:= 1 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1332 &:= 2 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1333 &:= 3 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1334 &:= 4 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1335 &:= 5 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1336 &:= 6 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1337 &:= 7 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1338 &:= 8 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \\ 1339 &:= 9 + C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3270 &:= 0 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3271 &:= 1 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3272 &:= 2 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3273 &:= 3 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3274 &:= 4 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3275 &:= 5 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3276 &:= 6 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3277 &:= 7 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3278 &:= 8 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\ 3279 &:= 9 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 04390 &:= 0 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04391 &:= 1 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04392 &:= 2 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04393 &:= 3 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04394 &:= 4 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04395 &:= 5 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04396 &:= 6 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04397 &:= 7 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04398 &:= 8 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\ 04399 &:= 9 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13860 &:= 0 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13861 &:= 1 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13862 &:= 2 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13863 &:= 3 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13864 &:= 4 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13865 &:= 5 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13866 &:= 6 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13867 &:= 7 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13868 &:= 8 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \\ 13869 &:= 9 - (6 - T(T(8))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14490 &:= 0 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14491 &:= 1 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14492 &:= 2 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14493 &:= 3 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14494 &:= 4 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14495 &:= 5 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14496 &:= 6 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14497 &:= 7 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14498 &:= 8 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \\ 14499 &:= 9 + T(T(9)) \times (4 + T(C(4, 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21420 &:= 0 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21421 &:= 1 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21422 &:= 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21423 &:= 3 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21424 &:= 4 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21425 &:= 5 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21426 &:= 6 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21427 &:= 7 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21428 &:= 8 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \\ 21429 &:= 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22560 &:= 0 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22561 &:= 1 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22562 &:= 2 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22563 &:= 3 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22564 &:= 4 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22565 &:= 5 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22566 &:= 6 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22567 &:= 7 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22568 &:= 8 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 22569 &:= 9 + C(T(6), 5) + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22680 &:= 0 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22681 &:= 1 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22682 &:= 2 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22683 &:= 3 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22684 &:= 4 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22685 &:= 5 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22686 &:= 6 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22687 &:= 7 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22688 &:= 8 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \\ 22689 &:= 9 + T(8) \times C(T(6), 2) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23850 &:= 0 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23851 &:= 1 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23852 &:= 2 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23853 &:= 3 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23854 &:= 4 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23855 &:= 5 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23856 &:= 6 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23857 &:= 7 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23858 &:= 8 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23859 &:= 9 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24570 &:= 0 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24571 &:= 1 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24572 &:= 2 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24573 &:= 3 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24574 &:= 4 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24575 &:= 5 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24576 &:= 6 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24577 &:= 7 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24578 &:= 8 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \\ 24579 &:= 9 + C(T(7), 5)/C(4, T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24850 &:= 0 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24851 &:= 1 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24852 &:= 2 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24853 &:= 3 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24854 &:= 4 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24855 &:= 5 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24856 &:= 6 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24857 &:= 7 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24858 &:= 8 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24859 &:= 9 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26250 &:= 0 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26251 &:= 1 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26252 &:= 2 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26253 &:= 3 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26254 &:= 4 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26255 &:= 5 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26256 &:= 6 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26257 &:= 7 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26258 &:= 8 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26259 &:= 9 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27930 &:= 0 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27931 &:= 1 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27932 &:= 2 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27933 &:= 3 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27934 &:= 4 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27935 &:= 5 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27936 &:= 6 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27937 &:= 7 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27938 &:= 8 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27939 &:= 9 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28980 &:= 0 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28981 &:= 1 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28982 &:= 2 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28983 &:= 3 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28984 &:= 4 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28985 &:= 5 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28986 &:= 6 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \end{aligned}$$

$28987 := 7 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2)$	$36843 := 3 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$
$28988 := 8 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2)$	$36844 := 4 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$
$28989 := 9 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2)$	$36845 := 5 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$
$33250 := 0 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$36846 := 6 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$
$33251 := 1 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$36847 := 7 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$
$33252 := 2 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$36848 := 8 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$
$33253 := 3 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$36849 := 9 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$
$33254 := 4 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$37890 := 0 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$33255 := 5 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$37891 := 1 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$33256 := 6 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$37892 := 2 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$33257 := 7 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$37893 := 3 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$33258 := 8 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$37894 := 4 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$33259 := 9 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)$	$37895 := 5 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$34220 := 0 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$37896 := 6 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$34221 := 1 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$37897 := 7 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$34222 := 2 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$37898 := 8 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$34223 := 3 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$37899 := 9 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7, 3))$
$34224 := 4 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$38430 := 0 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34225 := 5 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$38431 := 1 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34226 := 6 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$38432 := 2 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34227 := 7 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$38433 := 3 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34228 := 8 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$38434 := 4 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34229 := 9 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$	$38435 := 5 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34650 := 0 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38436 := 6 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34651 := 1 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38437 := 7 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34652 := 2 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38438 := 8 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34653 := 3 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38439 := 9 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8, 3))$
$34654 := 4 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38760 := 0 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
$34655 := 5 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38761 := 1 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
$34656 := 6 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38762 := 2 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
$34657 := 7 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38763 := 3 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
$34658 := 8 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38764 := 4 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
$34659 := 9 + T(5) \times T(T(6)) \times T(C(4, 3))$	$38765 := 5 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
$36840 := 0 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$	$38766 := 6 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
$36841 := 1 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$	$38767 := 7 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
$36842 := 2 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6, 3))$	$38768 := 8 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
	$38769 := 9 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3))$
	$42350 := 0 + T(T(C(5, 3))) / 2 \times T(T(4))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42351 &:= 1 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\
 42352 &:= 2 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\
 42353 &:= 3 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\
 42354 &:= 4 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\
 42355 &:= 5 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\
 42356 &:= 6 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\
 42357 &:= 7 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\
 42358 &:= 8 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\
 42359 &:= 9 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48620 &:= 0 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48621 &:= 1 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48622 &:= 2 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48623 &:= 3 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48624 &:= 4 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48625 &:= 5 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48626 &:= 6 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48627 &:= 7 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48628 &:= 8 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4) \\
 48629 &:= 9 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53130 &:= 0 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53131 &:= 1 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53132 &:= 2 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53133 &:= 3 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53134 &:= 4 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53135 &:= 5 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53136 &:= 6 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53137 &:= 7 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53138 &:= 8 + C(31 - T(3), 5) \\
 53139 &:= 9 + C(31 - T(3), 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53340 &:= 0 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53341 &:= 1 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53342 &:= 2 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53343 &:= 3 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53344 &:= 4 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53345 &:= 5 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53346 &:= 6 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53347 &:= 7 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53348 &:= 8 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$53349 := 9 + (-4 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53970 &:= 0 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53971 &:= 1 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53972 &:= 2 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53973 &:= 3 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53974 &:= 4 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53975 &:= 5 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53976 &:= 6 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53977 &:= 7 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53978 &:= 8 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\
 53979 &:= 9 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54330 &:= 0 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54331 &:= 1 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54332 &:= 2 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54333 &:= 3 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54334 &:= 4 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54335 &:= 5 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54336 &:= 6 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54337 &:= 7 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54338 &:= 8 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\
 54339 &:= 9 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54670 &:= 0 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54671 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54672 &:= 2 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54673 &:= 3 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54674 &:= 4 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54675 &:= 5 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54676 &:= 6 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54677 &:= 7 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54678 &:= 8 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5) \\
 54679 &:= 9 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), T(4) + 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64260 &:= 0 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6) \\
 64261 &:= 1 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6) \\
 64262 &:= 2 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6) \\
 64263 &:= 3 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6) \\
 64264 &:= 4 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6) \\
 64265 &:= 5 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6) \\
 64266 &:= 6 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$64267 := 7 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64268 := 8 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64269 := 9 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$67830 := 0 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67831 := 1 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67832 := 2 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67833 := 3 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67834 := 4 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67835 := 5 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67836 := 6 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67837 := 7 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67838 := 8 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67839 := 9 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$74250 := 0 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74251 := 1 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74252 := 2 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74253 := 3 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74254 := 4 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74255 := 5 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74256 := 6 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74257 := 7 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74258 := 8 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$74259 := 9 + T(5) \times T(-T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(4), 7)$$

$$76230 := 0 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76231 := 1 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76232 := 2 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76233 := 3 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76234 := 4 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76235 := 5 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76236 := 6 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76237 := 7 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76238 := 8 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$76239 := 9 + T(T(T(3))) \times C(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6), 7)$$

$$77520 := 0 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77521 := 1 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77522 := 2 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77523 := 3 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77524 := 4 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77525 := 5 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77526 := 6 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77527 := 7 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77528 := 8 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77529 := 9 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$79920 := 0 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79921 := 1 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79922 := 2 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79923 := 3 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79924 := 4 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79925 := 5 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79926 := 6 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79927 := 7 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79928 := 8 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$79929 := 9 + T(T(T(2)) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))$$

$$85260 := 0 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85261 := 1 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85262 := 2 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85263 := 3 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85264 := 4 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85265 := 5 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85266 := 6 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85267 := 7 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85268 := 8 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85269 := 9 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

3.2 Symmetric and Non Consecutive

$$38519 := -91 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)$$

$$38528 := -82 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38537 &:= -73 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \\ 38546 &:= -64 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \\ 38555 &:= -55 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \\ 38564 &:= -46 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \\ 38573 &:= -37 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \\ 38582 &:= -28 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \\ 38591 &:= -19 + C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

3.3 General Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 15 &:= T(C(5, 1)) \\ 168 &:= (8 \times T(C(6, 1))) \\ 254 &:= (C(T(4), 5) + 2) \\ 286 &:= C((T(6) - 8), T(2)) \\ 378 &:= T(-((8 - C(7, 3)))) \\ 525 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times 5) \\ 637 &:= (T(T(C(7, T(3)))) + T(T(6))) \\ 792 &:= C((T(2) + 9), 7) \\ 0139 &:= (C(9, 3) + T(10)) \\ 0238 &:= (C(8, T(3)) + T(20)) \\ 1129 &:= (T((T(9) + 2)) + C(1, 1)) \\ 1134 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T((T(3) + C(1, 1)))) \\ 1156 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 5) + C(1, 1)) \\ 1176 &:= T((6 \times C((7 + 1), 1)) \\ 1227 &:= (T((7^2)) + C(2, 1)) \\ 1266 &:= (6 \times (C(T(6), 2) + 1)) \\ 1326 &:= (C(T(6), T(2)) - (3 + 1)) \\ 1329 &:= (C(T((9 - T(2))), 3) - 1) \\ 1345 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) - T(T(3))) + 1) \\ 1356 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 5) \times T(C(3, 1))) \\ 1365 &:= C(T(5), ((6 - 3) + 1)) \\ 1368 &:= (8 \times T(C((6 \times 3), 1)) \\ 1386 &:= (T(6) \times T(C((8 + 3), 1))) \\ 1389 &:= ((T(9) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(C(3, 1)))) \\ 1435 &:= (T(53) + C(4, 1)) \\ 1449 &:= (-T((9 + 4)) + T(T(T(C(4, 1)))) \\ 1462 &:= (-T((2 \times 6)) + T(T(T(C(4, 1)))) \\ 1464 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (T(6) + T(T(C(4, 1)))) \\ 1483 &:= (-((T(T(3)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(C(4, 1)))) \\ 1484 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - C(8, (4 - 1))) \\ 1487 &:= (T(T(7)) + T((T(8) + T(C(4, 1)))) \\ 1494 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (-9) + T(T(C(4, 1)))) \\ 1525 &:= (-T(5) + T(T(C((2 \times 5), 1))) \\ 1534 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - C(T(3), C(5, 1))) \\ 1535 &:= (T(T(C(5, 3))) - C(5, 1)) \\ 1536 &:= (T(C(6, 3)) + T(51)) \\ 1557 &:= (T(C(7, 5)) + T(51)) \\ 1568 &:= (C(8, 6) + T(T(T((5 - 1)))) \\ 1575 &:= ((T(5) \times 7) \times T(C(5, 1))) \\ 1588 &:= (-8) + T((C(8, 5) \times 1)) \\ 1617 &:= (7 \times T(T(C((1 \times 6), 1))) \\ 1638 &:= (T((T(8)/3)) \times T(C(6, 1))) \\ 1653 &:= T((T(3 + 5)) + T(C(6, 1))) \\ 1654 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - C(6, 1))) \\ 1736 &:= (C(T(6), 3) + T(T(C(7, 1)))) \\ 1938 &:= (T((T(8) + T(3))) + T(T(C(9, 1)))) \\ 1998 &:= (T(T(8)) \times T((C(9, 9) + 1))) \\ 2024 &:= C((4 + 20), T(2)) \\ 2079 &:= (9 \times T(C(7, 02))) \\ 2205 &:= (C(T(5), 02) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2211 &:= T(C((1 \times 12), 2)) \\ 2226 &:= (T((T(6) \times T(2))) + T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) \\ 2255 &:= (C((T(T(5))/5), T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2268 &:= ((T(8) \times T(6)) \times C(T(2), 2)) \\ 2275 &:= (5 \times C(T((7 - 2)), T(2))) \\ 2278 &:= T(((C(8, 7)^2) + T(2))) \\ 2288 &:= (8 \times C((-8) + T(T(T(2))), T(2))) \\ 2295 &:= (T(5) \times C((9 \times 2), 2)) \\ 2353 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5))/T(T(3))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 2354** := $((4^5) + C(T(T(3)), T(2)))$
2358 := $((T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times C(3, 2))$
2365 := $-((T(T(5)) - T((C(6, 3)/T(2))))$
2388 := $((-8) + T(C(8, T(3)))) \times T(T(2))$
2447 := $(-T(7)) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(4), 2))$
2475 := $T(5) \times C((7 + 4), T(2))$
2484 := $((-4) + T(C(8, 4))) + T(2)$
2488 := $(T(C(8, (8 - 4))) + T(2))$
2539 := $(-T(9)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5))/T(T(T(2))))$
2558 := $(T((C(8, 5) + T(5))) + 2)$
2569 := $((T(T(9)) - 6) + T(T(C(5, 2))))$
2595 := $(T(T(5)) + (T(9) \times T(C(5, 2))))$
2596 := $((T(6) + T(T(9))) + T(T(C(5, 2))))$
2597 := $-((T(T(7)) - C(9 + 5), T(T(2))))$
2605 := $(T(50) + C(T(6), T(2)))$
2627 := $(T(72) - C(6, T(T(2))))$
2629 := $(T(9) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6)/T(T(T(2))))$
2649 := $((C(9, 4) \times T(6)) + T(2))$
2684 := $((4 \times T(T(8))) + C(6, T(2)))$
2748 := $-((T((8 \times 4)) - C(T(7), T(2))))$
2779 := $((-9) + T(T(7))) \times C(7, T(T(2)))$
2829 := $(T(C(9, T(2))) - T((T(8) + 2)))$
2856 := $(T(C(6, 5)) \times T((8 \times 2)))$
2878 := $(T(8) - (-7) \times T(C(8, 2)))$
2897 := $-((T(7) - C((-9) + T(8)), T(2)))$
2925 := $C(((5 - 2) \times 9), T(2))$
2926 := $T((T(6) + (C(2 + 9), 2)))$
2935 := $(C(T(5), T(3)) - (T(T(9)) \times 2))$
2945 := $(-((5^4)) + T(C(9, T(2))))$
2955 := $((C(T(5), 5) - T(9)) - T(2))$
3192 := $(2 \times T(C((9 - 1), 3)))$
3248 := $(8 \times T(C((4 \times 2), T(3))))$
3264 := $(4 \times C((T(6) - T(2)), 3))$
3268 := $(-8) + C(T((T(6)/T(2))), 3)$
3282 := $(C(28, T(2)) + T(3))$
3297 := $(C(T(7), (9/T(2))) + T(T(3)))$
3325 := $((T(5) \times C(T(T(T(2))), 3))/T(3))$
3328 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(2)) + C(T(T(3)), 3))$
3339 := $(T(C(9, 3)) - T(T(3 + 3)))$
3353 := $((-C(T(T(3)), 5) + T(T(T(3))))/(-T(3)))$
3394 := $((T(T(4)) + (T(C(9, 3)))) - T(T(T(3))))$
3432 := $(2 \times C((3 + T(4)), T(3)))$
3445 := $(C(T(5), 4) + T((4^3)))$
3478 := $(-8) + T((T(7) + T(T(C(4, 3))))$
3536 := $(T(T((6 + T(3)))) + (C(T(5), 3)))$
3538 := $((T(T(8)) \times 3) + T(T(C(5, 3))))$
3565 := $(-5) + T(C((-6) + T(5)), 3))$
3569 := $((T(C(9, 6)) + 5) - T(3))$
3654 := $C(((T(4) \times 5) - T(6)), 3)$
3755 := $((5^5) + T(C(7, 3)))$
3765 := $-((T(5) - (6 \times T(C(7, 3))))$
3772 := $(T((T(2) + T(7))) + (C(T(7), 3)))$
3784 := $(4 \times T((8 + C(7, 3))))$
3837 := $(C(T(7), 3) + T((T(8) - 3)))$
3876 := $(C(T(6), 7)/(T(8) - T(3)))$
3888 := $(T(88) - C(8, T(3)))$
3976 := $(T((T(6) + 7)) + (T(C(9, 3))))$
4241 := $(T(C(14, 2)) + T(T(4)))$
4278 := $T((8 + (C(7, 2) \times 4)))$
4288 := $(T((T(8) + C(8, T(2)))) + T(4))$
4422 := $(2 \times T(C((2 + T(4)), T(4)))$
4425 := $(T(5) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-C(T(4), 4))))$
4469 := $(T((C(9, 6) + T(4))) + 4)$
4522 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2)))/T(T(5))/T(4))$
4525 := $(C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times (-4)))$
4543 := $(T(T((T(3) + 4))) + (C(T(5), T(4))))$
4696 := $(T(T(6)) + T((C(9, 6) + T(4))))$
5026 := $(C(T(5), T(T(02))) + T(6))$
5125 := $(C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(15))$
5356 := $((T(T(6)) + C(T(5), T(3))) + T(T(5)))$
5365 := $(C(T(5), 6) - (-3) \times T(T(5)))$
5425 := $((-C(T(5), T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5)$
5445 := $((C(T(5), 4) \times 4) - T(5))$
5635 := $(T(T(C(5, 3))) + T((6 \times T(5))))$
5676 := $(6 \times T((T(C(7, 6)) + T(5))))$
5796 := $(T(6) \times (T(9) + T(C(7, 5))))$
5825 := $(C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T((8 \times 5)))$
5979 := $((T(C(9, 7)) \times 9) - T(5))$
5985 := $C(-((T(5) - T(8)), (9 - 5))$
6162 := $(2 \times T(T((C(6, 1) + 6)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6216 &:= (C(T(6), (1 + T(2))) + T(T(6))) \\
 6429 &:= ((T(C(9, 2)) \times T(4)) - T(T(6))) \\
 6435 &:= C(T(5), C((3 + 4), 6)) \\
 6524 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(5), 6)) \\
 6542 &:= ((-T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) + C(T(5), 6)) \\
 6825 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times (T(8) - T(6))) \\
 6853 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 8) + C(T(5), T(3))) \\
 6864 &:= (4 \times C((T(6) - 8), 6)) \\
 7224 &:= ((T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(2)) \times 7) \\
 7242 &:= (-T(2) - (T(C(T(4), 2)) \times (-7))) \\
 7483 &:= ((3 \times T(C(8, 4))) + T(7)) \\
 7752 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(-(5 - 7))))/7) \\
 7753 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + (7))/7) \\
 7756 &:= ((C(T(6), T(5)) + T(7))/7) \\
 7956 &:= (6 \times T((T(5) + C(9, 7)))) \\
 7992 &:= ((T(2) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))) \\
 8336 &:= (C(6, 3) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(8))) \\
 8532 &:= (C((T(2) \times T(3)), 5) - T(8)) \\
 9225 &:= ((-5) + T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) \times T(9)) \\
 9445 &:= (-5) + (C(T(4), 4) \times T(9)) \\
 \\
 01228 &:= ((T(C(8, 2)) \times T(2)) + 10) \\
 01234 &:= (C(T(4), T(3)) + (2^{10})) \\
 01235 &:= (T((T(C(5, 3)) - T(T(2)))) + 10) \\
 01246 &:= (T(6) + T((-C(4, 2)) + T(10))) \\
 01335 &:= ((5 - T(C(T(3), 3))) + T(T(10))) \\
 01355 &:= (C(T(5), (5 + T(3))) - 10) \\
 01357 &:= (-C(7, 5) + T((-3) + T(10))) \\
 01386 &:= (T(6) \times (C(8, 3) + 10)) \\
 01423 &:= ((3 - T(C(T(T(2)), 4))) + T(T(10))) \\
 01424 &:= (-((C(T(4), T(2)) - (4))) + T(T(10))) \\
 01425 &:= (-((C(T(5), 2) + T(4))) + T(T(10))) \\
 01428 &:= (C(8, 2) \times (-4) + T(10)) \\
 01463 &:= (C(-(T(3) - T(6)), T(4)) - T(T(10))) \\
 01522 &:= (-((C(T(2), 2) + T(5))) + T(T(10))) \\
 01564 &:= ((4 \times C(6, 5)) + T(T(10))) \\
 01568 &:= (C(8, C(6, 5)) + T(T(10))) \\
 01583 &:= ((-3) + T(C(8, 5))) - 10) \\
 01745 &:= ((T(5) \times C(T(4), 7)) - T(10)) \\
 01754 &:= ((C(T(4), 5) \times 7) - 10) \\
 01755 &:= (T(5) \times (C(T(5), 7)/T(10))) \\
 01927 &:= ((C(T(7), 2) + 9) + T(T(10)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 02234 &:= (C((4 \times T(3)), T(2)) + T(20)) \\
 02255 &:= ((5 \times C(T(5), T(2))) - (20)) \\
 02482 &:= -((T(2) - T((C(8, 4) + (2 \times 0)))) \\
 02486 &:= ((T(6) + T(C(8, 4))) - (20)) \\
 03276 &:= C((T(6) + (7)), T((2 + (3 \times 0)))) \\
 03327 &:= ((C(T(7), T(2)) + T(T(3))) + (30)) \\
 03345 &:= ((T(C(5, 4))^3) - (30)) \\
 03424 &:= (-T(T(C(4, 2)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (30))) \\
 03459 &:= (-9) + (C(T(5), T(4)) + T(30)) \\
 03468 &:= (C((T(8) - T(6)), T(4)) + T(30)) \\
 03599 &:= (-C(9, 9) + (T(T(5)) \times 30)) \\
 03795 &:= ((5 \times T(C(9, 7))) + T(30)) \\
 04137 &:= (C(T(7), 3) + T((1 + 40))) \\
 04185 &:= (C(T(5), (8 + 1)) - T(40)) \\
 04226 &:= (T(T((C(6, 2) - 2))) + 40) \\
 04275 &:= (5 \times (C(7, T(2)) + T(40))) \\
 04369 &:= ((T(C(9, 6)) - T(T(3))) + (T(40))) \\
 05676 &:= (6 \times T(-(C(7, 6) - 50))) \\
 05823 &:= (C(3, 2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(50))) \\
 05985 &:= (C(T(5), 8) - ((9 \times 50))) \\
 06273 &:= (-T(3) - (C(T(7), T(T(2))))/(-60)) \\
 06375 &:= (C(T(5), C(7, T(3))) - (60)) \\
 06384 &:= (4 \times T((C(8, 3) + (6 \times 0)))) \\
 06485 &:= ((C(T(5), 8) - T(4)) + (60)) \\
 06835 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(-(T(3) - 8)))) + T(60)) \\
 06955 &:= (T(T(5)) + (C(T(5), 9) + T(60))) \\
 06975 &:= (C(T(5), 7) + (9 \times 60)) \\
 07435 &:= ((C(T(5), T(3)) - T(T(4))) + (T(70))) \\
 07455 &:= (-((C(5, 5) - 4)) \times T(70)) \\
 07752 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))/(7 + (7 \times 0))) \\
 08165 &:= (C(T(5), 6) + T(-(1 - 80))) \\
 08245 &:= (C(T(5), C(4, 2)) + T(80)) \\
 09565 &:= (C(T(5), 6) + T((5 + 90))) \\
 \\
 10392 &:= (-T(2) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(C(3, 01)))))) \\
 10395 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times T(T(T(C(3, 01)))) \\
 10626 &:= C((T(6) + T(2)), (T(6) - 01)) \\
 11025 &:= (C(T(5), 2)^{01+1}) \\
 11223 &:= (3 \times T((C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + (T(11)))) \\
 11253 &:= (3 \times (T(T(C(5, 2))) + T(T(11)))) \\
 11256 &:= (T(T(6)) + (C(T(5), 2)^{1+1})) \\
 11346 &:= (6 \times T(((T(4) \times T(3)) + C(1, 1)))) \\
 11367 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(6)/3))) - C(1, 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 11368** := $(T(C(8, 6)) \times T((T(3) + C(1, 1))))$
11384 := $((C(T(4), 8) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1))) - 1)$
11562 := $(C((-2) + T(6), 5) - T(11))$
11774 := $(T((4 \times 7)) \times (T(7) + C(1, 1)))$
11775 := $(T(5) \times ((T(7) \times T(7)) + C(1, 1)))$
11935 := $(T(T(C(5, 3))) - (-T(9) \times T(T(T(T((1 + 1)))))))$
11988 := $(T(T(8)) \times (C((8 + 9), 1) + 1))$
12225 := $(T(5) \times (C((T(T(2)) \times T(2)), T(2)) - 1))$
12248 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(2)^{C(2, 1)})))$
12255 := $(T(5) \times (C((T(5) + T(2)), T(2)) + 1))$
12284 := $((T((C(T(4), 8) \times 2)) \times T(2)) - 1)$
12318 := $((8 \times T(T(T((1 + 3)))) - C(2, 1))$
12324 := $(4 \times T(T(C((2 \times 3) \times 2), 1)))$
12374 := $(C((T(4) + (7)), T(3)) - C(2, 1))$
12375 := $(C((-5) + T(7) - T(3), T(T(2))) - 1)$
12376 := $(C((T(6) - (7 - 3)), T((2 + 1)))$
12377 := $(C(((7 + 7) + 3), T(T(2))) + 1)$
12379 := $(C((T(9) - T(7)), T(3)) + (2 + 1))$
12397 := $(C(-(T(7) - T(9)), T(3)) + (21))$
12398 := $((C((8 + 9), T(3)) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1)$
12421 := $((12 \times T(C(T(4), 2))) + 1)$
12422 := $(2 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 2))) + 1))$
12424 := $(-4) \times ((-T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 2))) - 1)$
12448 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + C((4^2), 1)))$
12454 := $(-C(T(4), 5) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1))$
12495 := $(T((5 + 9)) \times (C(T(4), T(2)) - 1))$
12544 := $((-(4 + 4) + T(T(5)))^{C(2, 1)})$
12558 := $(T(T((8 + 5))) \times C((5 - 2), 1))$
12585 := $(T(5) \times ((8 \times C(T(5), 2)) - 1))$
12597 := $(T((-7) + T(9)) \times (T(5) + C(2, 1)))$
12643 := $((C((T(T(3)) + 4), T(6)) - T(T(2))) - 1)$
12645 := $(-5) + C((4 + T(6)), 21)$
12646 := $((C((T(6) + 4), T(6)) - T(2)) - 1)$
12652 := $(C(25, T(6)) + C(2, 1))$
12655 := $((C((5 \times 5), T(6)) + T(T(2))) - 1)$
12672 := $((C(-(T(2) - T(7)), T(6)) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1)$
12704 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(C(07, 2))) - 1)$
12725 := $((C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(7)) - T((T(T(2)) - 1)))$
12735 := $((C(T(5), 3) \times T(7)) - T(T(2))) + 1)$
12749 := $(T(9) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(C(7, 2))) - 1))$
12769 := $((T((9 + 6)) - (7))^{C(2, 1)})$
12785 := $(5 \times (T((T(8) + C(7, T(2)))) + 1))$
12815 := $(C((T(5) + 1), 8) - T(T((T(2) + 1))))$
12823 := $((T(T(T(3))) - 2) \times C(8, T(2))) - 1)$
12842 := $(C((2^4), 8) - T((T(T(2)) + 1)))$
12848 := $(8 \times (T(4) + T(C(8, (2 + 1)))))$
12855 := $((T(5) + (C(T(5), 8) \times (-2))) \times (-1))$
12857 := $((7 - C(T(5), 8)) \times (-2)) + 1)$
12864 := $(C((T(4) + (6)), 8) - T((2 + 1)))$
12885 := $((C(T(5), 8) + 8) \times 2) - 1)$
12936 := $(T(T(6)) \times ((T(3) \times 9) + C(2, 1)))$
12996 := $((69 + T(9))^{C(2, 1)})$
12997 := $((T(T(7)) - (T(9))) \times C(9, 2)) + 1)$
13227 := $((T(C(7, T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - C(3, 1))$
13231 := $((T(C((1 + T(3)), T(2))) \times T(T(3))) + 1)$
13233 := $(3 \times ((T(C(T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3))) + 1))$
13237 := $(7 \times T(((C(T(3), T(2)) \times 3) + 1)))$
13248 := $(T(8) \times (-T(4) + T((T(2))^{C(3, 1)})))$
13254 := $((T(T((-4) + T(5))) - 2) \times T(C(3, 1)))$
13269 := $((T((T(9) + T(6))) \times T(T(2))) + C(3, 1))$
13272 := $((2 + T(C(7, T(2)))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))))$
13293 := $((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9)))/2) \times T(T(C(3, 1))))$
13301 := $((10 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) + 1)$
13319 := $((T(T((9 - 1))) \times C(T(3), 3)) - 1)$
13338 := $(T((T(8)/3)) \times T((3 \times T(C(3, 1)))))$
13356 := $(T((6 \times T(5))) + (T(T(3))^{C(3, 1)}))$
13377 := $((7 + T(C(7, 3))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))))$
13394 := $((T((T(4) + (C(9, 3)))) \times 3) - 1)$
13419 := $(9 \times (T((-1) + T(T(4)))) + T(C(3, 1)))$
13479 := $((T(9) \times T((T(7) - 4))) - T(T(C(3, 1))))$
13524 := $((T(42) \times T(5)) - T(T(C(3, 1))))$
13536 := $((C(T(6), T(3)) - T(T(5)))/(3 + 1))$
13539 := $((T((T(9) - 3)) \times T(5)) - T(C(3, 1)))$
13557 := $(((-7) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(5))) - C(3, 1))$
13563 := $((-3) - (C(T(6), T(5)))/(-3 + 1)))$
13566 := $(C(T(6), C(6, 5))/(3 + 1))$
13568 := $((8 + C(T(6), T(5)))/(3 + 1))$
13586 := $((C(T(6), 8)/T(5)) + T(T(3))) - 1)$
13649 := $((9 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(C(6, 3)) + 1))$
13687 := $((C(T(7), 8)/T(T(6))) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1)$
13728 := $(C((8 + T(T(2))), 7) \times (3 + 1))$
13776 := $((T(T((6 + 7))) + T(T(7))) \times C(3, 1))$
13797 := $((T(7) + T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))))$
13818 := $((-8) + T(T((1 \times 8)))) \times T(T(C(3, 1))))$

- 13845 := $(T(5) \times (C((4+8), T(3)) - 1))$
13849 := $((9 \times T(T(T(4)))) - C((8+3), 1))$
13878 := $((T(T(8)) \times 7) - T(8)) \times C(3, 1)$
13888 := $(T((8 - C(8, 8))) \times T(31))$
13923 := $(T(T(3)) \times (-(T(2) - T(C(9, (3 - 1))))))$
13926 := $((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(C(3, 1))))))$
13938 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - (T(9) + C(3, 1)))$
13942 := $(-2) - (-4 \times T((C(9, 3) - 1)))$
13983 := $((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - C((9/3), 1))$
13992 := $(T(T(2)) + (T((T(9) - 9)) \times T(T(C(3, 1)))))$
14139 := $(9 \times (31 + T(T(T(C(4, 1))))))$
14184 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(8)) \times (-1 + T(C(4, 1))))$
14224 := $T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14228 := $((T((T(8) \times 2)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(T(C(4, 1)))))$
14242 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(2) - T(T(T(C(4, 1))))))$
14243 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) - 2) + T(T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14269 := $((T(C(9, 6)) - T(2)) \times 4) + 1$
14272 := $((-2) + T((T(7) \times T(2)))) \times C(4, 1)$
14275 := $(-5) - (T((T(7) \times T(2))) \times (-C(4, 1)))$
14281 := $((T(C((1+8), T(2))) \times 4) + 1)$
14292 := $((-T(2)) - T(C(9, T(2)))) \times (-C(4, 1))$
14293 := $(((-3) - T(C(9, T(2)))) \times (-4)) + 1$
14326 := $((62 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(4, 1))$
14345 := $((T(T(5))^{-4+T(3)} - T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14357 := $(7 \times (C(T(5), 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))))$
14382 := $((2 + T(C(8, 3))) \times (T(4) - 1))$
14419 := $((9 \times T((1 + T(T(4)))) + T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14448 := $(8 \times (C(T(4), 4) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))))$
14455 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(C(4, (4 - 1)))))$
14568 := $(8 \times (C((T(6) - 5), 4) + 1))$
14588 := $((-8) + T(85)) \times C(4, 1)$
14624 := $((C(T(4), 2) \times T((T(6) + (4)))) - 1)$
14648 := $(8 \times (T((4 \times C(6, 4)) + 1))$
14676 := $(-6) \times ((T(T(7)) \times (-6)) - T(C(4, 1)))$
14679 := $(9 \times (T(T(7)) + T((-6) + T(T(C(4, 1))))))$
14682 := $((-T(2)) - ((-T(8)) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14727 := $(((-C(T(7), T(2))) - T(T(7))) \times (-4)) - 1$
14728 := $(C(8, 2) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T((4 + 1))))$
14752 := $((2^5) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14756 := $((T((6 \times T(5))) - T(T(7))) \times C(4, 1))$
14774 := $((T((4 + T(7))) \times T(7)) - T(C(4, 1)))$
14777 := $((-7) - (-T(7)) \times T((T(7) + C(4, 1))))$
14784 := $(T((4 \times 8)) \times C((7 \times 4), 1))$
14787 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) + T((T(7) - T(C(4, 1))))$
14795 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(C(4, 1)))$
14868 := $(-(T(8) + (-6) \times (T(C(8, 4)) - 1)))$
14916 := $(6 \times (T(C(-(1 - 9)), 4) + 1))$
14949 := $(C(((T(9) - T(4)) - 9), 4) - 1)$
14952 := $(T(2) \times (C(T(5), 9) - T(T((4 - 1))))$
14973 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T((T(7) + 9)) + T(C(4, 1))))$
14986 := $((T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(9)))) + T(T(C(4, 1))))$
15015 := $(C(T(5), 10) \times C(5, 1))$
15168 := $(8 \times (T(61) + C(5, 1)))$
15241 := $((T((1 + T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - C(5, 1))$
15245 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(T(4))^2) \times C(5, 1)))$
15265 := $((5^6) - (T(2) \times T(T(C(5, 1))))$
15312 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times T((T(3) + C(5, 1))))$
15336 := $(6 \times T((C(T(3), 3) + (51))))$
15345 := $(T(5) \times ((C(4, 3)^5) - 1))$
15415 := $((T((5 - 1)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(C(5, 1)))$
15445 := $((5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(4)) - C(5, 1)$
15459 := $((T(9) - C((5 \times 4), 5)) \times (-1))$
15505 := $(C((5 + T(05)), 5) + 1)$
15522 := $(2 \times ((T(T(2))^5) - T(C(5, 1))))$
15525 := $(T(5) \times T((T(2) \times T(C(5, (5 - 1))))))$
15549 := $(T(9) + (C((4 \times 5), 5) \times 1))$
15552 := $((T(T(2))^5) \times (C(5, 5) + 1))$
15555 := $(C((5 + T(5)), 5) + (51))$
15615 := $((C(5, 1)^6) - T((5 - 1)))$
15624 := $((T(4)/2)^{C(6, 5)} - 1)$
15636 := $(T(T(6)) + (T(T((T(3) + (6)))) \times C(5, 1)))$
15675 := $(C(T(5), 7) - (-6) \times T(T(T((5 - 1))))$
15732 := $(T((T(2) \times T(3))) \times (-T(7)) + T(T(C(5, 1))))$
15745 := $((5^{T(-4+7)}) + T(T(C(5, 1))))$
15765 := $((5^6) + (T(7) \times C(5, 1)))$
15864 := $((4 \times 6) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(C(5, 1)))$
15924 := $(((-T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-9)) - T(C(5, 1)))$
15934 := $((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 9) - C(5, 1)$
15984 := $((-4) \times T(T(8))) \times (9 - T(C(5, 1)))$
16128 := $(8 \times T((C(2, 1) + 61)))$
16174 := $((4^7) - T((-1) + T(C(6, 1))))$
16224 := $((T(T(4)) - T(2))^2) \times C(6, 1)$
16275 := $(-5) \times ((C(T(7), T(2)) - T(6)) \times (-1))$
16324 := $(T(T(T(4))) - ((2^{T(3)}) \times T(T(C(6, 1))))$

16348 := $-(T(8) - (C(4,3)^{6+1}))$
16358 := $((T(8) \times C(T(5),3)) - (T(6) + 1))$
16375 := $(-5) - (C(T(7),3) \times (-6 - 1))$
16379 := $((T((C(9,7) + 3)) \times T(6)) - 1)$
16386 := $((T(6) \times T((T(8) + 3))) + C(6,1))$
16445 := $((T(T(C(5,4))) - T(T(4))) \times T((T(6) + 1)))$
16539 := $((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(3)) - 5)) - T(C(6,1)))$
16551 := $((T((1 + T(5))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(C(6,1))))$
16573 := $(-((3 - (7^5))) - T(T(C(6,1))))$
16592 := $((2 + T(T(9))) \times (-5) + T(C(6,1)))$
16599 := $((T((9 \times 9)) \times 5) - C(6,1))$
16638 := $((T(8) \times (T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(6)))) + C(6,1)$
16695 := $((T(5) + T((T(9) - 6))) \times T(C(6,1)))$
16744 := $(4 \times T(((T(4) \times 7) + T(C(6,1)))))$
16842 := $((T((2^4)) + T(T(8))) \times T(C(6,1)))$
16848 := $((T(8) \times T((4 + 8))) \times C(6,1))$
16989 := $((T(9) \times T((T(8) - 9))) - T(C(6,1)))$
17155 := $(5 \times (C((T(5) - 1), 7) - 1))$
17248 := $((T((T(8) + 4)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + T(C(7,1)))$
17283 := $(T(T(T(3))) - ((-T(8)) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(C(7,1))))$
17297 := $(-T(7)) - (T(9) \times (T(T(T(2))) - T(T(C(7,1)))))$
17329 := $((T(9) - 2) \times (-3) + T(T(C(7,1))))$
17369 := $((-T(9)) \times (C(6,3) - T(T(7)))) - 1$
17374 := $((T((T(4) \times 7)) - 3) \times C(7,1))$
17437 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times C(7,1)$
17455 := $(5 \times (5 + T((T(T(4)) + T(C(7,1)))))$
17466 := $((T(T(6)) + C(6,4)) \times 71)$
17472 := $((T(T(2)) - (T(C(7,4)))) \times (T(7) \times (-1)))$
17473 := $-(((T(3) - T(C(7,4))) \times T(7)) - 1)$
17529 := $-((T(T(9)) - C((T(2) + T(5)), (7 - 1)))$
17535 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))) - (T(5))) \times C(7,1)$
17542 := $((T(T(T(2))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5)))) \times C(7,1))$
17556 := $(C(6,5) \times T((5 + 71)))$
17592 := $(-T(2)) + (-T(9)) \times (T(5) - T(T(C(7,1))))$
17595 := $((5 \times 9) \times (-T(5)) + T(T(C(7,1))))$
17729 := $((-T(9)) \times (T(2) - T(T(7)))) - T(T(C(7,1)))$
17745 := $(C(T(5), 4) \times ((7 + 7) - 1))$
17775 := $(C(T(5), 7) + (T(7) \times (T(T(7)) - 1)))$
17793 := $(C(T(T(3)), (9 + 7)) - T(71))$
17794 := $((-4) + T(9)) \times (T(7) + T(T(C(7,1))))$
17847 := $(C(T(7), 4) - T((T(8) + T((7 + 1))))$
17864 := $(-((4 - (6 \times 8))) \times T(T(C(7,1))))$

17892 := $(-((2 - C(9,8))) \times T(71))$
17895 := $(-T(5)) + (-T(9)) \times (8 - T(T(C(7,1))))$
17972 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) \times (-T(9))) - T(C(7,1))$
17982 := $((-T(2)) \times T(T(8))) \times (-C(9, (7 + 1)))$
18216 := $(T((T(6) + 1)) \times (2 \times T(C(8,1))))$
18224 := $(T(((4^{T(2)}) + T(2))) \times C(8,1))$
18235 := $(C(T(5), T(3)) + (T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(8) - 1))))$
18244 := $((T(4) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) - T(T(C(8,1))))$
18248 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T((2 + T(C(8,1)))))$
18252 := $((T((2^5)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(C(8,1)))$
18285 := $(T(5) + (T(C(8,2)) \times T((8 + 1))))$
18353 := $((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(C(5,3))) - T(T(8)))) - 1)$
18456 := $(-6) \times (5 - T(T(C((4 + 8), 1))))$
18486 := $(6 \times T(((C(8,4) + 8) \times 1)))$
18563 := $(C((3 \times 6), T(-(5 - 8))) - 1)$
18642 := $(T((2 + T(4))) \times (T(T(6)) + C(8,1)))$
18677 := $(T(7) + ((T(C(7,6)) \times T(T(8))) + 1))$
18678 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + (-6) + T(C(8,1)))$
18682 := $(T(T(2)) + (C(8,6) \times (T(T(8)) + 1)))$
18684 := $((T((4 + 8)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(C(8,1))))$
18714 := $(T((T(4) + 1)) + (T(7) \times T(T(C(8,1)))))$
18724 := $((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(7) \times T(T(C(8,1)))))$
18729 := $((T(C(9,2)) \times T(7)) + (81))$
18753 := $(C(T(T(3)), 5) - T(((7 \times 8) \times 1)))$
18759 := $((-9) + T(T(5))) + (T(7) \times T(T(C(8,1))))$
18837 := $(C(T(7), T(3)) / (-8) + T((8 - 1)))$
18872 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 7) \times (8 + T(T(C(8,1)))))$
18928 := $(C(8,2) \times ((9 + T(T(8))) + 1))$
18963 := $(T(T(3)) \times T((6 + C(9, (8 - 1)))))$
19224 := $(4 \times ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T(C(9,1))))$
19313 := $((C(T(T(3)), (-1) + T(3)) - T(T(9))) - 1)$
19323 := $(3 \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(3) \times T(T(C(9,1)))))$
19347 := $(C(T(7), 4) - T(((3 + T(9)) - 1)))$
19353 := $((C(T(T(3)), 5) - (T(3))) - T((T(9) - 1)))$
19354 := $((4 \times C(T(5), T(3))) - T(T((9 - 1))))$
19356 := $((C(T(6), 5) - 3) - T((T(9) - 1)))$
19365 := $(-T(5)) \times (-T(C(6,3))) - T((T(9) + 1)))$
19368 := $(8 \times ((T(T(6)) \times T(3)) + T(T(C(9,1))))$
19372 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), 7) / T(3)) - (9 - 1))$
19396 := $((T(T(6)) \times C(9,3)) - (9 - 1))$
19439 := $(-9) + C((T(T(3)) - 4), (9 + 1))$
19447 := $(C((7 + T(4)), C(T(4), 9)) - 1)$

19448 := $C((T(T(T((8/4)))) - 4), (9 + 1))$
19485 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((8 + T(4)))) - T(T(C(9, 1))))$
19493 := $(3^9) - T((T(4) + C(9, 1)))$
19536 := $(T(T(6)) + (3 \times C(T(5), (9 - 1))))$
19575 := $((T(5) \times T(7)) + T(5)) \times T(C(9, 1))$
19647 := $((-T(7)) + T(T(-((T(4) - T(6)))))) \times C(9, 1)$
19665 := $((T(T(5)) - (6))/6) \times T(T(C(9, 1)))$
19733 := $((C((3^3), 7)/T(9)) - 1)$
19847 := $(-7) - ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)))) \times (-C(9, 1)))$
19888 := $(8 \times (T(C(8, (T(8)/9))) + 1)$
19953 := $(C(T(T(3)), 5) + (-9) \times (T(9) - 1))$
19965 := $(T(5) \times (C(T(6), (9 + 9)) + 1))$
20247 := $((C(T(7), 4) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(02))$
20265 := $(T(5) \times (C(T(6), T(2)) + T(T(02))))$
20343 := $(C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + T(3))) - T(T(02)))$
20346 := $(C(T(6), (T(4) + T(3))) - T(02))$
20349 := $(C((9 + T(4)), 3) \times T(T(T(02))))$
20352 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + C(3, 02))$
20353 := $(C(T(T(3)), 5) + (T(3) - 02))$
20356 := $(C(T(6), 5) + (T(T(3))/T(02)))$
20447 := $(C(T(7), 4) - T((T(4) - T(02))))$
20471 := $(-1) + (C(T(7), 4) - T(02))$
20472 := $-((T(2) - C(T(7), (4 + (0 \times 2))))$
20473 := $(C((T(T(3)) + 7), 4) - 02)$
20474 := $(-4) + (C(T(7), 4) + T(02))$
20477 := $(C(T(7), (T(7) - 4)) + 02)$
20481 := $(C(T(-((1 - 8))), 4) + T(T(02)))$
20565 := $(-((T(5) - C(T(6), 5)) + T(T(T(T(02))))$
20595 := $(T(T(5)) + ((T(9) \times C(T(5), T(02))))$
20752 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + ((T(T(7)) - T(02))))$
20753 := $((C(T(T(3)), 5) + T(T(7))) - 02)$
20916 := $(6 \times T((-1) + C(9, T(02))))$
20979 := $((-C(9, 7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(02)))$
21252 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + (T(21 \times 2)))$
21279 := $((T(T(9)) + (C(T(7), (T(2) + 1)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
21384 := $(T(C(T(4), 8)) + C(T(T(3)), (-1) + T(T(2))))$
21393 := $-((T(T(3)) + (-((T(C(9, 3)) - 1)) \times T(T(2))))$
21394 := $((T(4) + T(T(9))) + C(T(T(3)), (-1) + T(T(2))))$
21396 := $(6 \times ((T(C(9, 3)) - 1) - T(2)))$
21435 := $(T(5) - (-T(3)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))))$
21528 := $(T((C(8, 2) - 5) \times T(12)))$
21729 := $((T(C(9, 2)) \times T(7)) + T(T(12)))$
21732 := $(-T(2) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T((C(7, 1) + 2))))$
21966 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T(6) \times T(C((9 + 1), 2))))$
22183 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((C(C(8, 1), 2)^{T(2)}))$
22228 := $((C(8, 2)^{T(2)} + T((2 + T(T(T(2))))$
22274 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(7))) - C(2^{T(2)}), T(2))$
22324 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(C((2^3), 2))) - T(T(2)))$
22328 := $((T(C(8, 2)) \times T(T((T(3) - 2)))) - 2)$
22344 := $((T(4) + 4) \times T(C((T(3) + 2), T(2))))$
22357 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(C(5, 3))) + (T(2)^{T(2)}))$
22379 := $(-T(97) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(T(2))))$
22386 := $(T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + ((C(T(3), T(2))^2)))$
22398 := $((-8) + T((C(9, 3) + 2))) \times T(T(2))$
22447 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(T(4))) + (C(T(4), T(2)) - T(2)))$
22485 := $(T(T(5)) + (((T(C(8, 4)) \times T(2)) \times T(2))))$
22489 := $((T(T(9)) + T(8)) \times T(C(4, 2)) - 2)$
22525 := $((T(5) + 2) \times (-5) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)))$
22547 := $((T(T(7)) + 4) \times T(C(5, 2)) - T(2))$
22561 := $((T(T((1 + 6))) \times T(C(5, 2)) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
22617 := $((C((T(7) + 1), 6)/T(T(T(2)))) - T(2))$
22618 := $(T(T(8)) + (T((1 + 6))^{C(T(2), 2)}))$
22645 := $((T(5) \times T(T(T(4)))) - C(C(6, 2), T(2)))$
22663 := $((T(3)^6 - C(T(6), T(2)))/2)$
22674 := $((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7))) \times C(6, T(2))) - T(T(2)))$
22678 := $((T(8) \times T(C(7, (6/2)))) - 2)$
22716 := $(-6) \times ((-1) - T(C(7, T(2)))) \times T(T(2))$
22718 := $((T(8) \times (1 + T(C(7, T(2)))) + 2)$
22728 := $((C(8, T(2)) \times T(T(7))) - 2^{T(2)})$
22743 := $((C(T(T(3)), 4) + T((T(7) \times 2))) \times T(2))$
22748 := $((C(8, 4) \times T((T(7) - T(2)))) - 2)$
22758 := $((C(8, 5) \times T(T(7))) + 22)$
22769 := $((T(T(9)) \times (-6) + T(7)) - C(2, 2))$
22782 := $(-((T(T(2)) + (-T(8)) \times (T(C(7, T(2))) + T(2))))$
22784 := $(-4) - (-T(8)) \times (T(C(7, T(2))) + T(2))$
22785 := $((-T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times C(7, (2 + 2))$
22911 := $(T(T(11)) + (T(T(9)) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2))))$
22932 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-T(3)) + T((C(9, T(2)) + T(2))))$
22957 := $((T(7) \times T((-5) + T(9))) - C(T(2), 2))$
22964 := $(-4) - (-6) \times T((C(9, T(2)) + T(2)))$
22968 := $((T(8)/6) \times T((C(9, T(2)) + T(2))))$
22979 := $((9 \times T((T(7) + T(9)))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)))$
22984 := $((T(4) + T(T(8))) \times (C(9, 2) - 2))$
23055 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(C(5, 03))) - T(2)))$

- 23135** := $(-(5^{T(3)}) + C((-1) + T(T(3))), T(T(2)))$
23145 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(C((4+1), 3))) + T(2)))$
23223 := $((T(C(T(3), T(2))) - (T(T(2))^{T(3)})) / (-2))$
23229 := $(9 \times ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) / T(T(3))) - T(2)))$
23246 := $((6 \times (4^{T(T(2))}) - C(T(T(3)), T(2)))$
23247 := $(7 \times T(((C(4, 2) + 3)^2))$
23256 := $(C(T(6), (5+2)) / (3+2))$
23278 := $((T(T(8)) \times C(7, T(2))) - 32)$
23282 := $((28^{T(2)}) + C(T(T(3)), T(2)))$
23296 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(2))))$
23338 := $((T(8)^3) + C(T(3), 3)) / 2$
23343 := $(C(T(3), 4) - ((T(3))^{T(3)}) / (-2))$
23358 := $-((T(T(8)) + (C((-5) + T(T(3))), T(3)) \times (-T(2))))$
23385 := $-((T(5) - (8 \times C(3^3), T(2))))$
23428 := $((8 \times T((T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)))))) + C(T(3), T(2)))$
23433 := $((T(3)^{T(3)}) + C(T(4), T(3))) / 2$
23463 := $((-T(3) - T(T(6))) \times (-C(T(4), 3) + T(T(T(2))))$
23474 := $((-4) + C(T(7), 4) + T((T(T(T(3)))) / T(2)))$
23485 := $((5 + T(T(8))) \times C((4+3), T(2)))$
23544 := $((-(4^4) \times T(T(5))) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))))$
23583 := $(T(T(3)) \times (T(T(8)) + (C(T(5), 3) + 2)))$
23654 := $-((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(5)) \times (-T(C(6, 3)))) + T(T(2))))$
23688 := $(T(8) \times (-8) + T(C((6+3), 2)))$
23738 := $(83 \times C((7 + T(3)), T(2)))$
23739 := $((T(9) \times T(-((3 - C(7, 3)))) - T(T(T(2))))$
23744 := $((4 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) - T(C(T(3), T(2))))$
23751 := $C(((1^5) + T(7)), (T(3) - 2))$
23752 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + T(((T(7) \times 3) - 2)))$
23786 := $((T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) \times T(7) - C(T(T(3)), T(2)))$
23843 := $(T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + ((C(8, T(3))^{T(2)}))$
23889 := $-((T(9) - C((8+8), T(3))) \times T(2))$
23895 := $(-5) \times (9 - (T(C(8, 3)) \times T(2)))$
23925 := $(T(C(5, 2)) \times T(((9 \times 3) + 2)))$
23938 := $((T(C(8, 3)) \times T(9)) - T(3)) / T(2)$
23957 := $((T(T(7)) \times 59) + C(3, 2))$
23979 := $-((T(9) - (C((7+9), T(3)) \times T(2)))$
24024 := $(C(4^2), T(04)) \times T(2)$
24115 := $(C(T(5), T((1+1))) \times (T(T(4)) - 2))$
24135 := $((T(5) \times T(T(T((3+1)))) + T(C(T(4), 2)))$
24148 := $((T((C(8, 4) - 1)) \times T(4)) - 2)$
24159 := $((T(9) + C((T(5) + 1), T(4))) \times T(2))$
24165 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((T(6) - 1))) - T(C(T(4), 2)))$
24215 := $(5 \times (C((-1) + T(T(T(2))), 4) - 2))$
24225 := $(-T(5)) \times (C(C(T(T(2)), T(2)), 4) / (-T(2)))$
24235 := $(5 \times (C(C(T(3), T(2)), 4) + 2))$
24248 := $(8 \times ((T(T(4))^2) + C(4, 2)))$
24256 := $((T(T(6)) \times C(T(5), 2)) + (4 - T(2)))$
24259 := $((T(T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + C(4, T(2))$
24276 := $((6 + T(7))^2 \times T(C(4, 2)))$
24289 := $(C((9+8), (2 \times 4)) - T(T(T(2))))$
24368 := $((8 + T(6))^3 - T(C(4, 2)))$
24378 := $((-T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times T(C(T(3), 4)))) / (-2)$
24395 := $(5 \times ((T(C(9, 3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2))))))$
24417 := $(C((T(7) + 1), 4) + T(T((4 \times 2))))$
24427 := $((T(7)^{T(2)}) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(4), 2)))$
24437 := $((T(7)^3) + T((C(T(4), 4) / T(2))))$
24458 := $((8 \times (C(T(5), T(4)) + T(T(4)))) - T(T(2)))$
24465 := $((-5) \times T(T(6)) - T(4)) \times (-T(C(4, 2)))$
24475 := $((-C(T(5), 7) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(4) / (-2)))$
24478 := $((8 \times C((T(7) - T(4)), 4)) - 2)$
24486 := $((T((6 \times 8)) - T(4)) \times T(C(4, 2)))$
24488 := $-(((T(8) - T(C(8, 4))) \times T(4)) + 2)$
24497 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times (-4) + T(C(4, 2)))$
24525 := $((-T(5)) + (T(T(2)) \times C(T(5), 4)) \times T(2))$
24532 := $((-T(2)) + C(T(T(3)), 5) + T(T((T(4) + T(2))))$
24534 := $((C(T(4), T(3)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T((4 \times 2))))$
24546 := $(-6) \times (4 - (C(T(5), 4) \times T(2)))$
24565 := $(5 \times ((T(C(6, 5)) - 4)^{T(2)}))$
24566 := $((6 \times T((6 \times T(5)))) - C(4, T(2)))$
24567 := $(C(T(C(7, 6)), 5) / 4 - T(2))$
24588 := $((T(8) + (T(8) \times C(T(5), 4))) / 2)$
24625 := $((T((T(5) \times T(T(2)))) \times 6) + T(T(C(4, T(2))))$
24649 := $((C(9, 4) + T(6)) + T(4))^2$
24686 := $((T(6) \times T((8 \times 6))) - T(C(4, T(2))))$
24688 := $(-8) + (T((8 \times 6)) \times T(C(4, 2)))$
24692 := $((T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(6)) - C(4, T(2)))$
24752 := $(C((2 + T(5)), T((7 - 4))) \times 2)$
24783 := $((T(T(T(3))) \times T(C(8, 7))) - (T(T(4)))) \times T(2)$
24789 := $(T(T(9)) + ((C((T(8) - 7), 4) + T(2))))$
24792 := $((-2) + T(T(9))) \times (T(7) - C(4, T(2)))$
24822 := $(-T(2)) \times (T(T(2)) - (8 \times T(C(T(4), 2))))$
24824 := $((T(4) \times (-2) + T(C(8, 4))) - T(T(2)))$
24825 := $(-T(5)) - ((T(2) \times (-8)) \times T(C(T(4), 2)))$
24835 := $(-5) \times (3 + (T(C(8, 4)) \times (-2)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
24841 &:= (1 - ((T(C(T(4), 8)) \times (-4)) \times T(T(2)))) \\
24842 &:= (((T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 8))) \times 4) + 2) \\
24844 &:= (-4) + ((T(4) \times T(C(8, 4))) - 2) \\
24845 &:= (T(5) + (T(4) \times (T(C(8, 4)) - 2))) \\
24846 &:= (-6) + ((T(4) \times T(C(8, 4))) + 2) \\
24848 &:= ((T((8 - 4)) \times T(C(8, 4))) - 2) \\
24849 &:= (9 - ((T(C(T(4), 8)) \times (-4)) \times T(T(2)))) \\
24873 &:= ((37 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(C(4, 2)))) \\
24879 &:= ((T(C(9, 7)) \times T(8)) + T(42)) \\
24882 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (T(88) + T(T(C(4, 2)))))) \\
24895 &:= (-5) \times (-9) + (T(C(8, 4)) \times (-2)) \\
24948 &:= (((8 + 4) \times 9) \times T(T(C(4, 2)))) \\
24975 &:= ((T(5) \times (T(7) + 9)) \times C(T(4), 2)) \\
24985 &:= (-5) \times (8 - C(T((9 - 4)), T(T(2)))) \\
25025 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(C(05, 2))) \\
25045 &:= (-5) \times (-4 - C(T(05), T(T(2)))) \\
25046 &:= (T(6) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(05), T(2)))) \\
25125 &:= (5 \times (T(T(T(2))) + (-1) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))))) \\
25135 &:= (5 \times ((T(T(3)) + 1) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))))) \\
25145 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times C(15, T(2)))) \\
25165 &:= (-5) \times (-T((6 + 1))) - C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \\
25195 &:= (-5) + (T(9) \times C((1 + T(5)), T(2))) \\
25203 &:= ((T(C(T(3), T(02))) \times T(T(5))) + T(2)) \\
25206 &:= ((C(T(6), 02) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(2))) \\
25221 &:= ((T(C(T((1 + 2)), T(2))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\
25223 &:= (T(T(3)) - ((T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) \times (-T(T(5)))) - 2)) \\
25225 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(C(T(T(2)), T(2)))) + (5^2)) \\
25235 &:= (-5) \times ((T(T(3)) \times (-2)) - C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \\
25236 &:= ((C(6, 3) + T(T((-2) + T(5)))) \times T(T(2))) \\
25238 &:= (T(8) + ((T(C(T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(5))) + 2)) \\
25251 &:= (((-1) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \times 5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
25253 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) \times (-5)) + T(2))) \\
25255 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T((T(T(5))/T(T(2)))))) + T(C(5, 2)) \\
25256 &:= (T(T(6)) + (C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(C(5, 2)))) \\
25323 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) - C(T(T(2)), 3)) \times T(T(5))) + T(2)) \\
25325 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times T(C(T(T(2)), 3)) + (5^{T(2)})) \\
25341 &:= (((1 + C(T(4), T(3))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(T(2)))) \\
25344 &:= (-((4^4)) \times (T(3) - C(T(5), 2))) \\
25355 &:= (55 \times (T(3) + C(T(5), T(2)))) \\
25392 &:= (2 \times (-9) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(C(5, 2)))))) \\
25431 &:= (T(T((1 + T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(5), T(2)))) \\
25437 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(5), T(2)))) \\
25442 &:= (((2 + C(T(4), 4)) \times T(T(5))) + 2) \\
25449 &:= (-C(9, 4) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(5) \times 2)))) \\
25466 &:= ((T(6) \times T(6)) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(5), T(2)))) \\
25475 &:= (T(T(5)) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) \times (-T(C(5, 2)))))) \\
25487 &:= (-7) \times (-((8^4)) + C(T(5), T(2))) \\
25488 &:= (8 \times (T(T((8 + 4))) + (C(T(5), 2)))) \\
25495 &:= (-5) \times (-94 - C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \\
25525 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times T((T(5) + T(2)))))) \\
25536 &:= (T(6) + ((3^5) \times C(T(5), 2))) \\
25575 &:= (T(((5 \times 7) - 5)) \times T(C(5, 2))) \\
25596 &:= (T(6) - (T((T(9) - T(5))) \times (-T(C(5, 2)))))) \\
25655 &:= (-5) \times ((-C(T(5), 6) - T(T(5))) - T(T(2))) \\
25658 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - (C(T(6), T(5)) - 2)) \\
25695 &:= (T(T(5)) - (T((9 + T(6))) \times (-T(C(5, 2)))))) \\
25696 &:= -C(-T(6) + T(9), T(6)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
25698 &:= ((T((8 + C(9, 6))) + (5)) \times T(T(2))) \\
25704 &:= (C(-((T(4) - T(07))), 5) \times T(2)) \\
25727 &:= ((T((7^2)) \times C(7, 5)) + 2) \\
25734 &:= ((C((T(4) + 3), 7) \times T(5)) - T(T(2))) \\
25737 &:= ((C((7 + T(3)), 7) \times T(5)) - T(2)) \\
25739 &:= ((T((T(9) - 3)) \times T(7)) + (C(T(5), T(2)))) \\
25742 &:= ((C((T(2) + T(4)), 7) \times T(5)) + 2) \\
25743 &:= ((C((3 + T(4)), 7) \times T(5)) + T(2)) \\
25754 &:= ((4 \times (C(T(5), 7) + (5))) - T(T(2))) \\
25768 &:= ((T(C(8, 6)) \times T(7)) + (T(T(5))^2)) \\
25812 &:= -((T(T(2)) \times T((1 + T(8))) - C(T(5), T(T(2)))))) \\
25824 &:= (4 \times ((T(2)^8) - C(T(5), 2))) \\
25845 &:= (-5) \times ((T(C(T(4), 8)) \times (-5)) + T(T(2))) \\
25847 &:= (-T(7)) - (T(C(T(4), 8)) \times (-5^2)) \\
25854 &:= (((4 \times C(T(5), 8)) + T(T(5))) - T(T(2))) \\
25865 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times (6 \times T(8))) - T(C(5, 2))) \\
25869 &:= (((T(9) - 6) \times T(T(8))) - (C(T(5), 2))) \\
25872 &:= (T((T(2) \times 7)) \times (C(8, 5) \times 2)) \\
25928 &:= (C(8, T(2)) \times (T((T(9) - T(5))) - 2)) \\
25935 &:= (C(T(5), 3) \times ((T(9) + T(5)) - T(2))) \\
25974 &:= (-T(4)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-9) - T(C(5, 2)))) \\
25975 &:= (5 \times (T((T(7) - 9)) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))))) \\
25977 &:= (-7) - (T(T(7)) \times (-9) - T(C(5, 2)))) \\
26125 &:= ((5^{T(2)}) \times (-1) + C(T(6), 2)) \\
26136 &:= (-((6^3)) \times (-1) - T(C(6, 2))) \\
26187 &:= (7 \times T((C((8 + 1), 6) + 2))) \\
26238 &:= ((T(8) \times (C(3, 2)^6)) - T(T(2)))
\end{aligned}$$

- 26251** := $(1 + ((5^{T(2)}) \times C(T(6), 2)))$
26265 := $(- (T(5)) \times (C(T(6), T(2)) - T(T((6 \times 2))))$
26279 := $(- ((T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(C(6, 2))))$
26292 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (- (T((9 + T(2))) - C(T(6), T(2))))$
26297 := $(- (T(7)) - (- (9) \times C((T(T(2)) + (T(6))), T(2))))$
26312 := $(C(T((T(T(2)) + 1)), T(T(3)))/T((6 + T(2))))$
26342 := $(- ((T((- (T(2)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(3))) \times T(C(6, 2))))$
26355 := $((5 \times C(T(5), T(3))) + C(T(6), T(2)))$
26376 := $((T(6) + C(T(7), 3)) \times (6 + 2))$
26378 := $((8 \times (C(T(7), 3) + T(6))) + 2)$
26399 := $((9 \times T(T((9 + 3)))) - C(T(6), T(2)))$
26424 := $(4 \times (T(T(2)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(C(6, 2))))$
26425 := $(C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T((4 \times T(6))) \times T(T(2))))$
26439 := $((T(C(9, 3)) \times T(4)) - (T(6)^{T(2)}))$
26442 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((C(T(4), 4) \times T(6)) - T(2)))$
26472 := $((T(T(2)) + (T(C(7, 4)) \times T(6))) \times 2)$
26475 := $(T(5) + ((T(C(7, 4)) \times T(6)) \times 2))$
26537 := $(- (T(7)) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (5 - T(C(6, 2))))$
26568 := $(8 \times T((6 + (5 \times C(6, 2))))$
26615 := $(T(5) + ((- (1) + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2))))$
26684 := $(- ((T(T(T(4))) - (((C(8, 6) \times 6)^2))))$
26691 := $(C(19, 6) - (T(6)^2))$
26875 := $(- (5) + ((T(7) \times 8) \times T(C(6, 2))))$
26901 := $(C((10 + 9), 6) - T(T(T(T(2))))$
26922 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times (- ((T(2) + T(9)) - C(T(6), T(2))))$
26943 := $((C(T(T(3)), 4) \times (- 9)) - (T(6)))/(- 2)$
26985 := $((T(5) - T(8)) \times (T(9) - C(T(6), T(2))))$
26999 := $(- (C(9, 9)) + ((9 + T(6))^{T(2)}))$
27027 := $((C(T(7), T(2))/T(07)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
27126 := $(C((T(6) - 2), - ((1 - 7))) - T(T(2)))$
27128 := $((8 - C(T(T(T(2))), - ((1 - 7)))/(- 2))$
27131 := $(- (1) + (C(T(T(3))), - ((1 - 7)))/2)$
27132 := $(C(T((2 \times 3)), - ((1 - 7)))/2)$
27134 := $((- (4) - C(T(T(3))), - ((1 - 7)))/(- 2))$
27136 := $((C(T(6), T(3)) + (1 + 7))/2)$
27138 := $((T(C(8, 3)) \times 17) + T(T(2)))$
27146 := $((C(T(6), T((4 - 1))) + T(7))/2)$
27168 := $(T(8) - (C(T(6), - ((1 - 7)))/(- 2)))$
27216 := $(C(T((6 + 1)), 2) \times 72)$
27223 := $(C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(T(2))) + T((7 + T(T(2))))$
27225 := $((T(C(5, 2))^2) \times (7 + 2))$
27251 := $((1 - T(T(5))) \times (2 - T(C(7, 2))))$
27254 := $(- (4) - ((T(T(5)) - 2) \times (- T(C(7, 2))))$
27258 := $((8 \times T(5)) - 2) \times T(C(7, 2))$
27276 := $((- (C(T(6), 7)) + (T(T(2))^{T(7)}))/T(T(2)))$
27285 := $(- (T(5)) - (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times (- C(7, T(2))))$
27295 := $(- (5) - (- (C(9, T(2))) \times T((T(7) - T(2))))$
27297 := $((C(T(7), 9)/T(- ((T(T(2)) - T(7)))) - T(2))$
27321 := $((- (1) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 3) - (T(7)))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
27332 := $(- (T(2)) - ((C(T(T(3))), T(3)) + T(T(7)))/(- 2))$
27335 := $((- (C((T(5) + T(3)), T(3))) - T(T(7)))/(- 2))$
27342 := $((T(T(2))^{T(4)} + (T(3))) \times C(7, 2))$
27355 := $(- (5) - (T(T(5)) \times (3 - T(C(7, 2))))$
27423 := $((T(T(3))^{T(2)} - C(T(4), 7)) \times T(2))$
27432 := $(T(T(2)) \times ((T(3)^4 + C(T(7), T(2))))$
27445 := $((- (5) \times T(T(4))) + (C(T(4), 7) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
27467 := $(- (T((T(7) - 6))) + (C(T(4), 7) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$
27475 := $((T(T(5)) \times 7) - T(T(4))) \times C(7, T(2))$
27492 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (C(9, 4) - 7)) + T(2))$
27517 := $(T(7) + ((1 - T(T(5))) \times (- T(C(7, 2))))$
27532 := $- C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(7)))^2$
27545 := $(- ((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(C(7, 2))))$
27566 := $(T(T(6)) - ((C(T(6), T(5)) + T(T(7)))/(- 2))$
27573 := $((T(T(3)) \times (- 7)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(C(7, 2))))$
27615 := $((T(51) \times T(6)) - T(C(7, 2)))$
27654 := $((T(4) + C(T(5), 6)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(2))$
27664 := $((T(T(4)) + (T(6))) \times C((T(6) - 7), T(2))$
27668 := $((T(T(8)) + (C(T(6), 6))) + T(T(7)))/2$
27678 := $((T(T(8)) - 7) \times (T(6) + (C(7, 2))))$
27685 := $((T(5) \times 8) \times T(T(6))) - C(7, T(2))$
27726 := $((T(T(6)) \times C((T(2) + 7), 7)) + T(T(2)))$
27742 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(4), 7)) + (T(7) - T(T(2))))$
27746 := $((T(T(6)) \times C(T(4), 7)) + (T(7) - 2))$
27765 := $((T(T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + C(T((T(7)/7), 2))$
27825 := $((T(5) + T((T(2) + T(8)))) \times C(7, T(2))$
27846 := $(T(6) \times T((- (4) + T((C(8, 7) + 2))))$
27853 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(5) + T(8)))) + C(7, T(T(2))))$
27856 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T((C(8, 7) \times 2))$
27924 := $((T(C(T(4), 2)) \times 9) - 7) \times T(2)$
27925 := $(- (5) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T((9 - 7))) \times T(T(T(2))))$
27942 := $((- (2) - T(T(T(4)))) - (- (9) \times C(T(7), T(2))))$
27946 := $((C(T(6), 4) + 9) + (T(7)^{T(2)}))$
27947 := $((T(C(7, 4)) \times T(9)) - T(T(7))) + T(2)$
27964 := $((4 - (T(6) \times T(C(9, 7)))) \times (- 2))$

- 27965 := (((-5) - T(T(6))) + T(T(9))) × C(7, T(2))
27966 := (-6) + ((T(6) × T(C(9, 7))) × 2)
28125 := ((T(T(5)) × T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (-1) + T(C(8, 2))
28126 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T((T(T(2)) - 1)))) + (T(C(8, 2))))
28263 := ((T(T(3)) × C(T(6), T(2))) - (T(T(8)) / (-2)))
28266 := (T(6) × (C(T(6), T(2)) + ((8 × 2))))
28288 := ((T(8) + T(C(8, 2))) × (8²))
28325 := (T(C(5, 2)) × (3 + (8^{T(2)})))
28328 := (8 × (C(T(T(T(2))), 3) + T(T((8 + T(2)))))
28336 := ((C(T(6), 3) × T(T(3))) + T(C(8, 2)))
28355 := ((-T(5)) × (C(T(5), T(3)) + T(T(8)))) / (-T(2))
28357 := (-7) × (-T(C(5, 3)) - (T(T(8)) × T(T(2))))
28365 := (T(5) × T((6 + C((3 + 8), 2))))
28378 := ((T(T(8)) × (7 × T(3))) + T(C(8, 2)))
28391 := (-1) + ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) × C(8, 2))
28392 := (T((T(2) + 9)) × C((T(3) + 8), T(2)))
28428 := ((T(8)²) + C((T(T(4)) - T(8)), T(T(2))))
28434 := (((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(4), 8)) × T(T(T(2))))
28458 := (T((T(8) + T(5))) + C((T(T(4)) - T(8)), T(T(2))))
28496 := (((C(T(6), 9) / T(4)) - T(T(8))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))
28497 := (-7) × ((-T(9)) × T(T(4)) - T(C(8, T(2))))
28579 := ((T(T(9)) × T(7)) - (-5 + T(C(8, 2))))
28588 := ((8 × T((-T(8) + T(T(5)))) + C(8, 2))
28623 := (T(T(3)) × ((-2) - T(T(6))) + T(C(8, T(2))))
28629 := (((T(C(9, T(2))) + 6) × 8) + T(T(T(2))))
28637 := (-T(7)) - (T(T(3)) × (T(T(6)) - T(C(8, T(2))))))
28662 := (-T(2)) - (T(6) × (T(T(6)) - T(C(8, T(2))))))
28665 := ((T(5) × T(6)) × C((6 + 8), 2))
28672 := ((2 × T(C(7, 6))) × (8^{T(2)}))
28674 := ((C(T(4), 7) × (T(T(6)) + 8)) - T(T(2)))
28686 := (T(6) × (T(8) + C(T(6), (T(8) / 2))))
28689 := ((-T(9)) × (C(8, 6) - T(T(8))) - T(T(T(2))))
28756 := ((-C(T(6), T(5))) - (T(T(7)) × 8)) / (-2)
28784 := ((T(C(T(4), 8)) - 7) × C(8, 2))
28798 := (((8 + T(T(9))) × T(7)) - T(C(8, 2)))
28812 := ((T(T(2)) - T(T((1 + 8)))) × (-C(8, 2)))
28826 := (((T(6) × T(2)) + 8) × T(C(8, 2)))
28855 := (-5) × ((-C(T(5), 8)) + T(T(8)) - 2)
28898 := (((T(T(8)) × T(9)) - T(T(8))) - T(C(8, 2)))
28922 := (-2) - ((-2) + T(T(9))) × (-C(8, 2))
28924 := (((4 - 2) - T(T(9))) × (-C(8, 2)))
28929 := ((-T(9)) - T(T(2))) - (T(T(9)) × (-C(8, 2)))
28938 := (-((C(8, T(3)) - T(98))) × T(T(2)))
28946 := ((T(6) - T(T(4))) - (T(T(9)) × (-C(8, 2))))
28948 := (-((8 × 4)) - (T(T(9)) × (-C(8, 2))))
28952 := ((T((2 + 5)) × T(T(9))) - C(8, 2))
28955 := (-((5 × 5)) - (T(T(9)) × (-C(8, 2))))
28957 := (-((T(7) - 5)) - (T(T(9)) × (-C(8, 2))))
28959 := -((T((-9) + T(5))) + (T(T(9)) × (-C(8, 2))))
28964 := (-((T(4) + 6)) - (T(T(9)) × (-C(8, 2))))
28967 := (-((7 + 6)) - (T(T(9)) × (-C(8, 2))))
28995 := (T(5) - (T(T(9)) × (-T((C(9, 8) - 2))))
28997 := ((T(7) × T(T(9))) + (T(9) - C(8, 2)))
29226 := (-C(6, 2) + (T((2 × 9)²))
29232 := ((2³) × C(29, T(2)))
29245 := (-5) + (T(4) × C((T(2) × 9), T(2)))
29295 := -((T(5) × (T(9) - (T(2) × T(C(9, 2)))))
29298 := (((T(T(8)) × T(9)) - T(T(2))) - T(C(9, 2)))
29304 := ((T(40) - T(3)) × C(9, 2))
29322 := (T(T(2)) × ((T(T(T(2))) × T(T(T(3)))) + C(9, 2)))
29344 := ((T(4) × T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + C(9, T(2)))
29364 := ((T(4) × T((T(T(6)) / 3))) - T(C(9, 2)))
29387 := ((C(T(7), (T(8) / 3)) / T(T(9))) - T(T(2)))
29393 := (C(T(T(3)), 9) / ((3 + 9) - 2))
29427 := (((C(T(7), T(2)) - 4) × 9) - T(T(T(2))))
29457 := (((C(T(7), 5) / T(4)) - 9) × T(2))
29465 := (5 × (C(T(6), 4) - 92))
29474 := (-T(4)) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) × (-C(9, T(2))))
29476 := ((C(T(6), 7) / 4) + T(T((9 - 2))))
29477 := (-7) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) × (-C(9, T(2))))
29487 := ((C(T(7), T(8) / 4)) × 9) + T(2)
29527 := (((C(T(7), T(2)) + 5) × 9) - 2)
29534 := -((T((T(4) + T(T(3)))) + (-C(T(5), 9)) × T(T(2))))
29556 := (((T(T(6)) + T(5)) × T(T(5))) + C(9, 2))
29562 := (-((T((2 × 6)) - C(T(5), 9))) × T(T(2)))
29579 := ((-T(9)) - T(T(7))) - (-C(T(5), 9) × T(T(2)))
29648 := (8 × (T((T(4) + 6))) + T(C(9, T(2))))
29652 := ((2 + T((5 + T(6)))) × C(9, T(2)))
29724 := ((T(T(4)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-C(T(7), 9)) / T(T(T(T(2)))))
29729 := (-T((9 × 2))) - (-C(T(7), 9) / T(T(T(T(2)))))
29742 := ((C(T(T(T(2))), 4) - (-7) + T(T(9))) × T(T(2)))
29747 := (-T((7 + T(4))) - (-C(T(7), 9)) / T(T(T(T(2)))))
29784 := (((-4) + T(T(C(8, 7)))) × T(9)) - T(T(2))
29794 := ((T(T(4)) + (T(C(9, 7)) × T(9))) - T(T(T(T(2))))

$$\begin{aligned} 29795 &:= (- (T((5+9))) - (- (C(T(7), 9)) / T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29799 &:= ((T(9) \times T(C(9, 7))) - T((9 \times 2))) \\ 29889 &:= (9 \times T(((C(8, 8) \times 9)^2)) \\ 29898 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) - (T(8) + C(9, 2))) \\ 29914 &:= - ((T(T(4)) + (1 - (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29915 &:= - ((T(T((5 - 1))) - ((T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29925 &:= - (((T(5) \times T(2)) - (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29945 &:= - (((T(5) + T(4)) - (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29952 &:= - (((T(2) + T(5)) - (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29955 &:= - ((T(5) + (- ((5 \times 9)) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29957 &:= - (((T(7) - T(5)) - (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29962 &:= - ((2 + 6) + (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))) \\ 29968 &:= - ((8 - 6) + (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))) \\ 29971 &:= ((1^7) + (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))) \\ 29976 &:= (T((T(6)/7)) + ((T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29978 &:= (C(8, 7) + (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))) \\ 29983 &:= (T(T(3)) - (8 - (T(9) \times T(C(9, 2)))))) \\ 29985 &:= (T(5) + ((T(8) + 9) \times T(C(9, 2)))) \\ 30288 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(8))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(03))) \\ 30492 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (C(9, 4))) \times T(T(T(03)))) \\ 31185 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(-((1 + 1) - C(8, 5)))) \\ 31374 &:= (- (T((C(3, 1)^3))) \times (- (T(7)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 31374 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(7)) \times T((C(3, 1)^3))) \\ 31465 &:= ((5 \times C(T(6), 4) + T(T(T((1 + 3)))))) \\ 31552 &:= (C((2 + T(5)), T(5)) \times (1 + T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 31668 &:= (T(C(8, 6)) \times (6 \times 13)) \\ 31733 &:= (C((3 \times T(3)), 7) - T(13)) \\ 31814 &:= - ((T(4) - C(18, (1 + T(3)))))) \\ 31817 &:= (- (7) + C(18, (1 + T(3)))) \\ 32139 &:= (((T(C(9, 3)) + 1) \times T(2)) \times 3) \\ 32214 &:= ((T(T(C((4 + 1), 2))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32234 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(T(2)), 3))) \\ 32235 &:= (- (5) + T(T(C((3 + 2), 2)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32259 &:= (T(9) + ((T(T(C(5, 2))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 32312 &:= - (((T((T(T(2)) + 1))^3) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)))) \\ 32325 &:= ((T(T(C(5, 2))) \times T(T(3))) - T((2 + 3))) \\ 32334 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(3))) - (C(3, 2) + 3)) \\ 32335 &:= ((T(T(C(5, 3))) \times T(T(3))) - (2 + 3)) \\ 32361 &:= ((1 + T(T((C(6, 3)/2)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32368 &:= (C(8, 6) - (- (T(T(3))) \times T(T(T((- (2) + T(3))))))) \\ 32382 &:= ((2 + T(C((8 + 3), 2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32438 &:= (C(8, 3) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times (-T(T(3)))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32545 &:= (- (5) - ((- (T(4)) - T(T(C(5, 2)))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 32556 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T(5))) + (T(T(C(5, 2))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 32558 &:= ((8^5) - C(C(5, 2), T(3))) \\ 32578 &:= ((C(8, 7)^5) - T((- (2) + T(T(3)))))) \\ 32592 &:= (((T(2) + 9) + T(T(C(5, 2)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32655 &:= ((T(5) + T(C((5 + 6), 2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32688 &:= (((8 \times T(T(8))) + (T(C(6, 2)))) \times T(3)) \\ 32724 &:= - (((T(4) \times (T(2) - C(T(7), T(2)))) + T(3))) \\ 32725 &:= (T(C(5, 2)) \times T((T(7) + (2 \times 3)))) \\ 32742 &:= ((T(2) + (T(4) \times C(T(7), T(2)))) - T(T(3))) \\ 32745 &:= (T(5) + (T(4) \times (C(T(7), T(2)) - 3))) \\ 32747 &:= (- (7) + ((T(4) \times C(T(7), T(2))) - T(3))) \\ 32757 &:= ((C(T(7), 5) - (7 + 2)) / 3) \\ 32775 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(7), (7 - 2)) / 3)) \\ 32824 &:= (((T(C(T(4), 2)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(2))) / T(T(3))) \\ 32827 &:= ((C(T(7), T(T(T(2)))) / T(8)) - (T(2) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 32837 &:= ((- (C(T(7), - ((3 - 8)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) / (- (3))) \\ 32845 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times T((C(8, 2) + T(3)))))) \\ 32852 &:= ((2^{T(5)}) + (C(8, 2) \times 3)) \\ 32867 &:= ((C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8)) - (23)) \\ 32889 &:= (((T(9) + T(8)) \times T(C(8, 2))) + 3) \\ 32928 &:= (C(8, 2) \times T(((T(9) - T(2)) + T(3)))) \\ 33145 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T((T(4) + 1)))) - C(T(3), 3)) \\ 33228 &:= (T(8) \times (C(T(T(2)), T(2)) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))))) \\ 33245 &:= (- (5) + ((4 + T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(T(3)), 3))) \\ 33278 &:= ((8 \times T(T((7 + T(T(2)))))) - T(C(T(3), 3))) \\ 33282 &:= ((- (T(2)) + (T(C(8, T(2))) \times T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33284 &:= (((4 \times T(8)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(3), 3)) \\ 33292 &:= ((- (2) + C(9, T(2))) \times T(T((T(T(3)) / 3)))) \\ 33298 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(9) + T(2))) + C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 33325 &:= ((5^2) \times (C(T(T(3)), 3) + 3)) \\ 33355 &:= (- (5) \times ((- (5) \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 33364 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C((6 \times 3), (T(T(3)) / 3)))) \\ 33383 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(8) + T(T(3)))) - C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 33385 &:= (- (5) + ((T(C(8, 3)) - T(3)) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 33397 &:= ((- ((T(7) \times T(C(9, 3)))) - T(T(T(3)))) / (- (3))) \\ 33425 &:= - ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) - (T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 33428 &:= (T((T(8) \times 2)) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-C(T(3), 3)))) \\ 33438 &:= (((T(C(8, 3)) - (4)) \times T(T(3))) + (T(3))) \\ 33464 &:= (- ((T(4) \times T(64))) + C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \\ 33516 &:= (T(6) \times T(C(((1 \times 5) + 3), 3))) \\ 33519 &:= ((T(C((9 - 1), 5)) \times T(T(3))) + 3)$$

- 33523** := $(C((T(T(3)) + 2), 5) + (-T(3) \times T(T(3))))$
33558 := $((T(C(8, 5)) + (5 - 3)) \times T(T(3)))$
33582 := $((T(2) + T(C(8, 5))) \times T(T(3))) + 3$
33584 := $((T(T(4)) - T(T(8))) \times (-T(C(5, 3)))) - T(T(3))$
33664 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(6)) + ((C(T(6), 3) - T(3)))$
33669 := $(9 \times T((66 + C(T(3), 3))))$
33683 := $((C(T(T(3)), 8) - (6))/T(3) - T(T(T(3))))$
33689 := $((9 \times T(86)) + C(T(3), 3))$
33825 := $(T(5) \times (C((T(2) \times 8), 3) + T(T(T(3))))$
33831 := $((T((-1) + T(3))) + T(C(8, 3))) \times T(T(3))$
33838 := $((T(8) \times T((T(3) + T(8)))) + C(T(T(3)), 3))$
33846 := $((6 \times T(T(4))) + (T(C(8, 3)) \times T(T(3))))$
33852 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((-5) + T(C(8, 3))) + T(T(3)))$
33869 := $-((T(9) - ((C(T(6), 8) - T(3))/T(3))))$
33885 := $(T(5) \times (T(T(8)) + ((T(C(8, 3)) - 3))))$
33912 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), -(1 - 9))/T(3) - 3)$
33916 := $((C(T(6), -(1 - 9)) + T(3))/T(3))$
33958 := $((8^5) + (T(C(9, 3))/3))$
33999 := $((T(9) \times (9 \times C(9, 3))) - T(T(3)))$
34125 := $(C(T(5), 2) \times T((1 + (4 \times T(3))))$
34235 := $(T(5) + (C(T(3), T(2)) \times T((T(T(4)) + 3))))$
34285 := $(-T(5) + (C(8, 2) \times T((T(T(4)) - (T(3))))))$
34299 := $(9 \times ((T(C(9, T(2))) + T(4)) + T(T(T(3))))$
34352 := $(-((T(2) - C(T(5), 3))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(3))))$
34364 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(6)) + (C((T(3) \times 4), 3)))$
34375 := $((5^{7-3}) \times T(T(C(4, 3))))$
34398 := $(T((T(8) - 9)) \times T((3 + T(C(4, 3))))$
34427 := $((T(C(7, T(2))) - 4) \times T(T(4))) - 3$
34448 := $(8 \times (C(T(4), 4) + (4^{T(3)})))$
34474 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(C(7, 4))) + T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))$
34515 := $(T(5) \times (1 + C((T(5) + T(4)), 3)))$
34595 := $(-C(T(5), 9) + ((T(T(5)) \times T(T(4))) \times T(3)))$
34596 := $((T(T(6)) - (T(9)))^{C(5, 4)-3})$
34647 := $((T(C(7, 4)) \times T((6 + 4))) - 3)$
34735 := $((C(T(5), T(3)) \times 7) - T((4 \times T(3))))$
34833 := $((T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(8)))) + C(T(4), 3))$
34842 := $((-T(2) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))) + (C(T(4), T(3)))$
34872 := $((T(T(2))^7)/8) - (C(T(4), 3))$
34882 := $(-2) - (-T(8) \times C((-T(8) + T(T(4))), 3))$
34957 := $((7 \times C(T(5), 9)) - T((4 \times 3)))$
35112 := $((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times T((1 + T(C(5, 3))))$
35224 := $(4 \times ((T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)}) - (C(T(5), 3))))$
35266 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T(6)/T(2)) \times C(T(5), T(3))))$
35287 := $(7 \times (T(8) + C((T(2) \times 5), T(3))))$
35294 := $(-4) + (T(C(9, 2)) \times 53)$
35352 := $((2^{T(5)}) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5))/T(T(3))))$
35398 := $((T((8 + 9)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(C(5, 3)))$
35469 := $((T(C(9, 6)) \times T(4)) - T((T(5) + T(3))))$
35475 := $((T(5) + T(C(7, 4))) \times T(C(5, 3)))$
35485 := $(-5) + (T((8 + 4)) \times C(T(5), 3))$
35574 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(C(7, 5)))/C(5, 3))$
35694 := $((T(4) \times T(C(9, C(6, 5)))) - T(3))$
35695 := $(-5) + (T(C(9, 6)) \times C(5, 3))$
35805 := $((-T(5) + T(T(08))) \times T(C(5, 3)))$
35919 := $(T(T(9)) + (C(19, 5) \times 3))$
35934 := $((4 + C(T(T(3)), (9 - 5))) \times T(3))$
35945 := $((T(T(5)) - (-4 + T(9))) \times C(T(5), 3))$
35946 := $((C(T(6), 4) - 9) + T(5)) \times T(3))$
36197 := $(-T(7) + (T(T(9)) \times C((1 + 6), 3)))$
36253 := $((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \times 2) + T(T(6)))/3$
36287 := $((T(7) \times (T(8)^2)) - C(6, T(3)))$
36294 := $((T(T(4)) \times (T(C(9, 2)) - 6)) - T(3))$
36337 := $((T(7) \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) - T((T(6) + T(T(3))))$
36432 := $((T(2) \times T(3)) \times C((4 \times 6), 3))$
36465 := $((C(T(5), 6) \times T((-4) + T(6)))/T(T(3)))$
36575 := $(5 \times C((7 + T(5)), (6 \times 3)))$
36595 := $(-5) + (T((T(9) + T(5))) \times C(6, 3))$
36652 := $(-((T((2 + 5)) \times (T(6) - C(T(6), 3))))$
36673 := $(T(T(3)) - ((T(7) \times (T(6) - C(T(6), 3))))$
36728 := $(-((8^{T(2)}) - (T(7) \times C(T(6), 3))))$
36744 := $((C(T(4), 4) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) - T(3))$
36897 := $((T(7) \times T((T(C(9, 8)) + 6))) - T(T(T(3))))$
36947 := $((T(T(7)) \times T((4 + 9))) + C(6, T(3)))$
36979 := $(-9) - (T(7) \times (9 - C(T(6), 3)))$
36988 := $((8 - T(8)) \times (9 - C(T(6), 3)))$
37122 := $(T(2) \times (-2) + C(17, T(3)))$
37124 := $(-4) + (T(2) \times C(17, T(3)))$
37128 := $(C(8, 2) \times T((17 \times 3)))$
37222 := $(T(2) + ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times T(7)) - T(T(3))))$
37227 := $(-7) + ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times T(7)) - T(3))$
37232 := $(-2) - ((C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \times (-T(7))) + T(3))$
37234 := $((-4) \times (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \times (-7))) - T(3))$
37235 := $(-5) + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \times T(C(7, T(3))))$
37237 := $((C((7 \times 3), T(2)) \times T(7)) - 3)$

- 37243** := $((C(T(T(3))), T((4-2))) \times T(7)) + 3$
37246 := $((C(T(6), T((4-2))) \times T(7)) + T(3))$
37261 := $((C(T((1 \times 6)), T(2)) \times T(7)) + T(T(3)))$
37264 := $(-4) \times ((C(T(6), T(2)) \times (-7)) - T(3))$
37296 := $(((-6) \times T(C(9, 2))) \times T(7)) / (-3)$
37298 := $((T(8) \times T(T(9))) + (T(2) + C(7, 3)))$
37366 := $((T(T(6)) - C(T(6), 3)) \times (-T(7) + T(3)))$
37385 := $((C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) - T((T(7) + T(T(3))))$
37457 := $((T(7) \times (C(T(5), 4) - T(7))) + T(T(3)))$
37479 := $((T((T(9) - 7)) \times T(T(4))) - (C(T(7), 3)))$
37498 := $(-T(T(8))) + (94 \times T(T(C(7, T(3))))$
37575 := $((T(5) \times T(T(7))) + C(T(5), 7)) \times 3$
37584 := $((T((T(4) + 8)) - C(T(5), 7)) \times (-T(3)))$
37596 := $((T(6) - T(T(9))) + ((C(T(5), 7) \times T(3))))$
37632 := $((2^{T(3)} \times T(6)) \times T(C(7, T(3))))$
37635 := $((T(5)^3 - C(T(6), 7)) / (-3))$
37672 := $(-2) - (C(T(7), 6) / (-7 + 3))$
37689 := $-((T(T(9)) + (T(8) - (C(T(6), 7) / 3)))$
37697 := $((-T(7)) - T(T(9))) - (C(T(6), 7) / (-3))$
37736 := $((C(T(6), 3) \times T(7)) + T((T(7) + 3)))$
37752 := $(C((-2) + T(5)), 7) \times (T(7) - T(3))$
37758 := $((T(T(8)) - (T(5))) \times T(T(7))) / C(7, T(3))$
37835 := $(T((C(5, 3) + T(8))) \times C(7, 3))$
37848 := $((T(8) \times T(C(T(4), 8))) + (T(7) \times T(T(3))))$
37962 := $((2 - T(6)) \times T(C(9, 7))) \times (-3)$
37968 := $((T(8) + T(6)) \times T(C(9, 7))) + T(3)$
37995 := $(T(59) + (T(T(9)) \times C(7, 3)))$
38112 := $(-T(2)) - (-C(11, 8) \times T(T(T(3))))$
38227 := $((T(7) \times (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + T(8))) - (T(T(3))))$
38232 := $((T(2) + T(T(3))) \times (-T(2) - T(C(8, 3))))$
38235 := $(T(T(5)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times C((T(2) + 8), 3)))$
38247 := $(((-T(7)) - T(C(T(4), 2))) \times (-T(8))) - T(T(3))$
38248 := $((T(T(8)) - 4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C(8, 3)$
38268 := $(-T(8) - ((T(6) + T(2)) \times T(C(8, 3))))$
38286 := $((-6) + (T(C(8, T(2))) \times 8)) \times 3$
38289 := $((T(T(9)) + C(8, 2)) \times T(8)) + T(T(3))$
38294 := $(-T(4) + ((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(C(8, 3))))$
38304 := $(4 \times T(03)) \times T(C(8, 3))$
38328 := $(8 \times (T(2) + (3 \times T(C(8, 3))))$
38338 := $((8 - C(T(T(3)), 3)) \times (-8) - T(T(3)))$
38344 := $(4 \times (T(4) + (T(3) \times T(C(8, 3))))$
38346 := $((T(6) - T(C(4, 3))) \times T(83))$
38349 := $(T(9) - ((-4) \times T(3)) \times T(C(8, 3)))$
38354 := $(C((4 \times 5), T(3)) - T(C(8, T(3))))$
38444 := $((T(4) + 4)^4 + C(8, T(3)))$
38529 := $(-(9^2) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)))$
38532 := $-((T((2 \times T(3))) - ((C(T(5), 8) \times T(3))))$
38533 := $((T(T(T(3))) / (-3)) + ((C(T(5), 8) \times T(3))))$
38538 := $((T(8) / (-3)) + C(T(5), 8)) \times T(3)$
38545 := $(-5) - ((T(4) - C(T(5), 8)) \times T(3))$
38556 := $((6 - T(5)) + C(T(5), 8)) \times T(3)$
38565 := $((T(5) - C((T(6) - 5), 8)) \times (-3))$
38567 := $(-7) - (-6) \times (C(T(5), 8) - T(3))$
38568 := $-(((T(8) + 6) - (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3))))$
38574 := $(T(-(4 - 7))) \times (C(T(5), 8) - T(3))$
38575 := $(-(5 \times 7)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3))$
38576 := $((-6) - T(7)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3))$
38584 := $((T(4) - T(8)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)))$
38592 := $(-(2 \times 9)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3))$
38654 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(5)) - T(6))) \times T(C(8, T(3))))$
38655 := $((T(5) + C((-5) + T(6)), 8) \times 3)$
38724 := $-((T((4 \times 2)) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))$
38732 := $-((T((T(T(T(2)))) / 3) - (C((T(7) - 8), T(3))))$
38733 := $(-(3^3) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))$
38736 := $-(((T(6) + 3) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3))))$
38739 := $-((T((9 - 3)) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3))))$
38743 := $-((T(T(3)) + (-4) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3))))$
38744 := $(-(4 \times 4) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))$
38745 := $((-5) - T(4)) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3))$
38748 := $(-(8 + 4) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))$
38752 := $-(((T(2) + 5) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3))))$
38754 := $-((T(T((T(4)/5))) - (C((T(7) - 8), T(3))))$
38755 := $(-5) + C(((5 + 7) + 8), T(3))$
38757 := $-((T((7 - 5)) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3))))$
38772 := $((C((T(2) \times 7), 7) + T(8)) / 3)$
38773 := $((T(3) + 7) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))$
38775 := $(T(5) + C(((T(7) + T(7)) - T(8)), T(3)))$
38779 := $((-9) + T(7)) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3))$
38788 := $((-8) + T(8)) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3))$
38797 := $((T(7) + 9) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))$
38826 := $((C(C(6, 2), 8) + T(8)) \times T(3))$
38836 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) \times 8) + C(8, T(3))$
38842 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(8)) \times C(8, 3)))$
38922 := $((T((C(2, 2) + T(9))) \times T(8)) + (T(3)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38934 &:= (((C(T(4), T(3)) \times 9) - T(8)) \times T(T(3))) \\
 38976 &:= ((6 \times (7 + 9)) \times T(C(8, T(3)))) \\
 39228 &:= ((T((T(8) - T(T(2)))) + 2) \times C(9, 3)) \\
 39237 &:= (((C(T(7), T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2))) + 9) - T(T(T(3)))) \\
 39255 &:= (-(T(5)) + ((5 + T(T(2))) \times T(C(9, 3)))) \\
 39284 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (C(8, T(2)) \times (9^3))) \\
 39285 &:= (T(5) - ((-8) - T(2)) \times T(C(9, 3))) \\
 39292 &:= ((2 + 9) \times (2 + T(C(9, 3)))) \\
 39327 &:= (((C(7, T(2)) + 3) \times T(T(9))) - 3) \\
 39336 &:= ((T(T(6))/T(T(3))) \times (T(3) + T(C(9, 3)))) \\
 39384 &:= (4 \times ((T(C(8, 3)) + T(9)) \times T(3))) \\
 39422 &:= (((T(2) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(4)))/9) + T(T(T(3)))) \\
 39582 &:= ((C((T(T(T(2))) + 8), 5) - 9)/3) \\
 39585 &:= (-(T(5)) + (8 \times T((T(5) + (C(9, 3))))) \\
 39745 &:= (-(T(5)) + (T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(C(9, 3)))))) \\
 39795 &:= (((5 \times T(T(9))) \times 7) + (T(C(9, 3)))) \\
 39886 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (C(8, 8) + T(T(9))))/T(3)) \\
 40956 &:= (C(6, 5) + (T(90) \times T(4))) \\
 41469 &:= -((T(T(9)) - C((6 \times 4), (1 + 4))) \\
 41775 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (7 \times C(T((7 - 1), 4))) \\
 41838 &:= -((T(T(8)) - C((3 \times 8), (1 + 4))) \\
 42175 &:= ((T(T(5)) \times C((T(7) - 1), 2) + T(T(4))) \\
 42273 &:= ((3 \times T(C(7, 2))) \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(4)))) \\
 42335 &:= ((T(5) \times C((3^3), T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 42368 &:= (8 \times ((-C(T(6), 3) + T(T(2))) \times (-4)) \\
 42384 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(T(3)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 4)) \\
 42396 &:= (-6) \times (-((C(9, 3)^2) - T(4))) \\
 42426 &:= (((C(T(6), 2) - 4)^2) - T(4)) \\
 42427 &:= ((T(7)^{T(2)}) + C(T((T(4) - T(2))), 4)) \\
 42435 &:= (T((T(5) \times 3)) \times (C(T(4), 2) - 4)) \\
 42436 &:= ((T(C(6, 3)) - 4)⁻²⁺⁴) \\
 42462 &:= (C((T(2) \times 6), T(4)) - (T(T(2))⁴)) \\
 42475 &:= (-((T(5) + (C(T(7), 4) \times (-2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 42496 &:= ((C(-((T(6) - T(9))), 4) - 2) \times 4) \\
 42528 &:= (C((8 \times T(2)), 5) + (24)) \\
 42532 &:= (C((T(2) + T(T(3))), 5) + T((T(2) + 4))) \\
 42534 &:= (C((4 \times T(3)), 5) + (T(2) \times T(4))) \\
 42559 &:= (C((9 + T(5)), (T(5)/T(2))) + T(T(4))) \\
 42562 &:= ((C((T(2) + T(6)), 5) + T(2)) + T(T(4))) \\
 42564 &:= (C((4 \times 6), 5) + (T(T(2)) \times T(4))) \\
 42572 &:= (-(T(2)) + ((T(T(7)) \times C(T(5), 2)) - T(T(4)))) \\
 42582 &:= (C((T(2) \times 8), 5) + T((2 + T(4)))) \\
 42595 &:= (C((T(5) + 9), 5) + T((T(2) + T(4)))) \\
 42685 &:= (((5 \times T(C(8, 6))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)))) \\
 42693 &:= (-T(T(3))) \times (-((T(C(9, 6)) + T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 42699 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - (C((T(6) - 2), 4))) \\
 42812 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times (T(C(8, 2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 42822 &:= ((T(2)^{T(2)}) \times (T(C(8, T(2))) - T(4))) \\
 42846 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 4)) \\
 42867 &:= (-T((T(7) - 6))) - (-C(8, 2) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\
 42899 &:= (-C(9, 9)) + (T((T(8) + T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \\
 42928 &:= (C(8, 2) + (T((T(9) - T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4)))) \\
 43277 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((C(7, T(2))³) - 4)) \\
 43282 &:= (-T(T(2)) + (C(8, 2) \times (T(3) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\
 43284 &:= (-4) + (C(8, 2) \times (T(3) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\
 43293 &:= -((T((T(T(3)) + 9)) - C((T(2) \times T(3)), T(4))) \\
 43344 &:= ((T(T(T(4)) - C((-4) + T(T(3))), T(3))) \times (-4)) \\
 43352 &:= -((T(T(2+5))) - C((3 \times T(3)), T(4))) \\
 43357 &:= -((T(T(7)) - (5 + C((3 \times T(3))), T(4))) \\
 43365 &:= (T(5) \times ((C(T(6), 3) + T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\
 43373 &:= ((T(T(3)) - T(T(7))) + C((3 \times T(3)), T(4))) \\
 43398 &:= ((-8) \times T(9)) + C((3 \times T(3)), T(4)) \\
 43428 &:= (C((T(8)/2), T(4)) + (-T(3) \times T(T(4)))) \\
 43433 &:= (C((3 \times T(3)), T(4)) - T((T(T(3)) + 4))) \\
 43488 &:= (T(8) \times (8 + (C(T(4), 3) \times T(4)))) \\
 43524 &:= ((T(C(T(4), 2)) \times (-T(5))) + ((3^{T(4)}))) \\
 43527 &:= -((T(C(7, 2)) - C((T(5) + 3), T(4))) \\
 43545 &:= (-C((5 \times 4), 5) + (3^{T(4)})) \\
 43569 &:= ((-9) \times T(6)) + C((T(5) + 3), T(4)) \\
 43582 &:= ((C((T(T(2)) + 8), 5) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 43632 &:= -(((T(T(2)) \times T(T(3))) - C((6 \times 3), T(4))) \\
 43635 &:= -((T(T(5)) - (-3) + C((6 \times 3), T(4)))) \\
 43653 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times (-5)) + C((6 \times 3), T(4))) \\
 43667 &:= -((T((7 + 6)) - C((6 \times 3), T(4))) \\
 43675 &:= (-5) + (-T(7)) \times (-C(6, 3) - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 43692 &:= -((T((2 + 9)) - C((6 \times 3), T(4))) \\
 43694 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (-9) + C((6 \times 3), T(4)))) \\
 43725 &:= (T(5) \times (C(27, 3) - T(4))) \\
 43728 &:= (((T(8) \times T(2)) \times T(T(7))) - T(C(T(3), 4))) \\
 43748 &:= (C((8 + T(4)), (7 + 3)) - T(4)) \\
 43749 &:= (-9) + C((-((4 - 7)) \times T(3)), T(4)) \\
 43752 &:= -((T(T(2)) - C(((5 + 7) + T(3)), T(4))) \\
 43754 &:= (-4) + C(((5 + 7) + T(3)), T(4)) \\
 43762 &:= (C((T(2) \times 6), (7 + 3)) + 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43836 &:= (C((6 \times 3), 8) + T((3 \times 4))) \\ 43838 &:= (((T(8) \times 3) \times T(C(8, T(3)))) - T(4)) \\ 43935 &:= (T(5) \times (C((3 \times 9), 3) + 4)) \\ 43956 &:= (T((6 + 5)) \times T(C(9, (3 + 4)))) \\ 44224 &:= (((T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(T(4))) + 4) \\ 44225 &:= (5 \times (C((2 + T(T(T(2))))), 4) - T(4)) \\ 44228 &:= (-T(8) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - ((T(4)^4)))) \\ 44236 &:= ((T(C(6, 3))^2) + T((4 \times 4))) \\ 44262 &:= (-2) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - ((T(4)^4))) \\ 44264 &:= (C(T(T(T(-(4 - 6))))), T(T(2))) - ((T(4)^4))) \\ 44265 &:= ((5 \times C((T(6) + 2), 4)) - T(4)) \\ 44266 &:= ((C(T(6), 6) + 2) - T(4)^4) \\ 44324 &:= -((T(T((T(4) + T(2)))) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-C(T(4), 4)))))) \\ 44325 &:= (-5) \times (-C(23, 4) - T(4)) \\ 44379 &:= (-T(C(9, 7))) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(4) + T(T(4)))))) \\ 44435 &:= (-T(5)) + (((-C(T(T(3)), 4)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4))) \\ 44446 &:= (((-C(T(6), 4)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4))) - 4) \\ 44465 &:= (T(5) + ((-C(T(6), 4)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4))) \\ 44728 &:= ((T(C(8, T(2))) \times T(7)) + (T(4) \times 4)) \\ 44745 &:= ((T(5)^4) - (T(7) \times C(T(4), 4))) \\ 44826 &:= ((6^{T(T(2))}) - T((C(8, 4) - T(4)))) \\ 44832 &:= -((T(2) \times (T(3) - C((T(8) - T(4)), 4)))) \\ 44835 &:= -((T(5) - (3 \times C((T(8) - T(4)), 4)))) \\ 44959 &:= ((9 \times (C(T(5), 9) - T(4))) + 4) \\ 45045 &:= (C(T(5), T(4)) \times T(C(05, 4))) \\ 45055 &:= ((C(T(5), 5) \times T(05)) + T(4)) \\ 45116 &:= ((6^{C(1,1)+5}) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45135 &:= (T(5) \times (T(3) + C(15, T(4)))) \\ 45165 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T((6 - 1)) \times C(T(5), T(4)))) \\ 45195 &:= (T(5) \times ((9 + 1) + C(T(5), T(4)))) \\ 45225 &:= (-T(5)) \times ((T(T(2)) \times (-2)) - (C(T(5), T(4)))) \\ 45255 &:= (T(T(5)) + (T(5) \times (T(T(2)) + (C(T(5), T(4)))))) \\ 45277 &:= (-T(7)) + ((C(T(7), 2) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4))) \\ 45285 &:= (T(5) \times ((8 \times 2) + C(T(5), T(4)))) \\ 45291 &:= ((T(-(1 - 9)))^{T(2)}) - (C(T(5), 4)) \\ 45298 &:= (T(T(T((T(8)/9)))) + C((T(2) + T(5)), T(4))) \\ 45375 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(7) - T(3)) + C(T(5), T(4)))) \\ 45477 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) \times 4)) + C(5, 4)) \\ 45525 &:= (T(5) \times ((2^5) + C(T(5), T(4)))) \\ 45529 &:= (((-T(T(9))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) - (5 \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 45585 &:= (T(5) \times (T(8) + C(T(5), C(5, 4)))) \\ 45675 &:= (T(5) \times ((7 \times 6) + C(T(5), T(4)))) \\ 45732 &:= ((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) - (T(C(7, 5)) \times 4)) \\ 45836 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) - T((8 \times C(5, 4)))) \\ 45843 &:= -((T(T(3)) \times (T((4 + T(8))) - (C(T(5), T(4)))))) \\ 45857 &:= (-7) \times ((-C(T(5), 8)) - T(T(5))) + 4) \\ 45864 &:= ((4 \times T(6)) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(C(5, 4)))))) \\ 45895 &:= ((T((5 + T(9))) \times T(8)) - C(5, 4)) \\ 45975 &:= (((5 \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) \times T(C(5, 4))) \\ 46116 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T(11)) - C(6, 4))) \\ 46212 &:= (-T(2)) - (T(T(12)) \times (-C(6, 4))) \\ 46224 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(C(T(T(2)), T(2)))) + 6) \times 4) \\ 46311 &:= ((T(T(11)) \times T(T(3))) - (T(C(6, 4)))) \\ 46356 &:= ((C(6, 5)^{T(3)}) - T((6 \times 4))) \\ 46398 &:= (T((-8) + T(9)) \times C((T(3) + 6), T(4))) \\ 46416 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T((1 + T(4)))) - C(6, 4)) \\ 46421 &:= ((T(C(12, T(4))) \times T(6)) - T(4)) \\ 46431 &:= (T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T(T(-(4 - C(6, 4)))))) \\ 46466 &:= ((6^6) - T((4 + C(6, 4)))) \\ 46512 &:= (C((T(T(T(2))) - 1), 5) \times T((6 - 4))) \\ 46549 &:= ((9 \times (-4) + C(T(5), 6)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 46557 &:= (7 \times (T(T((T(T(5))/T(5)))) + (C(T(6), 4)))) \\ 46626 &:= -(((C(6, T(2)) - ((6^6))) + T(4))) \\ 46636 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) - C(6, T((6 - 4)))) \\ 46711 &:= (C(1, 1) - 7)^6 + T(T(4)) \\ 46722 &:= ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + T((C(7, 6) + 4))) \\ 46789 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (8 \times (-7) + C(T(6), 4)))) \\ 46834 &:= (((-C(T(4), T(3))) \times (8 - T(T(6)))) + 4) \\ 46845 &:= -((T(T((5 + 4))) - (8 \times C(T(6), 4)))) \\ 46849 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(C(T(4), 8)) + 6)) + 4) \\ 46992 &:= ((T(2) + 9) \times T((C(9, 6) + 4))) \\ 47124 &:= ((C(T(4), T(2)) - 1) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4))) \\ 47283 &:= (-3) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(C(7, 4))) \\ 47286 &:= ((6^{8-2}) + T(C(7, 4))) \\ 47352 &:= (-T(2)) - (((-C(T(5), 3)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 47436 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) + T((4 + C(7, 4)))) \\ 47565 &:= (T(5) \times (T(6) + (5 \times T(C(7, 4)))))) \\ 47887 &:= ((7 \times T(88)) + C(T(7), 4)) \\ 47928 &:= (8 \times (T(T(2)) + C(T(T(T((9 - 7))))), 4)) \\ 47952 &:= (((T(2) + T(5)) \times T(C(9, 7))) \times 4) \\ 47985 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(8))) + (T(9))) \times C(7, 4)) \\ 47988 &:= (T(8) \times (T((-8) + T(9))) + (T(C(7, 4)))) \\ 48356 &:= ((T(T(6)) - (T(T(C(5, 3))) \times 8)) \times (-4)) \\ 48365 &:= (((T(5) + C(T(6), 3)) \times T(8)) - T(T(4)))$$

- 48366** := $((T(T(6)) \times T(C(6,3))) - (T(8) \times 4))$
48369 := $(T(T(9)) + (-T(6) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(C(8,4))))))$
48545 := $((C(T(5),4) - T(5)) \times T(8) - T(T(4)))$
48599 := $(-C(9,9) - (-T(5) \times T((8 \times T(4))))$
48632 := $((C(T(T(T(2))),3) + (T(6))) \times T(8) - 4)$
48635 := $(T(5) + C((3 \times 6), (T(8)/4)))$
48639 := $((T(T(9)) + C(T(T(3)),6) - (T(T(8)) \times T(4)))$
48724 := $((C(T(4),T(2)) \times T(T(7))) + (8 - 4))$
48726 := $((T(C(6,2)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T((8/4)))$
48746 := $((T(C(6,4)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(8) - T(4)))$
48825 := $((5^2) \times T(-((8 - C(8,4))))$
48856 := $(C(T(6),T(5)) - (8 \times (T(T(8)) + T(4))))$
48925 := $((T(T(C(5,2))) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(8) + T(T(4))))$
49225 := $((-5) + (C(T(T(2)),T(2)) \times T(9))) \times T(T(4))$
49229 := $((T(C(9,2))^2/9) - T(T(4)))$
49255 := $((T(T(5)) \times (C(T(5),T(2)) - T(9))) + T(T(4)))$
49275 := $(-((T(5) \times (C(T(7),T(2)) - (9^4))))$
49324 := $((C((-4) + T(T(T(2))))), T(3)) - T(9) \times 4)$
49595 := $(-5) - ((T(9) - C(T(5),9)) \times T(4))$
49722 := $(C((T(T(T(2))) - 2), 7) - T((9 \times 4)))$
49735 := $((T(C(5,3)) - 7) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(4))$
49736 := $(-6) - (C(-((T(3) - T(7))),9)/(-T(4)))$
49742 := $(C((2 \times (4 + 7)),9)/T(4))$
49763 := $(T(T(3)) + (C((-6) + T(7)),9)/T(4))$
49955 := $(-5) + ((C(T(5),9) - 9) \times T(4))$
50268 := $((T(T(8)) \times (-6)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(05)))$
50625 := $(T(5))^{-2+C(6,05)}$
51667 := $((T(T(C(7,6))) + (T(6))) \times (1 + T(T(5))))$
51723 := $(C(T(T(3)),T(T(2))) - ((T(71) - T(5))))$
51968 := $(T(C(8,6)) \times ((9 - 1) + T(T(5))))$
52053 := $(-((T(T(T(3) + 5))) - C(T(T(T(02))), T(5))))$
52164 := $((-T(4) \times T((T(6) - 1))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)))$
52184 := $(-((T((T(T(4)) + (8 + 1))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))))$
52192 := $((-2) \times (T(T(9)) + 1)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52224 := $((4^{T(2)}) \times C((T(T(2)) \times T(2)), T(5)))$
52226 := $(C(6, T(2)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5))$
52229 := $((T(9) - T((2^{T(T(2))}))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52239 := $(-((T(9) \times T(3^2))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)))$
52248 := $((T(C(8,4)) + T(2)) \times (T(T(2)) + (T(5))))$
52253 := $((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))) + 5)$
52263 := $(-T((3 \times T(6))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + T(5)))$
52266 := $(C(T(6),6) + (-T(2) \times T(T((T(2) + 5))))$
52268 := $(-((T(T(8)) + C(T(6), T(2)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)))$
52284 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-T(8))) + C(T((2 \times T(2))), T(5)))$
52287 := $(((-7) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(2))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52353 := $(C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - (T(T(3)) \times T((-2) + T(5))))$
52364 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) + (-C(T(6), T(3))) - (-T(2) \times T(T(5))))$
52368 := $((-8) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(3)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52373 := $(-T((T(3) + T((7 + 3)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52395 := $((T(5) \times T(C(9,3))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-5))$
52424 := $((-T(4) - T((T(T(2)) \times T(4)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52427 := $((-T(T(7)) - T((-2) + T(T(4)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52432 := $((-2) - T((T(3) \times T(4)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52433 := $((C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + T(2)))) - (T(T(5))))$
52434 := $(-((T((T(4) \times T(3))) - C(T(C(4,2)), T(5))))$
52442 := $((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4) + T(T(C(4,2)))) + 5)$
52444 := $(-C((4 \times 4), 4) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52449 := $((-T(9)) - T((4 + T(T(4)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52493 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) + T((T(9) + T(4)))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))))$
52494 := $(-T((49 + T(4))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52527 := $((-7) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-T(T(5))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)))$
52539 := $((T(T(9)) / (-3) \times 5) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52553 := $(-T((3 + 55))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52584 := $(-((T((T(T(4)) + 8)) + (-C(T(5), T(2))) \times T(T(5))))$
52604 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) - (C(T(06), T(T(2))) - T(T(5))))$
52624 := $(4 \times (C(26, T(T(T(2)))) / 5)$
52646 := $(C(T(6),4) + ((6^{T(T(2))}) + 5))$
52647 := $((T(7) / (-4)) \times T(T(6))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52649 := $((T(9) - T(T(T(4)))) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - T(T(5))))$
52694 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) + (T(9) - (C(T(6), T(T(2))) + (T(5))))))$
52722 := $((-2) - T(T((T(2) + 7)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52724 := $(-T((T(4) + T((2 + 7)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52726 := $((T(T(6))^2 - T(C(7, T(2)))) - 5)$
52727 := $(-((T(T(7)) - (T(2) + C((T(7) - T(2)), 5))))$
52736 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(C(7, T(2))) - 5))$
52745 := $((C(T(5),4) - T(T(7))) \times T((2 \times 5)))$
52752 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - (-T(7) + T(T((2 \times 5))))$
52758 := $(-((T(T(8)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-7)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52784 := $((-4) \times (-T(8) + T(T(7)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
52833 := $(C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T(((T(8) + 2) + T(5))))$
52844 := $-T(T(T(4))) + C(T(T(T(T(4) - 8))), T(T(2))) + T(T(5))$
52914 := $(-((T(T(T(4))) - T(19)) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))))$
52933 := $((C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) - 5)$
52934 := $((-4) - T((T(3) + T(9)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 52946 &:= (((T(T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 9) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\
 52948 &:= (T((C(8, 4) - 9) \times T((2 + 5))) \\
 52953 &:= ((C(T(T(3))), T(5)) - T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \\
 52954 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times (-5)) - T(T(9))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\
 52964 &:= -(((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(6)) + 9))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\
 52976 &:= (-((T((-6) + T(7))) + T(T(9))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\
 52995 &:= (T(T(5)) - ((T(9) - T(C(9, T(2)))) \times T(5))) \\
 53145 &:= (C((T(5) + T(4)), (-1) + T(3))) + T(5)) \\
 53164 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(6) - 1)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53184 &:= -(((T((T(4) + T(8))) - 1) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53214 &:= -(((T((T(4) - 1))) - (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(5)))) \\
 53219 &:= -(((T(T(9)) + T((1 + T(2)))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53223 &:= ((C(T(T(3))), T(T(2))) - T(T(2))) - T((3 \times T(5))) \\
 53224 &:= ((T((4^{T(2)})) / (-2)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53227 &:= -(((T(T((7 + 2))) + 2) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53229 &:= (C(T((9 - T(2))), T(T(2))) - T((3 \times T(5)))) \\
 53232 &:= (T(2) + (C(T(T(3))), T(T(2))) - T((3 \times T(5)))) \\
 53239 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - T((T(3) - 2))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53241 &:= ((T(T(C((1 \times 4), 2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(5)))) \\
 53242 &:= (-(((2^{T(4)}) - 2)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53243 &:= -(((T(T(3)) + ((T(4)^{T(2)}))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53249 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - (T(4) \times 2)) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53257 &:= ((T(7) - T((T(5) \times T(2)))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53259 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - (T(5) \times 2)) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53264 &:= (-((T(4)^{6/2})) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53272 &:= ((-2) \times T((T(7) + T(2)))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53274 &:= -((T((47 - T(2))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53318 &:= -(((T((T(8) + 1) + T(3))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53319 &:= ((-T(9)) \times T(T((1 \times 3)))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53326 &:= ((T(T(6))^2 - (C(T(3), 3) + T(5))) \\
 53334 &:= ((-4) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(3) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53336 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (C(T(3), 3) + 5)) \\
 53358 &:= -(((T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) - (C(T(T(3))), T(3)) - T(T(5)))) \\
 53364 &:= ((T((4 \times 6)) \times (-3)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53367 &:= (-((T((7 \times 6)) - T(3))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53382 &:= -(((T(T(2)) + T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53388 &:= ((T((T(8) + T(8))) / (-3)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53422 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2))))^2 + (T(T(4)) + C(T(3), 5))) \\
 53429 &:= -(((T(T(9) - T(T(2)))) + (T(T(4)) - C(T(T(3))), T(5)))) \\
 53439 &:= (((T(9)) / (-3)) \times T(T(4))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53442 &:= ((-2) - T((T(4) \times 4))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53444 &:= (-T((44 - 4)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53448 &:= -(((T((T(8) + 4)) - 4) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53449 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - (4 \times T(T(4)))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53454 &:= ((T(4) - T((-T(5)) + T(T(4)))) + (C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53472 &:= ((-2) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53478 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (C(T(T((7 - 4))), T(3)) - T(T(5)))) \\
 53484 &:= (-((T(4) \times T((8 + 4))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53489 &:= ((T(9) - T((T(8) + 4))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53498 &:= -(((T(T(8)) + T(T(9))) + T(T(4)) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53514 &:= ((T(T((T(4) + 1))) \times T(5)) + (C(T(T(3))), 5)) \\
 53519 &:= -((T((T(9) + 1)) + (-C(T(5), 3)) \times T(T(5)))) \\
 53523 &:= (C(T(T(3))), T(T(2))) - T((53 - T(5))) \\
 53528 &:= -(((T((T(8) + 2)) - 5) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53529 &:= ((T(C(9, T(2))) \times T(5)) - (T(3) + T(5))) \\
 53534 &:= ((-T(4)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + (-T(3) \times T(T(5))) \\
 53537 &:= ((-7) + C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + (-T(3) \times T(T(5))) \\
 53539 &:= (((T(C(9, 3)) \times T(5)) - T(3)) - 5) \\
 53544 &:= (C(T((-4) + T(4))), T(5)) + (-T(3) \times T(T(5))) \\
 53545 &:= ((T(5) \times T(C((4 + 5), 3))) - 5) \\
 53561 &:= -(((T((1 + T(6)) + T(5))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53565 &:= ((T(5) \times T(C((-6) + T(5)), 3)) + T(5)) \\
 53572 &:= (((-2) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(5)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53582 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(8)) - 5) - C(T(T(3))), T(5)))) \\
 53583 &:= -(((T((-3) + T(8))) + T(T(5)) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53589 &:= ((-9) - T(T(8))) + C((T(5) + T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53598 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (C((9 + T(5)) - 3), T(5)))) \\
 53618 &:= -(((T(T(8)) - (-1 + T(6))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53619 &:= -(((T(T(9 - 1))) - T(6)) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53624 &:= ((T(4) \times (-2^6)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53627 &:= (-T(T(7))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T((T(3) + T(5)))) \\
 53628 &:= ((-T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))) - ((-C(T(6), T(3))) - T(T(5))) \\
 53632 &:= (-2) + (C(T(T(3))), 6) - T(35))) \\
 53634 &:= (((T(4) \times (-3)) \times T(6)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53649 &:= (((-9) \times T(T(4))) + (C(T(6), T(3)))) - T(T(5))) \\
 53664 &:= -(((T(T(4) - T(6))) - (C(T(6), T(3)) - 5))) \\
 53669 &:= ((T(C(9, 6)) / (-6)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53672 &:= ((T(2) - T((T(7) + 6))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53673 &:= ((-3) - (T(7) \times T(6))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53676 &:= -(((T(6) \times T(7)) - C(T(6), (3 \times 5))) \\
 53679 &:= ((T(9) \times (-7 + 6)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))) \\
 53681 &:= -(((T((1 + T(8))) - (C(T(6), T(3)))) - T(T(5))) \\
 53682 &:= -((T(-((T(2) - T(8)))) - (-T(6) + C(T(T(3))), T(5)))) \\
 53694 &:= -(((T(4) \times T(9)) - C(T(6), T(3)))) - T(T(5))) \\
 53703 &:= -(((T(T(T(3))) / 07) - (C(T(T(3))), T(5))))
 \end{aligned}$$

53718 := $-(T(T(8)) - (C(T(-(1-7))), T(3)) + T(T(5))))$
53722 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)))) - T((T(T(3)) - (5))))$
53724 := $((T(T(4)) - T((T(T(2)) + T(7)))) + (C(T(T(3))), T(5)))$
53725 := $(C(T(5), T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T((3 \times 5))))$
53732 := $(((-2) + T(T(3))) \times (-T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$
53738 := $-((T(T((8-3))) + T(T(7))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)))$
53742 := $((T(T(2)) - T((4 + T(7)))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53746 := $((T(T(6)) \times (-4)) + T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53753 := $((C(T(T(3))), T(5)) - T((T(7) + 3))) - (T(5))$
53763 := $((C(T(T(3))), 6) - T((T(7) + 3))) - (5)$
53767 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) + (C((T(7) - 3), 5)))$
53774 := $((T(4) \times (-7 \times 7))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53784 := $((-4) \times T((8 + 7))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53788 := $(T(T(8)) + (-8) + C((T(7) - 3), 5))$
53792 := $((-T((2 + 9))) - T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53814 := $((-T(4) \times T((1 + 8)))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53822 := $-((T(T((T(T(T(2)))/T(2)))) + (T(8) - C(T(T(3))), T(5))))$
53827 := $((T(7) - T(-(T(T(2)) - T(8)))) + (C(T(T(3))), T(5)))$
53832 := $(((-2) \times T(3)) \times T(8)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53837 := $-((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) - C(T((T(8)/T(3))), T(5)))$
53843 := $-((T(T(T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) - T(8)))) - (C(T(T(3))), T(5))))$
53844 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(C(T(4), 8))) - T(T(-(3) + T(5))))$
53852 := $((-T(T(2))) - T(T((T(5) - 8)))) + (C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53853 := $((C(T(T(3))), T(5)) - T(C(8, T(3)))) - (5)$
53854 := $((T(4) \times (-5 - T(8))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53858 := $-((T(T((C(8, 5)/8))) - C(T(T(3))), T(5)))$
53863 := $((C(T(T(3))), 6) - T(C(8, T(3)))) + (5)$
53872 := $((T(T(2)) - T(T(7))) + 8) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53873 := $-(((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) - T(8)) - C(T(T(3))), T(5)))$
53886 := $-((T(((6 \times T(8))/8)) - C(T(T(3))), T(5)))$
53894 := $((-T(4) - (T(9) \times (-8)))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53897 := $((-7) + (T(9) \times (-8))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53904 := $((-40 \times 9)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53922 := $((-2) \times T((2 \times 9))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53925 := $((5^2) + T(C(9, 3))) \times T(5)$
53934 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-T(3))) + C(T((9 - 3))), T(5))$
53942 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T((4 + 9))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))))$
53943 := $((C(T(T(3))), 4) \times 9) + T((-3) + T(5))$
53946 := $-(((C(T(6), 4) + 9) \times (T(3) - T(5))))$
53954 := $((-T(4) - T((T(5) + 9))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53957 := $((-7) - T((T(5) + 9))) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53962 := $((-2) - T(-(T(6) - T(9)))) + (C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
53964 := $-((T((4 \times 6)) - C(T((9 - 3))), T(5)))$

53985 := $(((-5) + T(8)) \times (-9)) + C(T(T(3))), T(5))$
54033 := $-((T(T(T(3))) - (C(T(T(3))), T((0 \times 4) + 5))))$
54123 := $((C(T(T(3))), T(T(2))) - T(T(-(1 - 4)))) - (T(T(5)))$
54128 := $((-T((8 \times 2))) + C(T(T(-(1 - 4))), T(5))$
54129 := $((-T(9) \times T(2))) + C(T(T(-(1 - 4))), T(5))$
54133 := $((C(T(T(3))), T(3)) - (1 + T(4))) - T(T(5))$
54134 := $((-T(4)) + (C(T(T(3))), T(-(1 - 4)))) - T(T(5))$
54137 := $((-7) + (C(T(T(3))), T(-(1 - 4)))) - T(T(5))$
54144 := $(C(T((-4) + T(4))), T(-(1 - 4))) - T(T(5))$
54153 := $((C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + (-1) + T(4)) - T(T(5))$
54154 := $((T(4) - T(T(5))) + C(T(T(-(1 - 4))), T(5))$
54159 := $((-T((9 + 5))) + C(T(T(-(1 - 4))), T(5))$
54165 := $((-T(T(5)) - T(6))) + C(T(T(-(1 - 4))), T(5))$
54173 := $((-T((T(3) + 7))) + C(T(T(-(1 - 4))), T(5))$
54184 := $((T(4) \times (-8)) + C(T(T(-(1 - 4))), T(5))$
54214 := $(C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(T(2))) - (T(4) \times 5))$
54219 := $((T(9) \times (-1)) + C(T((2 + 4))), T(5))$
54223 := $(C(T(T(3))), T(T(2))) - (T((2 \times 4)) + (5))$
54224 := $((C(T(C(4, 2))), T(T(2))) - T(T(4))) + (T(5))$
54226 := $(C(T(6), T(T(2))) - (2 \times (4 + T(5))))$
54227 := $((-T(7)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - (4 + 5)))$
54228 := $((T(8) - C((T(2) \times (T(2) + 4))), T(5)))$
54232 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - (-((2 - 4)^5))$
54233 := $(C(T(T(3))), T(3)) - ((2^4) + T(5))$
54234 := $((T(4) \times (-3)) + C(T((2 + 4))), T(5))$
54236 := $((C(T(6), T(3)) - T(2) - T(4)) - T(5))$
54237 := $((-7) + (C(T(T(3))), T(T(2))) - (4 \times 5))$
54239 := $(C(T((9 - 3))), T(T(2))) - (T(4) + T(5))$
54243 := $-((T(T(3)) - (C(T(((4 - 2) + 4))), T(5))))$
54244 := $-((T(4) + T(4)) - C(T((2 + 4))), T(5))$
54247 := $((-7) - T(4)) + C(T((2 + 4))), T(5))$
54249 := $((-T((9 - 4)) - C(T((2 + 4))), T(5)))$
54252 := $((T(2) - T(5)) + C(T((2 + 4))), T(5))$
54253 := $-(((T(3) + 5)) - C(T((2 + 4))), T(5))$
54254 := $-((T(4) - C(((5^2) - 4))), T(5))$
54255 := $(C(T(T((T(5)/5))), T(T(2))) - (4 + 5))$
54256 := $((C(T(6), T(5)) - T(2) - T(4)) + (5))$
54257 := $((-7) + C(((5^2) - 4))), T(5))$
54258 := $-((T((8 - 5)) - C(T((2 + 4))), T(5))$
54259 := $(C(T((-9) + T(5))), T(T(2))) - (T(4) - (5))$
54261 := $(C(T((1 \times 6))), T(T(2))) - T((T(4)/5))$
54262 := $(T(2) + (C(T(6), (2 + 4)) - (5)))$

- 54263 := ((T(3)/(-6)) + C(T((2+4)), T(5)))
54264 := C(T(C(4, ((6+2)/4))), T(5))
54265 := (-((5-6)) + C(T((2+4)), T(5)))
54266 := (C(T(6), 6) - ((2 × (4-5))))
54267 := (T(7) + (C(T(6), T(T(2)))) - (T(4) + T(5)))
54268 := (-T(8) + ((C(T(6), T(T(2)))) + T(T(4))) - (T(5)))
54269 := (C(T(T(9-6))), T(T(2))) + (T(4) - (5))
54271 := ((1 × 7) + C(T((2+4)), T(5)))
54273 := (C(T(T(3)), T((7-2))) + (4+5))
54274 := (T(4) + C(C(7, -((2-4))), T(5)))
54279 := (C(T(T(T(9-7))))), T(T(2))) + (T(4) + (5))
54283 := (C(T(T(3)), (8-2)) + (4+T(5)))
54285 := -(((T(5) - T(8)) - C(T((2+4)), T(5))))
54292 := (T(-((2-9))) + (C(T((2+4)), T(5))))
54304 := (40 + C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + (5))))
54309 := (T(9) + C(T(T(03)), (T(4) + (5))))
54314 := (C(T(T((4-1))), T(3)) + (T(4) × 5))
54315 := (51 + C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + (5))))
54319 := (T((9+1)) + C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + (5))))
54322 := (-2) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) + (4 × T(5)))
54323 := (((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - (T(3))) - T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))
54324 := (C(T(C(4,2)), T(3)) + (4 × T(5)))
54325 := (-5) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) + T((-4) + T(5)))
54326 := (((C(T(6), T(T(2))) - 3) - T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))
54329 := ((C(T((9-T(2))), T(3)) - T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))
54342 := (T((2+T(4))) + C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + (5))))
54347 := ((T(7) + T(T(4))) + C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + (5))))
54348 := (84 + C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + (5))))
54353 := (((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(3))) - T(4)) + T(T(5)))
54356 := ((C(T(6), T(5)) - T((3+4))) + T(T(5)))
54359 := (95 + C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + (5))))
54363 := ((C(T(T(3)), 6) - T(T(3))) + T((T(4) + (5))))
54364 := (T(T(4)) + ((C(T(6), T(3)) + 45)))
54365 := (T(T(5)) + (((C(T(6), T(3)) - (4)) - T(5))))
54367 := ((-7) + (C(T(6), T(3)) - T(4)) + T(T(5)))
54369 := ((T(9) + C(T(6), T(3))) + (4 × T(5)))
54374 := (C(T(T(-(4-7))), T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5))))
54423 := (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/T(4)) + 5))
54429 := (T(9) + (C(T(T(T(2))), (-4) + T(4)) + (T(T(5))))
54433 := (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + ((T(T(T(4)))/T(4)) + T(5)))
54435 := ((T(C(5,3)) × T(44)) - T(5))
54462 := (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) + (T(44)/5))
54467 := ((-T(7)) + T(T(6))) + C(T((-4) + T(4)), T(5))
54516 := (C(T(6), (1+5)) + C(T(4), 5))
54522 := (T(T(2)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (C(T(4), 5))))
54533 := ((-T(3)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) - (T(T(4)) × (-5))
54534 := -((T(T(4)) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T((T(4) + T(5))))))
54535 := (((C(T(5), 3) × T(T(5))) + T(T(4))) - T(T(5)))
54537 := (7 × ((T(3)^{C(5,4)}) + T(5)))
54539 := (C(T((9-3)), T(5)) - (T(T(4)) × (-5)))
54567 := ((T(7) + C(T(6), T(5))) - (T(T(4)) × (-5)))
54572 := (C((T(2) × 7), T(5)) - (T(T(T(4)))/(-5)))
54585 := (((5 × 8) × C(T(5), 4)) - T(5))
54595 := (((-5) + T(9)) × C(T(5), 4)) - (5))
54642 := -((T(T(T(2))) × 4) - (T(T(6)) × C(T(4), 5)))
54663 := (C(T(T(3)), 6) + (C(T(6), 4)/T(5)))
54664 := (T(T(T(4))) - (6 - C((T(6) + (4)), 5)))
54667 := ((T(T(7)) + (C(T(6), 6))) - T((T(4)/5)))
54726 := ((T(T(6))²) + ((C(T(7), 4)/T(5))))
54729 := (T((9 + T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(T((7-4))), T(5))))
54736 := ((C(T(6), T(3)) + T(T(7))) + T((-4) + T(5)))
54899 := (-C(9, 9)) - (-T(8)) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))
55125 := ((C(T(5), 2) × T((-1) + T(5))) × 5)
55167 := (T((7 × 6)) + C(T((1+5)), T(5)))
55179 := ((T(T(9)) + (C(T((7-1)), T(5)))) - T(T(5)))
55204 := (T(40) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (T(T(5))))
55216 := (T(T((6+1))) × C((2+T(5)), T(5)))
55249 := ((T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 5))
55269 := (T(T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - (T(5) + T(5))))
55275 := (T(C((5+7), 2)) × (5 × 5))
55278 := (T(T(8)) × ((T(7) × T(2)) - C(5, 5)))
55287 := ((T(7) × T(8)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + T(5)))
55292 := ((-2) + T(T(9))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - 5)
55294 := ((T(4) + T(T(9))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - T(5)))
55297 := ((-7) + T(T(9))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 5)
55299 := (T(T(9)) + (C(C((9-2), 5), T(5))))
55314 := (T(T((T(4)-1))) + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + (T(5))))
55325 := (((C(T(5), T(2)) + T(3)) × T(T(5))) + (5))
55329 := ((T(9) × T(T(T(2)))) + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T(T(5))))
55349 := ((T(T(9)) + T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - (5)))
55359 := ((9 × T(T(5))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + (T(5))))
55384 := ((T(T(T(4))) × T(8)) - C((3+5), 5))
55392 := (T((2+T(9))) + (C((T(3) + T(5)), T(5))))
55435 := (-5) + (C((T(T(3)) - T(4)), 5) × T(T(5)))
55468 := (C(8, 6) + (T(T(T(4))) × T((T(T(5))/T(5))))

- 55539 := $(T(T(9)) + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T(T(5))) + T(T(5))))$
 55642 := $(T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) + C(T(C(6, 5)), T(5)))$
 55648 := $((-T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) + (C(T(6), T(5)) - T(T(5)))$
 55659 := $((T((T(9) + (5))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) + T(T(5)))$
 55692 := $((-C((2 \times 9), 6)) \times T(5)) / (-5)$
 55795 := $((T(T(5)) \times T((9 + C(7, 5)))) - (5))$
 55804 := $(T(T(T(4))) + C((T(08) - T(5)), T(5)))$
 55829 := $((C(9, T(2)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(5))) + (5)$
 55845 := $((C(T(5), 4) \times (T(8) + (5))) - T(T(5)))$
 55847 := $(T(T(7)) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(8))) - C(5, 5)))$
 55849 := $((T(9) + T(T(T(4)))) + C((T(8) - T(5)), T(5)))$
 55869 := $((C(9, 6) \times T(T(8))) + (-5) \times T(5))$
 55875 := $((5 \times 7) \times T(C(8, 5))) + T(5)$
 55924 := $(T(T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), (-9) + T(5))) + (T(T(5))))$
 55937 := $((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times (C(9, 5) + 5))$
 55944 := $(T(T((4 + 4))) \times C(9, (T(5)/5)))$
 56133 := $(3^{T(3)-1}) \times T(T(C(6, 5)))$
 56224 := $(T(4^{T(2)})) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - (T(T(5))))$
 56244 := $((T(44) \times 2) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56259 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(C(5, 2))) - T((T(6) + T(5))))$
 56262 := $((T(2) \times T((6^2))) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56283 := $(T(T(3)) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-T(2))) - (C(T(6), T(5)))))$
 56289 := $((T(C(9, 8))^2) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56292 := $((T(2) + (T(9)^2)) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56294 := $-((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(C(9, T(2))) + (C(T(6), T(5))))))$
 56298 := $((-T(8)) - ((T(T(9)) \times (-2)) - (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56323 := $-(((T(T(3)) - T(2^{T(3)})) - (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56325 := $((T((T(T(5))/2)) + T(T(T(3)))) + (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56328 := $((8 \times T(T(2)))^3 - (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56329 := $((T(T(9)) \times 2) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) - (5)))$
 56342 := $((-2) + T(4^3)) + C(T(6), T(5))$
 56344 := $(T((4 \times (T(4) + T(3)))) + (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56349 := $(T((9 + T(T(4)))) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) + (5)))$
 56355 := $((-T(T(5))) + T(T((5 + T(3)))) + (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56373 := $((T(37) \times 3) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56382 := $((T(2) \times T(T(8))) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) + T(T(5))))$
 56433 := $(T(3) - (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (C(T(6), 5))))$
 56435 := $-((C(T(5), T(3)) + (-4^6) \times T(5)))$
 56472 := $((-T(2)) + T(T((7 + 4)))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56475 := $(T(5) \times ((T(C(7, 4)) \times 6) - T(5)))$
 56542 := $(T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) + (T(5))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56559 := $(T((T(T(9))/T(5))) - ((T(T(5)) - (C(T(6), T(5))))))$
 56574 := $((T(4) \times T(C(7, 5))) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56634 := $((T(4) \times (T(3) + T(T(6)))) + (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56637 := $(C(T(7), 3) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(C(6, 5))))$
 56679 := $(T(((9 \times 7) + 6)) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56739 := $((T(9) \times T((3 + 7))) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56743 := $((-T(3)) + T((T(4) \times 7))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56749 := $(T((-T(9)) + T(T(4))) \times 7) + (C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56756 := $((T(6) \times T(T(5))) - ((T(7) - C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56791 := $((T(19) \times T(T(7))) - (C(T(6), 5)))$
 56824 := $((T(4) \times 2^8) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56864 := $((T((4 + T(6))) \times 8) + (C(T(6), T(5))))$
 56891 := $((-1) + T((9 \times 8))) + C(T(6), T(5))$
 56904 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(T(09))) - T(C(6, 5)))$
 56919 := $((T(T(9)) \times T((1 + 9))) - C(6, 5))$
 56925 := $((T(5)^2) + T(C(9, 6))) \times T(5)$
 56926 := $((T(T(6))^2) + ((T(C(9, 6)) - (5))))$
 56931 := $((T(T((1 + 3))) \times T(T(9))) + C(6, 5))$
 56934 := $((T(T(C(4, 3))) \times T(T(9))) + (-6) + T(5))$
 56936 := $((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(C(9, 6)) + (5))))$
 56943 := $((-3) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))) + T(C(6, 5))))$
 56946 := $((T((6 + 4)) \times T(T(9))) + T(C(6, 5)))$
 56947 := $(T(7) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))) - C(6, 5)))$
 56949 := $((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(9) - T(C(6, 5))))$
 56964 := $((T((4 \times 6)) \times 9) + C(T(6), T(5)))$
 56974 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(7) + 9)) - C(6, 5))$
 56984 := $((-T(T(4))) + T((T(T(8))/9))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))$
 57225 := $((T(T(5) \times T(T(2)))) + (C(-((T(2) - T(7))), 5)))$
 57256 := $(T((6 + C(5, 2))) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(5))))$
 57329 := $(T(T(9)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-5))))$
 57345 := $((C(T(5), 4) \times T(3)) \times 7) + T(5)$
 57365 := $((C(T(5), 6) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(7)))) \times 5)$
 57431 := $((T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times (-4) + T(C(7, 5)))$
 57484 := $(T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-4 \times C(7, 5))))$
 57528 := $(T(8) \times (2 + T(C((T(5) - (7)), 5))))$
 57546 := $((T(T(6)) \times C(T(4), 5)) - T(T((-7) + T(5))))$
 57582 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), 8) / (-5)) + (C(T(7), 5)))$
 57588 := $((T(8) \times (T(C(8, 5)) + (7))) - T(T(5)))$
 57622 := $((-2) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - (-T(7)) \times T(T(5))))$
 57634 := $((T(4) + C(T(T(3)), 6)) + (T(7) \times T(T(5))))$
 57669 := $((T(9) + C(T(6), 6)) + (T(7) \times T(T(5))))$
 57729 := $((T(T(9)) \times (2 \times T(7))) - (T(C(7, 5))))$
 57897 := $((-7) \times (T(9) - (T(8) \times T(C(7, 5))))$

57923 := (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - ((-9) × T(T(7))) - (5))
57933 := (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - ((-9) × T(T(7))) - (T(5)))
57938 := ((C(8, 3) × T(T(9))) - (7 + T(5)))
57958 := ((C(8, 5) × T(T(9))) - (7 - 5))
57969 := (9 × ((6 × T(T(9))) + (T(C(7, 5))))
58184 := ((-4) - T(T((8 + 1)))) × (-C(8, 5))
58212 := (T(21) × C((2 + 8), 5))
58233 := (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(3))) × (-C((2 + 8), 5))))
58236 := ((T(T(6)) - C(T(3), T(2))) × T((8 + T(5))))
58246 := ((C(T(6), T(4))/T(T(2))) - (T(8) × T(5)))
58255 := ((T(T(5)) × C(T(5), T(2))) + (T(85)))
58293 := (-3) - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(2))) × (-C(8, 5)))
58353 := ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(8) × T(T(5))))
58368 := ((T(T(8)) - (T(C(6, 3)))) × (8 + T(T(5))))
58464 := ((T(T(T(4))) - (T((T(6) + T(4)))) × C(8, 5))
58469 := (((C(9, 6) + T(T(T(4)))) × T(8)) + 5)
58539 := ((-T(9)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) - (-T(8) × T(T(5)))
58563 := -(((T(T(3)) - (C(T(6), T(5)))) + (-T(8) × T(T(5))))
58563 := (T(T(5)) - (-C((8 + T(5)), T(6))) × T(T(T(3))))
58629 := (T(T(9)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - (T(T(8)) × (-5)))
58693 := ((C(T(T(3)), 9) - T((-6) + T(8)))/5)
58786 := (C(T(6), ((8 - 7) + 8))/5)
58856 := ((T(T(6)) + T((5 × 8))) × C(8, 5))
58897 := ((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) + (T(8) × T(C(8, 5))))
58914 := ((T(T(4)) - 1) × (T(T(9)) + C(8, 5)))
58923 := -(((T(T(3)) × T(T(2))) - ((C(9, 8)⁵)))
58935 := -((T(T(5)) - (T(3) + (C(9, 8)⁵)))
58938 := ((T(T(8))/(-T(3))) + ((C(9, 8)⁵)))
58944 := -((T((T(4) + 4)) - ((C(9, 8)⁵)))
58949 := ((-T(9)) - T(T(4))) + ((C(9, 8)⁵))
58957 := ((T(7) - T(T(5))) + ((C(9, 8)⁵)))
58958 := -((T((8 + 5)) - (C(9, 8)⁵)))
58983 := -((T((3 + 8)) - (C(9, 8)⁵)))
58993 := ((C(T(T(3)), 9) + T(T(C(9, 8))))/5)
58994 := -(((T(4) + T(9)) - (C(9, 8)⁵)))
58997 := ((-7) - T(9)) + (C(9, 8)⁵)
59214 := (C((T(4) + 1), T(2)) + 9⁵)
59256 := (-C(T(6), T(5))) + (T((-2) + T(9))) × T(T(5)))
59262 := (T(2) + (C(T(6), 2) + 9⁵))
59269 := (C((-9) + T(6), T(2)) + 9⁵)
59275 := ((-5) + T(C(7, 2))) + 9⁵)
59335 := ((T(C(5, 3)) + T(T(T(3)))) + 9⁵)

59427 := (C(T(7), -((2 - 4))) + 9⁵)
59428 := (C(8, 2) + ((T(T(4)) × 9) × T(T(5))))
59535 := (T(5) × (T((T(3) × T(5))) - (C(9, 5))))
59598 := ((8 + T((T(9) - T(5)))) × C(9, 5))
59637 := ((T(C(7, T(3))) × T(6)) + 9⁵)
59662 := ((-2) + C(T(6), 6)) - (-T(9) × T(T(5)))
59664 := (C(T(T(T(-(4 - 6))))), 6) - (-T(9) × T(T(5)))
59676 := (-6) - (T(T(7)) × (-T(6) + (C(9, 5))))
59682 := (T(28) × (T(6) + (C(9, 5))))
59683 := (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(8)) - (C(T(6), 9)/(-5))))
59686 := (T(T(6)) + (T(C(8, 6)) + 9⁵))
59934 := ((T(T(T(4))) × 39) - C(9, 5))
59976 := ((T(6) - T(7)) × (-C((9 + 9), 5)))
60732 := (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - (-T(7) × T(T(06))))
61455 := (T(5) - (T(5) × (-C(4, 1)⁶)))
61473 := (3 × (C(T(7), 4) + 16))
62369 := (((T(9) × T(T(6))) × T(3)) - C(T(T(2)), 6))
62377 := ((-7) - C(T(7), 3)) × (2 - T(6))
62489 := (((T(T(9)) × 8) - T(T(4))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 6))
62532 := (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) + (T(52) × 6))
62657 := -((T(T(7)) - ((C(T(5), T((6 - 2))) × T(6))))
62678 := (((T(T(8)) - C(T(7), 6)) + T(T(2)))/(-6))
62724 := -((T((-T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62727 := ((C(T(7), T(T(2))) - (C(T(7), 2)))/6)
62734 := -((T(T(4)) + ((T(3) - C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6))
62735 := (-T(C(5, 3)) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62739 := (-((T(9) + T(3))) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62745 := (-T((5 + 4)) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62749 := (-((T(9) - 4)) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62755 := ((T((5 + T(5))) - C(T(7), T(T(2))))/(-6))
62757 := (-((T(7) + 5)) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62763 := (-((T(3) + T(6))) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62776 := (-((T(6) - 7)) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62777 := -((T(77) - C((T(7) - 2), T(6))))
62781 := (-((1 + 8)) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62782 := (((T(T(2)) × (-8)) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6)
62783 := ((-((T(3) + T(8))) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6)
62788 := (-8) - ((-T(8)) - C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6)
62789 := (-((9 - 8)) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62791 := ((1⁹) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6)))
62792 := (-((T(2) + 9)) - C(T(7), T(T(2))))/(-6))
62795 := ((-((T(5) - T(9))) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6)

- 62799** := $((9 + T(9)) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6$
62827 := $((C(T(7), T(T(2))) + (T(T(8))/T(2)))/6$
62868 := $((8 + T(T(6))) \times T(8) + C(T(T(2)), 6))$
63345 := $((5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times (C(T(3), 3) + T(6)))$
63385 := $((T(5) - 8)^{T(3)} - C(T(T(3)), 6))$
63459 := $((9^5) + (C(T(4), T(3)) \times T(6)))$
63485 := $((-5) \times (8 - (T(T(C(4, 3))) \times T(T(6))))$
63504 := $(C(T(4), 05) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(6))))$
63524 := $((-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \times (-5) - C(T(3), 6))$
63525 := $((T(C(5, 2))^{5-3} \times T(6))$
63545 := $((-5) \times (-4 - (T(C(5, 3)) \times T(T(6))))$
63546 := $((-T(6)) \times T(T(4))) \times (-T(C(5, 3))) + (T(6)))$
63549 := $(T(9) - (-C(T(4), 5) \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(6))))$
63569 := $((T(T(9) + T(6))) - C((5 + T(T(3))), T(6)))$
63588 := $((T(T(8)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(5)))) - C(T(T(3)), 6))$
63648 := $(8 \times ((-4) + C(T(6), 3)) \times 6)$
63756 := $((-6) \times (C((-5) + T(7)), 3) \times (-6))$
63789 := $(T(T(9)) - (T(8) + (C(T(7), T(3)))/(-6)))$
63797 := $((-T(7)) + T(T(9))) - (C(T(7), T(3)))/(-6))$
63822 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times 8) - 3) \times 6$
63945 := $((C(T(5), T(4)) + T(9)) - 3) \times T(6)$
63948 := $((T(T(8)) + (-T(4)) \times T(T(9)))) - C(T(T(3)), 6))$
63966 := $(C(T(6), 6) - (-T(9) - 3)) \times T(T(6)))$
64225 := $((-C(T(5), T(2))) - (2 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6)))$
64255 := $((-5) + (C((T(5) + T(2)), 4) \times T(6)))$
64281 := $((1 + C((T(8)/2), 4)) \times T(6))$
64295 := $((-C(T(5), 9)) + (T(24) \times T(T(6))))$
64323 := $((3 + C((T(2) \times T(3)), 4)) \times T(6))$
64365 := $((5 + C((6 \times 3), 4)) \times T(6))$
64525 := $(C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times T((T(4) + T(6))))$
64539 := $(T(T(9)) - (T(T(3)) \times (-C(T(5), T(4)) + T(6))))$
64594 := $(T(T(T(4))) - (9 - (C(T(5), T(4)) \times T(6))))$
64735 := $(T(C(5, 3)) + ((T(7) \times T(4)) \times T(T(6))))$
64824 := $((4 \times T((T(2) + C(8, 4)))) \times 6)$
64834 := $((T(43) - C((T(8) - T(4)), T(6))))$
64883 := $((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) - C((T(8) - T(4)), T(6))))$
65085 := $((-T(5)) \times (T(T(8)) - C(T(05), 6)))$
65229 := $((T(9) \times (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + (T(T(5)))) - (T(6)))$
65252 := $((-T(2^5)) + C((T(T(T(2))) + 5), T(6)))$
65338 := $((-8) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) + C(T(5), 6))$
65372 := $((-2) - T(T(7))) + C((T(T(3)) + 5), T(6))$
65374 := $((-T((4 \times 7))) + C((T(T(3)) + 5), T(6)))$
65445 := $((-5) - (-T(4)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + C(T(5), 6)))$
65475 := $((5^7) - C((T(4) + T(5)), T(6)))$
65548 := $(T(C(8, 4)) + (C(T(5), 5) \times T(6)))$
65549 := $(C(((T(9) - 4) - T(5)), 5) - T(T(6)))$
65565 := $((T(6) + T(T(5))) \times T((5 \times C(6, 5))))$
65594 := $(T(T(T(4))) - (-((9^5) - C(T(5), 6)))$
65625 := $((C(5, -((2 - 6))^5) \times T(6))$
65644 := $((T((4 \times 4)) - C((T(6) + 5), T(6)))$
65644 := $(C((T(6) + 5), T(6)) - T((4 \times 4)))$
65649 := $(C(T(6), T(5)) - (-T(6) - T(4))) \times T(T(9)))$
65675 := $((T(5) \times (-7)) + C((T(6) + 5), T(6)))$
65675 := $(C((T(6) + 5), T(6)) + (-7) \times T(5))$
65688 := $(8 \times ((T(C(8, 6)) - T(5)) \times T(6)))$
65690 := $(C((T(6) + 5), T(6)) - (90))$
65696 := $(C((T(6) + 5), T(6)) - (C(9, 6)))$
65699 := $((-9 \times 9) + C((T(6) + 5), T(6)))$
65699 := $(C((T(6) + 5), T(6)) - (9 \times 9))$
65729 := $((T(9) - (C((-2) + T(7)), 5) - (6)))$
65759 := $(C(-((9 - (5 \times 7))), 5) - T(6))$
65765 := $((-T(5)) + C((T(T(T(6)/7))) + 5), T(6))$
65775 := $((-5) + C((T(7) - (7 - 5)), T(6)))$
65786 := $(C(((6 - 8) + T(7)), 5) + (6))$
65795 := $(T(5) + C(-((9 - (7 \times 5))), T(6)))$
65801 := $(C((-10) + T(8)), 5) + T(6)$
65856 := $(T((C(6, 5) \times 8)) \times 56)$
66235 := $(C(T(5), 3) + C(26, T(6)))$
66245 := $(T((T(T(5))/4)) + C(26, T(6)))$
66292 := $((2^9) + C(26, T(6)))$
66584 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times 8) + C((T(5) + 6), 6))$
66738 := $((T(C(8, 3)) - 7) \times (T(6) + T(6)))$
66759 := $((T(9) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(C(7, 6)))) - T(T(6))$
66786 := $((6 \times T(T(8))) - (C(T(7), 6)/(-6)))$
66918 := $((T(T(8)) \times 19) + (C(T(6), 6)))$
67248 := $(8 \times (-C(T(4), T(2))) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(6))))$
67255 := $((T(T(5)) - (T(C(5, 2)) \times T((T(7) + T(6))))$
67655 := $((-5) \times (-C(T(5), 6)) + (T(T(7)) \times (-T(6))))$
67823 := $((T(T(3)) - C(T(T(T(2))), 8)) \times (-7))/T(6)$
67825 := $((-5) + ((C(T(T(T(2))), 8) \times 7)/T(6)))$
67872 := $((-2) + T(T(7))) \times (C(8, 7) \times T(6))$
68235 := $((-T(5)) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6))$
68252 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - (-2 - (T(T(8)) \times T(6))))$
68253 := $((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T(2)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68256 &:= ((C(T(6), T(5)) + T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6))) \\
 68256 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(8))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 6)) \\
 68265 &:= (-T(5)) \times (-((T(C(6, 2)) \times T(8))) - T(T(6))) \\
 68355 &:= ((T(5) + T((C(5, 3) \times 8))) \times T(6)) \\
 68376 &:= (((6 \times T(T(7))) + (T(3))) \times C(8, 6)) \\
 68523 &:= ((C((T(3) \times T(2)), 5) \times 8) - T(6)) \\
 68648 &:= (8 \times (T(T(4)) + (T(6) \times T(C(8, 6)))) \\
 68733 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (-3) + C(T(7), T((8 - 6)))) \\
 68894 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) - T(C(8, (8 - 6)))) \\
 69258 &:= (-T(8) - ((T(T(C(5, 2))) \times (-T(9))) + (6))) \\
 69299 &:= (-C(9, 9) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))))) \\
 69328 &:= (C(8, 2) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))))) \\
 69351 &:= (((1 + T(T(C(5, 3)))) \times T(9)) + (6)) \\
 69384 &:= ((T((4 + T(8))) + (T(3))) \times C(9, 6)) \\
 69468 &:= (C(8, 6) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(9)) + (6))) \\
 69552 &:= (C((2 \times 5), 5) \times (T(9) + T(T(6)))) \\
 69597 &:= (T((T(7) + 9)) \times (T(5) + (C(9, 6)))) \\
 69624 &:= ((T(T(C(4, T(2)))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(9)))) - 6) \\
 69936 &:= (-C(T(6), T(3)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T((9 + 6)))))) \\
 71435 &:= (C(T(5), 3) \times (4 + T(17))) \\
 71456 &:= ((T(T(C(6, 5))) - T(T(4))) \times T(T((1 \times 7)))) \\
 71589 &:= ((T(9) \times T(C(8, 5))) - T(T(-(1 - 7)))) \\
 71848 &:= ((T(C(8, 4)) + (81)) \times T(7)) \\
 71928 &:= ((T(8) \times T(2)) \times T(C(C(9, 1), 7))) \\
 72072 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times C((7 \times 02), 7)) \\
 72248 &:= (C((T(8) - T(4)), T(T(T(2)))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(7)))) \\
 72325 &:= ((-T(5) + C(T(T(T(2))), 3)) \times T((T(2) + (7)))) \\
 72345 &:= (C(T(5), 4) \times (-3) + (2 \times T(7))) \\
 72352 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))/3) \times (-T(2) - (7))) \\
 72356 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(2) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))))/T(6)) \\
 72358 &:= (C((8 + 5), 3) \times T(-(T(T(2)) - T(7)))) \\
 72445 &:= (-5) + ((T(4) \times T(C(T(4), 2))) \times 7) \\
 72738 &:= (T(T(8)) + (T(T(3)) \times C((7 \times 2), 7))) \\
 72893 &:= (((T(3) \times T(C(9, 8)))^2) - (7)) \\
 73122 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times T(T((1 + 3)))) - (T(7))) \\
 73227 &:= (C(7, 2) \times (T(T((2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(7)))) \\
 73234 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times C(T(T(3)), T(2))) - (-3) \times T(7)) \\
 73269 &:= (9 \times (T(6) + (C(T(T(2)), 3) \times T(T(7)))) \\
 73334 &:= -((T(T(T(4) + 3))) - (C(C(T(3), 3), 7))) \\
 73535 &:= ((C(T(5), T(3)) \times T(5)) - T(T((3 + 7)))) \\
 73584 &:= (T((4 \times (8 + C(5, 3)))) \times T(7)) \\
 73976 &:= (-((T(6) \times (T(7) - T(C(9, 3)))) - T(T(7))) \\
 74228 &:= ((C((T(8)/2), T(T(2))) \times 4) - T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74229 &:= ((T(C(9, T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - (T((T(4) + T(7)))) \\
 74263 &:= ((C((3 \times 6), T(T(2))) \times 4) + (7)) \\
 74284 &:= ((C((T(4) + 8), T(T(2))) \times 4) + T(7)) \\
 74313 &:= (C((T(T(3)) + 1), T(3)) - T((-4) + T(7))) \\
 74333 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), 3) + T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + T(7)) \\
 74382 &:= (C((-2) \times T(8)) / (-3), 4) \times 7) \\
 74438 &:= ((8 + C((T(3) \times 4), 4)) \times 7) \\
 74439 &:= -((T(T((9 + 3))) - (C((T(4) + T(4)), 7)))) \\
 74589 &:= ((-9) + T(C(8, 5))) \times 47) \\
 74613 &:= (C((T(T(3)) + 1), T((6 + 4) - 7))) \\
 74616 &:= (C((T(6) + 1), 6) - ((4 - 7))) \\
 74631 &:= (C((1 + T(T(3))), 6) - ((T(4) - T(7)))) \\
 74637 &:= ((C((T(7) - T(3)), 6) - (4)) + T(7)) \\
 74655 &:= (T(5) \times (C(T(5), 6) - ((4 \times 7)))) \\
 74656 &:= ((T((-T(6) + T(T(5)))) \times C(6, 4)) + (T(T(7)))) \\
 74661 &:= ((C((1 + T(6)), 6) + T(T(4))) - (7)) \\
 74662 &:= ((C((T(2) \times 6), 6) \times 4) + T(T(7))) \\
 74675 &:= ((C((T(5) + 7), 6) + T(T(4))) + (7)) \\
 74676 &:= (T(6) \times ((7 + T(C(6, 4))) \times T(7))) \\
 74732 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) + ((C(T(7), 4) - (7)))) \\
 74755 &:= (-5) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(C(7, 4)) - (7))) \\
 74844 &:= (T((4 + 4)) \times (T(C(8, 4)) - T(T(7)))) \\
 74955 &:= ((T(5) \times C(T(5), 9)) - C(T(4), 7)) \\
 74965 &:= (-5) + (T(6) \times T(C(9, -(4 - 7)))) \\
 75247 &:= (((T(C(7, 4)) - T(2)) \times T(T(5))) + (7)) \\
 75255 &:= (T(5) \times (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (5 + 7))) \\
 75292 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (T(C(9, T(2))) + (T(5)))) + 7) \\
 75371 &:= ((1 + C(T(7), 3)) \times (-5) + T(7)) \\
 75373 &:= (-3) + ((C(T(7), T(3))/5) + T(7)) \\
 75374 &:= (((T(4) - C(T(7), T(3))) / (-5)) + T(7)) \\
 75375 &:= (((-5) + C(T(7), T(3))) / 5) + T(7)) \\
 75376 &:= ((C((T(6) + 7), T(3)) / 5) + T(7)) \\
 75554 &:= (C((4 + T(5)), (T(T(5)) / T(5))) - T(7)) \\
 75556 &:= (T(T(7)) + (T(5) \times (5 + C(T(5), 6)))) \\
 75574 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(7)) - (C((5 + T(5)), 7)))))) \\
 75582 &:= (C(((T(2) \times 8) - (5)), (T(5) - (7))) \\
 75599 &:= (-C(9, 9)) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T((5 \times 7)))) \\
 75628 &:= (C(8, 2) \times T((T((6 + 5)) + (7)))) \\
 75645 &:= ((T(7) + (C(T(5), 6) + T(4))) \times T(5)) \\
 75648 &:= (C((7 + T(5)), 6) + T(C(T(4), 8))) \\
 75669 &:= ((C((7 + T(5)), 6) + T(6)) + T(T(9))) \\
 75694 &:= (C((7 + T(5)), 6) + T((-9) + T(T(4)))) \\
 75699 &:= -((T(T(9)) - ((9 \times T(C(6, 5))) \times T(T(7))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 75888** := $(T(8) \times (T((8 + C(8, 5))) + T(7)))$
75925 := $(T(T(C(5, 2))) + (T(9) \times T(57)))$
75988 := $(T(T(7)) + C((T(T(-(5 - 9)))) - T(8)), 8)$
76048 := $((T(C(8, 4)) + T(T(06))) \times T(7))$
76142 := $-((T((-T(2)) + T(T(4)))) - (C((-1) + T(6)), 7)))$
76188 := $-((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) - C((-1) + T(6)), 7))$
76225 := $(-5) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times C((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6)), 7))$
76425 := $(-T(5)) + (T(C(T(T(2))), 4) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))))$
76435 := $(-5) + (T(C(T(3), 4)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))))$
76446 := $-((C(T(6), (4 + 4)) - (6^7)))$
76587 := $((7 \times T(C(8, 5))) - T(T(6))) \times 7$
77114 := $(C((T(4) \times (1 + 1)), 7) - T(T(7)))$
77124 := $(T(4) + (C((T(T(T(2))) - 1), 7) - (T(T(7))))$
77294 := $((T(-(T(4) - C(9, T(2)))) \times T(7)) - (T(T(7))))$
77428 := $((T(T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(4), 7) + (T(7)))$
77448 := $((T(T(8)) - C((T(4) + (4)), 7)) \times (-T(7)))$
77462 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), 6) \times (-T(4))) + (T(T(7))))/(-7)$
77492 := $(C((2 \times (-T(9)) + T(T(4))), 7) - T(7))$
77515 := $(-5) + C((-1) + T(T(T(-(5 - 7))))), 7)$
77535 := $(T(5) + C((-((3 + 5)) + T(7)), 7))$
77542 := $-((T(T(2)) - C((4 \times 5), 7) + T(7)))$
77544 := $(-((4 - C((4 \times 5), 7))) + T(7))$
77548 := $(C(((8 - 4) \times 5), 7) + T(7))$
77616 := $(C((T(6) + 1), 6) + T(7))$
77716 := $(C((T(6) - 1), 7) - (-7 \times T(7)))$
77835 := $((T(5) \times T(T(3))) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7))$
77845 := $(T((T(5) + T(4))) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7))$
77889 := $((T(T(9)) - T(T(8))) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7))$
77898 := $(T((T(8) - 9)) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7))$
77926 := $(C(C(6, -(T(T(2)) - 9)), 7) + (T(T(7))))$
78421 := $((-1) + T(C(T(T(2))), 4)) \times (T(T(8)) - (7))$
78456 := $(-T(6)) \times ((-C(5, 4) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(7)))$
78562 := $(-T(7)) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(5))) - C(T(6), T(2)))$
78726 := $(-6) + ((T(2)^7) \times T(C(8, 7)))$
78731 := $(-1) - (-((3^7) \times T(C(8, 7)))$
78732 := $((-((T(2) - T(3))^7) \times T(C(8, 7)))$
78795 := $(C((T(7) - 8), 7) + T((T(9) + (5))))$
78795 := $(T((5 + T(9))) + C((T(7) - 8), 7))$
79244 := $((T((T(T(4)) + C(4, T(2)))) \times T(9)) - (T(T(7))))$
79248 := $(8 \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(2))) + T(C(9, 7))))$
79252 := $(-T(2)) + (T(C(5, 2)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7))))$
79254 := $((-4) + T(T(5))) + T(2) \times T(C(9, 7))$
79255 := $(T(C(5, (5 - 2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7))))$
79452 := $((T(T((T(T(2)) + (5)))) - 4) \times C(9, 7))$
79455 := $(T(5) + (T(T(5)) \times (-4) + T(C(9, 7))))$
79548 := $((T((C(8, 4) + 5)) - 9) \times T(7))$
79625 := $(-C(T(5), T(2))) \times (T(T(T(-(6 - 9)))) - (T(T(7))))$
79674 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (C(7, 6) + T(9))) - (T(T(7))))$
79765 := $((C((-5) + T(6)), 7) - T(9)) \times 7$
79828 := $(T(8) - C((2 \times 8), 9)) \times (-7)$
79935 := $(T(5) + (T((T(3) + 9)) \times T(C(9, 7))))$
79948 := $((T(T(8)) \times T(T((4 + C(9, 9)))) + T(7))$
79975 := $((T(5) - C((7 + 9), 9)) \times (-7))$
81364 := $(4 \times (C(T(6), (T(3) - 1)) - 8))$
82278 := $((T(T(8)) - (C(T(7), 2))^2) - T(T(8)))$
82368 := $((C((-8) + T(6)), T(3)) \times T(T(2))) \times 8$
82425 := $(-T(5)) + (T(C(T(T(2))), 4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8))))$
82435 := $(-5) - (-T(C(T(3), 4)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8))))$
82455 := $(T(5) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(C(4, 2))) - T(T(8))))$
82494 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times (9 \times C(4, 2))) - (T(T(8))))$
82594 := $(T(4) - (-((C(9, 5) - 2) \times T(T(8))))$
82678 := $(T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-C(T(6), 2) - 8)))$
82782 := $(T(-((2 - 8))) \times (C(T(7), T(2)) + T(T(8))))$
83556 := $((T(6) + (C((5 \times 5), 3))) \times T(8))$
83622 := $(T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(2) \times C(T(6), 3)) - 8))$
83684 := $((T((T(T(4)) + T(8))) \times C(6, 3)) - T(8))$
83768 := $(8 \times (6 + (C(T(7), T(3))/T(8))))$
83772 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 7) + (T((7 \times T(3))) \times (-T(8))))$
83859 := $((C(9, 5) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(3))) - T(8)$
83916 := $((6 + C((1 + 9), 3)) \times T(T(8)))$
84254 := $((4 + T(T(C(5, 2)))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(8))$
84384 := $((T(C(T(4), 8)) - T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)$
84525 := $(C(T(5), 2) \times (-T(5)) + T((4 + T(8))))$
84535 := $(T(C(5, 3)) \times ((5 + T(T(T(4)))) - 8))$
84546 := $(T(T(6)) \times (C((-4) + T(5)), 4) + T(8))$
84576 := $(-6) - ((-7) - T(T(C(5, 4)))) \times T(T(8))$
84732 := $((T(C(T(T(2))), 3)) \times T(T(7))) - T((4 \times 8))$
84925 := $(C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T(T((9 - 4))) \times T(T(8))))$
84979 := $((T(T(9)) + T(7)) - (-C(9, 4) \times T(T(8))))$
85184 := $((C(T(4), 8) - 1)^{-5+8})$
85237 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(C(T(3), T(2)))) - (T(5) + 8))$
85525 := $(C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T(T(5)) \times (5 + T(T(8))))$
85635 := $(T(C(5, 3)) \times (T(T(6)) + T((T(5) + T(8))))$
85672 := $(-8) + (T((-5) + T(6))) \times T(C(7, T(2)))$

85697 := ((T(8) + C(T(5), 6)) × (T(9) – T(7)))
85914 := (((4 – 1) + C(9, 5)) × T(T(8)))
85924 := (T(4) – (–((T(2) + C(9, 5)))) × T(T(8)))
86292 := ((T((2 × C(9, 2))) – T(T(6))) × T(8))
86598 := (T(8) – (–(C(9, 5)) × (T(6) + T(T(8))))))
86855 := ((C(T(5), 5) – 8) × (T(6) + 8))
86969 := ((C(9, 6) × T(T(9))) + (T(6) + 8))
87216 := (6 × (1 – (C(T(T(T(2))), 7)/(-8))))
87222 := (T(T(2)) × (2 – (C(T(T(T(2))), 7)/(-8))))
87225 := (T(5) – (T(T(2)) × (C(T(T(T(2))), 7)/(-8))))
87298 := ((C((8 + 9), T(T(2))) × 7) + T(T(8)))
87336 := (6 × (T(T(3)) + (C(T(T(3)), 7)/8))
87534 := (((C(T(4), T(3)) × T(5)) × T(7)) – T(T(8)))
87668 := (–(C(8, 6)) – ((6 × T(T(7))) × (–T(8))))
88438 := (((T(C(8, 3)) × T(T(4))) – 8) + T(T(8)))
88462 := (C((–2) + T(6)), T(4)) – T(88))
88794 := ((T((C(T(4), 9) × 7)) × T(8)) – T(T(8)))
89268 := (–(86) × (–(T(2)) – T(T(C(9, 8))))))
89475 := (T(5) – (T((T(C(7, 4)/9)) × (–T(8))))
89592 := (T(T(2)) – (–(C(9, 5)) × (T(9) + T(T(8))))))
89635 := (C(T(5), 3) × ((T(6) × 9) + 8))
89655 := (–((T(T(5)) – ((T(5) × C(T(6), (9 + 8))))))
89667 := ((T(7) – C(6, 6)) × T((T(9) + T(8))))
89685 := ((T(T(5)) × (T(8) × T(6))) – T(T(C(9, 8))))
89775 := (T(5) × C((–7) + T(7)), (9 + 8))
89856 := ((6 – (T(5) × T(T(8)))) × (–C(9, 8)))
91568 := (8 × (6 + C((T(5) + 1), 9)))
91727 := ((C(T(7), T(2)) × T(7)) – (1⁹))
91737 := ((C(T(7), 3) × T(7)) + (1 × 9))
91756 := ((T(T(6)) – (5)) × T(T(C(7, (1⁹))))))
92225 := (–(T((T(5) + 2))) + C((T(T(T(2))) – 2), 9))
92242 := (–(T((2⁴))) + C((T(T(T(2))) – 2), 9))
92252 := (–((T(T(2)) + T(T(5)))) + C((T(T(T(2))) – 2), 9))
92254 := ((–(4) – T(T(5))) + C((T(T(T(2))) – 2), 9))
92258 := ((–(8) × T(5)) + C((T(T(T(2))) – 2), 9))
92273 := (–((T((T(T(3)) – (7))) – C((T(T(T(2))) – 2), 9)))
92323 := (–((T(T((T(3) – 2))) – C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9)))
92333 := (–(T((3 × 3))) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92336 := ((–(T(6)) – T(T(3))) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92339 := (–((T(9) – T(3))) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92342 := (–(T((2 × 4))) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92352 := (–((T(T(T(2))) + (5 – C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))))

92355 := (((T(T(5)) × T(T(C(5, 3))))/2) – (T(9)))
92357 := (–(C(7, 5)) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92363 := ((T(3) – T(6)) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92366 := (–((6 + 6)) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92369 := (–(9) + C((T(6) – (T(3)/T(2))), 9))
92371 := (–((1 × 7)) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92372 := (–((T(T(2)) – C(((7 × 3) – 2), 9)))
92375 := (–((T(–((5 – 7))) – C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9)))
92377 := (–(C(7, 7)) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92378 := C(((–8) + T(7)) – (3 – 2), 9)
92383 := (–((3 – 8)) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92384 := (T(T((T(4) – 8))) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92393 := ((T(3) + 9) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92397 := ((T(7) – 9) + C((T(T(3)) – 2), 9))
92423 := ((C(C(T(3), T(2)), T(4))/2) + T(9))
92426 := ((C((T(6) – 2), T(4)) + T(2)) + T(9))
92432 := (C((–2) + T(T(3))), T(4)) + (T(T(2)) × 9))
92577 := ((T(T(7)) × (T(C(7, 5)) – T(2))) + 9)
92631 := (T((1 + T(T(3)))) + C((T(6) – 2), 9))
92664 := ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) + C((T(6) – 2), 9))
92745 := ((T((T(5) × 4)) + T(C(7, 2))) × T(9))
92751 := ((T(T((1 + 5))) × T(T(C(7, T(T(2)))))) – T(T(9)))
92757 := (((T(C(7, 5)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(2))) – T(T(9)))
92772 := (T(T(T(2))) – ((T(T(7)) × (–T(C(7, 2)))) + T(T(9))))
92997 := ((T(7) × T((T(9) + C(9, 2)))) + 9)
93285 := ((T(T(5)) + T((C(8, T(2)) + T(3)))) × T(9))
93288 := (–((T(8) + C(8, T(2)))) × (T(T(3)) – T(T(9))))
93435 := ((T(T(C(5, 3))) × (T(4) × T(3))) + T(T(9)))
93599 := (–(C(9, 9)) + (T(T(5)) × T(39)))
93776 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) – C((7 + 3), 9))
93831 := (((–1) × T(T(T(3)))) × (–T(C(8, T(3)))) + T(9))
94269 := (C(9, 6) + (T((T(2) + T(4))) × T(T(9))))
94489 := (–((9 – C(8, 4)) × (T(T(T(4))) + 9))
94584 := (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(8)) + C((T(5) + (4)), 9))))
94599 := ((9 × C((9 + T(5)), 4)) – T(T(9)))
94776 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) + T((C(7, 4) + 9)))
94824 := (4 × (C((T(T(T(2))) + 8), 4) – T(9)))
94867 := ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) + T((T(8) + C(T(4), 9))))
95256 := (–((C(9, 5)²) × (T(5) – T(6)))
95326 := (T(T(6)) – ((–2) + T(T(3))) × (–C(T(5), 9)))
95634 := ((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) × (C(6, 5) × 9))
95634 := (9 × C((T(5) + (6 + 3)), 4))
95725 := (T(T(C(5, 2))) + (T((T(7) – T(5))) × T(T(9))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 95856 &:= -(((T(9) - C(T(5), 8)) \times T(5)) - (6)) \\
 95859 &:= -(((T(9) - C(T(5), 8)) \times T(5)) - 9) \\
 95886 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(8))) + (-C(8, 5) \times T(T(9)))) \\
 96465 &:= (-T(5) - (T(C(6, 4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\
 96535 &:= (T(C(5, 3)) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))) \\
 96756 &:= (T(T(6)) - (C(T(5), 7) \times (-6 + 9))) \\
 96768 &:= ((8 \times 6) \times T((C(7, 6) \times 9))) \\
 96936 &:= (T(T(6)) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(C(9, 6))) - T(T(9)))) \\
 97217 &:= (C(T(7), (-1) + T(T(2))) - (T(7) + T(T(9)))) \\
 97236 &:= ((C(T(6), 3) + 2) \times (T(7) + T(9))) \\
 97257 &:= (((T(C(7, 5)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(9))) \\
 97328 &:= (C(8, T(2)) \times (T(37) + T(T(9)))) \\
 97422 &:= (2 \times ((T(C(T(T(2)), 4)) \times T(T(7))) - 9)) \\
 97465 &:= (5 \times (C((T(6) - 4), 7) + T(9))) \\
 97555 &:= ((-5) + (T(5) \times C(T(5), 7))) + T(T(9))) \\
 97577 &:= (C(T(7), (T(7) - 5))) - T((T(7) + 9)) \\
 97657 &:= (((C(T(7), 5) + 6) + T(T(7))) - T(T(9))) \\
 97749 &:= (((C(9, 4) \times T(7)) \times T(7)) - T(T(9))) \\
 97825 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times ((8 \times T(7)) - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97846 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(C(8, -(7 - 9)))) \\
 97857 &:= (((C(T(7), 5) - 8) - T(T(7))) - 9) \\
 98127 &:= (C(T(7), (T(T(2)) - 1)) - T((8 + 9))) \\
 98227 &:= (C(T(7), (2 + T(2))) - (8 + T(9))) \\
 98256 &:= -(((T(9) - (C(C(8, 2), 5))) - T(6))) \\
 98257 &:= ((C(T(7), 5) - T(T(2))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 98271 &:= (C(T((1 \times 7)), -(T(2) - 8)) - 9) \\
 98275 &:= (-5) + C(T(7), (T(T(2)) + ((8 - 9)))) \\
 98317 &:= (C(T(7), (-1) + T(3)) - (8 - T(9))) \\
 98325 &:= (C(T((5 + 2)), -(3 - 8)) + T(9)) \\
 98357 &:= ((C(T(7), 5) + 3) - (T(T(8)) / (-9))) \\
 98556 &:= (T(9) + (C(T((-8) + T(5)), 5) + T(T(6)))) \\
 98637 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(C(T(6), -(8 - 9)))) \\
 98857 &:= ((C(T(7), 5) + T(T(8))) - (89)) \\
 99245 &:= ((T(5)^4) + C((2 \times 9), 9)) \\
 99492 &:= (-T(2) + (T(9) \times T(T((T(4) + C(9, 9)))))) \\
 99784 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (T(8) - C(T(7), (T(9)/9)))) \\
 99954 &:= (((T(4)^5) - T(9)) - C(9, 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4]. Friedmann [6, 7] also made some study in this direction. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Following subsections give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers are with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **Quadratic numbers**, **Cubic numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of **permutable powers**, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

4.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &:= 1^1 & 2173 &:= -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7 \\
 23 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 & 2537 &:= 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 \\
 1239 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & 3125 &:= -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5 \\
 1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 & 3275 &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 \\
 1654 &:= -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 & 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 \\
 1837 &:= 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 & 3529 &:= -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2 \\
 2137 &:= -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2 & 4316 &:= 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4355 &:= 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5 & 423858 &:= 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5 \\ 39339 &:= -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3 & 637395 &:= 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7 \\ 46350 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4 & 758014 &:= 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8 \\ 46360 &:= 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6 & 778530 &:= 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8 \\ 397612 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 & 804637 &:= 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15647982 &:= 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6 \\ 17946238 &:= 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7 \\ 57396108 &:= -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8 \\ 134287690 &:= 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 \\ 387945261 &:= 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5 \\ 392876054 &:= 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\ 392876540 &:= -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [20].

4.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$$\begin{aligned} 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5-2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\ 14641 &:= (1+4+6)^4 \times 1 &= (1+4+6)^4 \times 1 \\ 15552 &:= (1^5+5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5+5) \times 1 \\ 16377 &:= (1+6-3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7-3)^{6+1} \\ 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8-2)^{3+3}/2 \\ 116565 &:= (-1+16) \times (-5+6^5) &= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\ 131072 &:= (1+3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\ 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\ 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\ 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\ 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned} 656250 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 0 = 0 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656251 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 1 = 1 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656252 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 2 = 2 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656253 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 3 = 3 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656254 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 4 = 4 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656255 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 5 = 5 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 6 = 6 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 7 = 7 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 8 = 8 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2+5) + 9 = 9 + (5+2) \times 6 \times 5^6.\end{aligned}$$

The past work up to 6 digits numbers can be seen in [14, 15, 16, 30].

4.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!\end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned}35280 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35281 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35282 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35283 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35284 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35285 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35286 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35287 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35288 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\35289 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!.\end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

4.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$	$1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$
$19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$	$1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9}+2-1}$
$19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$	$2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$
$19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$	$3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$
$839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$	$9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$
$839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$	$12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$
$839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$	$19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$
$839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$	$42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$
$995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$	$59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$
$999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$	$999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$
$999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [14, 15].

4.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse

$936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6!$	$= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}}$
$1296 := \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6}$	$= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)}$
$2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!)$	$= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2$
$331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}}$	$= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3$
$342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$	$= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3$
$759375 := (-7 + 59 - 37)^5$	$= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7}$
$759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1$	$= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7$

$5040 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$
$5041 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$
$5042 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$
$5043 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$
$5044 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$
$5045 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$
$5046 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$
$5047 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$
$5048 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$

$$5049 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0)!$	$25 := 5^2$
$127 := -1 + 2^7$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3$	$289 := (9 + 8)^2$
$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9}$	$3894 := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3$
$1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!}$	$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4!$
$38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70$	$6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6!$
$38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6}$	$26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3$
$40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10$	$30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92)$
$90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!!)/4$	$54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6$
$91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!)$	$75989 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!!) + 5^7$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [14, 15, 16].

4.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$143 := -1 + F(4 \times 3)$	$= F(3 \times 4) - 1$
$986 := F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6))$	$= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9)$
$1178 := F(11) \times F(7) + F(8)$	$= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11)$
$2585 := F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5)$	$= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2)$
$12819 := 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9)$	$= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1$
$24297 := F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7)$	$= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2)$
$39394 := -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)}$	$= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3$
$74997 := -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7)$	$= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7$
$87937 := -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7)$	$= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8$
$98703 := 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03))$	$= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9$

$34 := F(3 \times F(4))$	$36 := 6^{F(3)}$
$233 := F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3))$	$143 := F(3 \times 4) - 1$
$630 := F(F(6)) \times 30$	$231 := F(13) - 2$
$1178 := F(11) \times F(7) + F(8)$	$377 := F(-7 + 7 \times 3)$
$2079 := (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9$	$986 := (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9)$
$4864 := F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))$	$1165 := 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1))$
$8759 := -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8))$	$1596 := F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1)))$
$8849 := -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8))$	$2592 := F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2))$
$9349 := -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9)))$	$9756 := F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 834660 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834661 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834662 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834663 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834664 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834665 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834666 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834667 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834668 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834669 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21960 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21961 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21962 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21963 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21964 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21965 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21966 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21967 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21968 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21969 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2.
 \end{aligned}$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [23, 24].

4.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{1069} := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) & \mathbf{874} := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8) \\
 \mathbf{1081} := T(1 + T(08 + 1)) & \mathbf{0105} := 50 + T(10) \\
 \mathbf{2887} := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7) & \mathbf{1155} := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{4965} := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) & \mathbf{1224} := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{4999} := 49 + T(99) & \mathbf{2418} := T(81) - T(42) \\
 \mathbf{99545} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5 & \mathbf{99632} := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{99546} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6. & \mathbf{99633} := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \mathbf{2210} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2211} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2212} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2213} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2214} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2215} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2216} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2217} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2218} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2219} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))).
 \end{array}$$

For more details see author's work [21, 31].

4.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m - r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways**, **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{6435} := C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\
 \mathbf{15504} := C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{42504} := C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\
 \mathbf{54264} := C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\
 \mathbf{74613} := C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!).
 \end{array}$$

$$12650 := C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!)$$

$$12870 := C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!)$$

$$14950 := C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!)$$

$$18564 := C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!)$$

$$19448 := C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8)$$

$$26334 := C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$43758 := C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8)$$

$$53130 := C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!).$$

$$28 := C(8, 2)$$

$$792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7)$$

$$924 := C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$2024 := C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!)$$

$$4845 := C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4)$$

$$00378 := C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!)$$

$$00792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!)$$

$$00924 := C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)).$$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$$25920 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0$$

$$25921 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1$$

$$25922 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2$$

$$25923 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3$$

$$25924 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4$$

$$25925 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5$$

$$25926 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6$$

$$25927 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7$$

$$25928 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8$$

$$25929 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9.$$

$$98280 := 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98281 := 1 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98282 := 2 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98283 := 3 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98284 := 4 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98285 := 5 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98286 := 6 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98287 := 7 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98288 := 8 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$98289 := 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}).$$

For more details refer author's work [22].

4.9 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\
 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\
 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\
 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\
 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\
 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\
 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\
 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}. & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 86640 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0 & 5640 &:= 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86641 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1 & 5641 &:= 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86642 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2 & 5642 &:= 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86643 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3 & 5643 &:= 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86644 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4 & 5644 &:= 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86645 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 & 5645 &:= 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86646 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6 & 5646 &:= 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86647 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7 & 5647 &:= 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86648 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8 & 5648 &:= 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86649 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9. & 5649 &:= 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

4.10 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{t n(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$2883 := K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3$$

$$2888 := K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8$$

$$3640 := K(3!, 6) \times 40$$

$$14939 := -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9$$

$$14959 := (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9$$

$$15144 := K(15, (-1 + 4!)) \times 4!$$

$$15347 := (-1 + 5!) \times 3!! - K(4!, 7)$$

$$15399 := K(1 \times 5! / 3!, 9) \times 9$$

$$00938 := K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!)$$

$$01051 := K(15, 010)$$

$$01199 := K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10)$$

$$59938 := K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5$$

$$62424 := 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6)$$

$$63384 := 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6!$$

$$63744 := 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!)$$

$$63973 := K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6).$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$99360 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99361 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99362 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99363 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99364 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99365 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99366 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99367 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99368 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99369 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

4.11 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inverse order of digits**:

$48 := -Q(4) + Q(8)$	$49 := Q(-9 + Q(4))$
$81 := Q(8 + 1)$	$89 := Q(9) + 8$
$128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$	$224 := (Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2))$
$292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$	$275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$
$322 := Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$	$736 := Q(Q(6) - Q(3)) + 7$
$1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$	$0107 := 7 + Q(010)$
$1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$	$0231 := -Q(13) + Q(20)$
$1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$	$1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$
$9843 := (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$	$2239 := -Q(9) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2))$
$10025 := 100^2 + Q(5)$	$08136 := Q(6) + Q(Q(3) + 1 + 80)$
$10384 := (-1 + Q(Q(03))) \times 8 \times Q(4)$	$99712 := Q(Q(2)) \times 1 \times (Q(79) - 9)$
$99378 := 9 \times (Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8$	$37293 := -3 + (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3).$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 12680 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12681 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12682 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12683 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12684 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12685 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12686 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12687 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12688 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12689 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

4.12 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **cubic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$125 := 1^2 \times C(5)$	$512 := C(2 + 1 + 5)$
$522 := 5 \times 2 + C(C(2))$	$991 := (C(1 + 9) - 9)$
$991 := -9 + C(9 + 1)$	$0235 := 5 \times (C(3) + 20)$
$1371 := (1 + 3) \times C(7) - 1$	$0263 := C(3) + C(6) + 20$
$1715 := 1 \times C(7) \times 1 \times 5$	$1735 := 5 \times (3 + C(7) + 1)$
$2587 := -C(2) + 5 \times (C(8) + 7)$	$5974 := -4 + 7 \times (C(9) + C(5))$
$9945 := C(9) + 9 \times 4^5$	$00157 := -C(7) + 5 \times 100$
$10125 := (10 - 1)^2 \times C(5)$	$01928 := 8 \times (C(C(2)) + C(9) - C(10))$
$16444 := C(16) \times 4 + C(4) - 4$	$45194 := -4 + C(9) \times (1 + C(5) - C(4))$
$30375 := C(30) + C(3 + 7 + 5)$	$99535 := 5 \times (C(C(3)) + C(5) + 99)$
$99873 := C(9) \times (9 + C(8)/(7 - 3))$	

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 22950 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22951 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22952 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22953 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22954 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22955 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22956 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22957 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22958 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22959 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 4.1. The notation $C(., .)$ in two variables represent **binomial coefficients**, while the $C(.)$ in single variable represent **cubic numbers**.

For more details refer author's work [25].

Acknowledgements

The author is thankful to T.J. Eckman, Georgia, USA (email: jeek@jeek.net) in programming the script to develop these representations.

References

- [1] **J. BARTON**, Centered Polygonal Numbers, <http://www.virtuescience.com/centered-polygonal.html>.
- [2] **C. ROSE**, Radical Narcissistic numbers, *J. Recreational Mathematics*, **33**, (2004-2005), pp. 250-254.
- [3] **C. ROSE**, Pretty Wild Narcissistic numbers, The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, founded by N.J.A. Sloane, <https://oeis.org/A193069>, August 08, 2011.

- [4] **C. ROSE**, Pretty Wild Narcissistic numbers, <http://www.tri.org.au/numQ/pwn/>.
- [5] **H.E. DUDENEY**, Amusements in Mathematics, EBD E-Books Directory.com, 1917.
- [6] **E. FREIDMAN**, Math Magic Archive, <http://bit.ly/2wp7HWS>.
- [7] **E. FREIDMAN**, Math Magic Numbers Archive, <http://bit.ly/2Tzbo5Q>.
- [8] **H. HEINZ**, Number Patterns, <http://www.magic-squares.net>.
- [9] **R. KNOTT**, Polygonal Numbers, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Figurate/figurate.html>.
- [10] **R. KNOTT**, The Mathematical Magic of the Fibonacci Numbers, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Fibonacci/fibmaths.html>
- [11] **J.S. MADACHY**, Mathematics on Vacations, Charlars Scriber's Son, New York, 1966.
- [12] **WOLFRAM MATH WORLD**, Polygonal Numbers, <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/PolygonalNumber.html>.
- [13] **WOLFRAM MATH WORLD**, Centered Polygonal Numbers, <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/CenteredPolygonalNumber.html>.
- [14] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - I: Symmetrical and Unified Representations, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 174, pp.1-94. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a174.pdf>.
- [15] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers - V: Six Digits Symmetrical Representations with Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 164, pp.1-60, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a164.pdf>.
- [16] **I.J. TANEJA**, Digit's Order Selfie Numbers: Factorial and Square-Root, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 140, pp. 1-86, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a140.pdf>.
- [17] **I.J. TANEJA**, S-gonal and Centered Polygonal Selfie Numbers, and Connections with Binomials Coefficients, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 43, pp. 1-42, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a43.pdf>.
- [18] **I.J. TANEJA**, Crazy, Selfie, Fibonacci, Triangular, Amicable Types Representations of Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 3, pp. 1-140, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a03.pdf>.
- [19] **I.J. TANEJA**, 2019 In Numbers, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529103>.
- [20] **I.J. TANEJA**, Permutable Powers Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 15, 2019, pp. 1-227, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2566445>.
- [21] **I.J. TANEJA**, Triangular-Type Selfie Numebrs, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 17, 2019, pp. 1-91, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567571>
- [22] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 18, 2019, pp. 1-116, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571472>.
- [23] **I.J. TANEJA**, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 19, 2019, pp. 1-233, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572044>.

- [24] **I.J. TANEJA**, Simultaneous Representations of Selfie Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and Triangular Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 20, 2019, pp. 1-115, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2574136>.
- [25] **I.J. TANEJA**, Quadratic-Type Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 25, 2019, pp. 1-315, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2577472>.
- [26] **I.J. TANEJA**, Factorial-Type Selfie Numbers in Digit's Order, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 06, 2019, pp. 1-243, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2585586>.
- [27] **I.J. TANEJA**, Factorial-Type Selfie Numbers in Reverse Order of Digits, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 06, 2019, pp. 1-227, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2585599>.
- [28] **I.J. TANEJA**, Concatenation-Type Selfie Numbers With Factorial and Square-Root, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 08, 2019, pp. 1-43, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2587751>.
- [29] **I.J. TANEJA**, Cubic-Type Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 12, 2019, pp. 1-150, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2591257>.
- [30] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers: Basic Operations, **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 26, 2019, pp. 1-134. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2609143>.
- [31] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients and Fibonacci Numbers. **Zenodo**, Open Access, March 30, 2019, pp. 1-148. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2617290>.
- [32] **I.J. TANEJA**, Triangular-Type Selfie Numbers: Digit's Order. **Zenodo**, Open Access, April 11, 2019, pp. 1-240. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2636787>.
- [33] **I.J. TANEJA**, Triangular-Type Selfie Numbers: Reverse Order of Digits. **Zenodo**, Open Access, April 14, 2019, pp. 1-249. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2639099>.
-